

PROCEEDINGS OF THE

CRIME PREVENTION THROUGH ENVIRONMENTAL DESIGN CONFERENCE 2023

Organised by
SCHOOL OF PLANNING AND ARCHITECTURE, NEW DELHI
AND
ISAC CENTRE FOR BUILT ENVIRONMENT POLICY

Held on 21st September 2023
at School of Planning and Architecture,
New Delhi

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School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi was established in 1941 and is an institution of National Importance under an Act of Parliament under the Ministry of Education, Government of India.

ISAC Centre for Built Environment Policy is an integral part of Information Sharing and Analysis Center, A Global Non-Profit working on Cyber Security, Physical Security and Professional Ethics.

PREFACE

On September 21st, 2023, the School of Planning and Architecture, in collaboration with the ISAC Centre for Built Environment Policy, hosted a conference centered around Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED).

School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi, an Institute of National Importance created under an Act of Parliament is at the forefront of built environment-related education, consultancy, and research. The conference was jointly organised with Information Sharing and Analysis Center, India which is a Non-Governmental Organisation working closely with the government on issues related to security, both physical and cyber.

With a focus on using changes in the built environment to prevent crime, the conference aimed to promote collaboration and knowledge exchange among academics, policymakers, and stakeholders.

The event was graced by distinguished figures from Indian politics, administration, and academia. Ms. Swati Maliwal, Chairperson of the Delhi Commission for Women, served as the honorable chief guest, her active involvement in crime prevention in the national capital adding significance to the occasion. As a special guest, Ms. D. Thara IAS, Additional Secretary of MoHUA, left a lasting impact with her insights gained from her extensive career and keen understanding of infrastructural nuances related to crime prevention.

The conference commenced with an inaugural address by Prof. Dr. Anil Dewan, Head of the Department of Architecture at SPA, followed by a keynote speech by Prof. Dr. Sewa Ram, also from SPA. Both emphasized the critical role of the built environment in reducing crime incidents, citing examples from Delhi's infrastructure such as flyovers and parks to illustrate how design tweaks can save lives.

Two informative panel discussions were conducted.

The first, 'Smart City Security,' moderated by Prof. Dr. Mahavir, featured insights from experts like Group Captain P. Aanand Naidu from ISAC and K.C. Mittal, former Chair of the Bar Council of India.

The second panel, 'Road Map for including CPTED in Buildings, Campuses & Parks,' moderated by Dr. Parama Mitra of SPA Bhopal, delved into the practical implementation of CPTED, including its application in hospitals, presented by Prof. Dr. Nirupam Madaan from AIIMS Delhi.

Following a networking lunch, students and professors from across the country had the opportunity to present their research findings to esteemed judges and invitees. The papers showcased rich and impactful contributions to the CPTED discourse.

The conference concluded on a high note with the release of proceedings by dignitaries, marking a fulfilling and successful day of collaboration and knowledge sharing in the pursuit of creating safer and more secure built environments.

The collection of groundbreaking research on CPTED concepts conducted by scholars nationwide is presented in the proceedings.

Conference Proceedings

The research papers were selected after rigorous screening and peer review. This was preceded by an abstract selection process. Out of many abstracts only limited were selected as full papers for presentation in the conference.

The peer review process was done in collaboration with Qeios, which is an open peer review based Journal.

All the papers have been finally uploaded into the Zenodo archive for their easy web presence and indexation. This step also makes the citation of the papers very convenient.

The organisers are very thankful to all the people who made this conference a success.

Contact: cbep@isacfoundation.org or cpted@spa.ac.in

Photos, Top Left: Prof. Dr Sewa Ram, Ms. D Thara, Additional Secretary, Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs; Top Right: Ms. Swati Maliwal, Chairperson, Delhi Commission for Women, Prof. Dr. Meenakshi Dhote, Dean Academics, and Group Captain P Aanand Naidu. Middle: Left to Right: Prof Dr Hina Zia, JMI; Prof. Dr. R Biswas, Prof. Dr. Anil Dewan, Dr. Raja Singh, Dr. Priyanka Kochhar. Bottom: Left to Right: Prof. Dr. Nirupam Madaan, Prof. Dr. Anil Dewan, Prof. Manoj Mathur, Dr. Shuvojit Sarkar, Mr. Rajshekhar Pullabhatla

Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design Conference 2023

Organisers: School of Planning and Architecture, New Delhi and ISAC Centre for Built Environment Policy.

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CONFERENCE ON CRIME PREVENTION THROUGH ENVIRONMENTAL DESIGN

SCHOOL OF PLANNING AND ARCHITECTURE, NEW DELHI

DEPARTMENT OF ARCHITECTURE

21st September 2023

Co organised by ISAC Centre for Built Environment Policy,
an integral part of the Information Sharing and Analysis Center

INAUGURAL

- 09:00 - 09:10 Inaugural speech by Prof Dr Anil Dewan, HOD_Arch, SPA Delhi
09:10 - 09:20 Address by Dean Academics, Prof Dr Meenakshi Dhote, SPA Delhi
09:20 - 09:30 Message from Publishing partner Qeios: Gabrielle Marinello
09:30 - 09:40 Address by Director, Prof Dr Yogesh Singh, SPA Delhi
09:40 - 10:00 SPA Key Address by Prof. Dr Sewa Ram, SPA Delhi (Safe Streets-Noida)

KEYNOTE

- 10:00 - 10:15 Keynote by Special Guest, Ms. D. Thara, IAS, Addl Sect, MoHUA
10:15 - 10:30 Address by Chief Guest, Ms Swati Maliwal, Chairperson, DCW
10:30 - 10:40 Vote of Thanks by Group Captain P Aanand Naidu, Director, ISAC
10:40 - 11:00 High Tea

EXPERT DISCUSSION I

- 11:00 - 11:50 Discussion I: Smart City Security
Prof. Dr Mahavir, Former Professor and Dean/Planning Expert (Moderator)
R Srinivas, Former TCPO, MoHUA
Group Captain P Aanand Naidu, ISAC
Prof Dr P.S.N. Rao, SPA Delhi
Prof Dr Mandeep Singh, IPU
Advocate K.C. Mittal, Former Chairman, Bar Council of Delhi
Prof Dr G Subbaiyan, NIT Trichy
Dr Gurkirpal Singh, PTU

EXPERT DISCUSSION II

- 11:50 - 12:40 Discussion II: Roadmap for including CPTED in Buildings, Campuses & Parks
Dr Parama Mitra, SPA Bhopal (Moderator)
Prof Manoj Mathur, SPA Delhi
Prof Dr T Srinivas, NIT Trichy
Prof Dr Vandana Sehgal, AKTU Lucknow
Prof Dr Nirupam Madaan, AIIMS Delhi
Rajshekhar Pullabhatla, ISAC
Dr Shuvojit Sarkar, SPA Delhi
Karthik Mohan, CET-Trivandrum

CONFERENCE

- 12:40 - 13:25 Networking Lunch
13:25 - 13:35 Welcoming the Judges: [See Page 2 for Complete Proceedings Detail]
Chief Judge: Ms Manju Paul, Commissioner, DDA
Prof. Dr V K Paul, SPA Delhi | Ar. J K Gupta, Renowned Academician |
Prof Dr R Biswas, SPA Delhi | Dr Priyanka Kochhar, Researcher
Prof. Dr Hina Zia, JMI
13:35 - 17:01 Conference Proceedings | 14 Presentations from across the country
17:01 - 17:20 Release of Proceedings by Ms Manju Paul, Prof Dr Anil Dewan and PA Naidu.
17:20 - 17:30 Vote of Thanks by Dr Khushal Matai
Co-ordinator: Dr Raja Singh | Compere: Pavani B

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A Study of the Urban Nightlife of Delhi and its Impact on Safety

S Ahsan

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Author Details

Sobia Ahsan is an Architect with a Masters in Urban Regeneration. She has more than 9 years of experience and has worked on several architectural and urban projects of different scales and typologies.

In her academic career, she has taught at the School of Art and Architecture, Sushant University as an Associate Professor and K.R. Mangalam University as an Assistant Professor. She has also worked in the Housing and Urban Projects Wing of Delhi Development Authority and at Dimension Architects, a Delhi based architectural firm. Currently she is working on her PhD proposal. Her work builds on the interdisciplinary research and intersections of architecture with society, culture and history. She is currently curious and researching about the migration histories in India and its connection with the urban landscape.

Abstract

Delhi, the capital of India, has many facets as an urban space. It is a city that attracts vast number of people for better job opportunities and for quality education. Delhi has a rich heritage that attracts tourists from all over the world. Digitalization and current working trends have transformed the concept of working hours in the city. Many MNC's provide flexible working hours to their employees, while in some cases, long working hours are required. This has created an opportunity for the nighttime economy to grow. But the opportunities provided by the nightlife are counteracted by the various challenges. People's safety is argued to be most compromised in the spaces at night.

In this context, the paper attempts to represent active nightlife as an approach that acts as a driving force for the city in terms of well-being and safety. It argues that spaces that are vibrant with nightlife establishments are comparatively safer than spaces that do not account for any such establishments. One of the objectives of the study is to explore how nightlife establishments contribute to the social capital and public life of cities. Another objective is to identify the actors involved in the production of active nightlife spaces.

The study elucidates the argument by reviewing theoretical evidence and case studies. The relationship between nightlife and urban safety is explored, and various reasons for an active nightlife culture are identified through literature review.

The inferences are then applied to various urban spaces in Delhi. These urban spaces are selected based on the extent of activities happening at night. Through fieldwork, the material and immaterial structures of the nightlife establishments are documented and then dismantled to understand the nature of these areas, and how they operate and function among their people. The paper unfolds the potential of government regulations in enhancing the nightlife of the city. The paper concludes with specific suggestions for the improvement of nightlife in a public space where required.

Keywords: Nightlife, Urban Safety, Working Hours, Diverse Activities, Social Inclusion, Government Regulations

1. INTRODUCTION

Every city has a prevalent lifestyle that includes its people, place and creativity, which defines its character. Delhi is a cosmopolitan city where people are open to embracing new ideas and lifestyle. It is a city of professional business careers and foremost of upper and middle class with endless opportunities. The rapid urbanization over the years has led to the demographic changes in Delhi. Apart from the natural increase there has been a large-scale migration. As per the Census of India 2011, the total population of Delhi was 16,787,941, with a percentage decadal growth of 21.21. A paper on Urbanization and Urban Crime in India (Gupta, n.d.) established through an empirical investigation established that there is a relationship between the growth in population and crime rate in Delhi. A report released by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) stated that Delhi is one of the top four crime affected cities in India. The data revealed that the crime rate increased six times in the last ten years. (Gupta, n.d.). As per NCRB data, Delhi recorded 13,892 cases of crimes against women in 2021. The data showed that on an average, over two girls were raped every day in Delhi in 2021. The national capital also recorded the highest number of kidnapping cases among the 19 metropolitan cities in 2022. Delhi recorded 36% of the robberies during the night time from 8:00 p.m. to midnight. (Singh, 2022) In an industry chamber Assocham survey, a majority of 65 percent of women in Delhi interviewed said they felt insecure working night shifts (PTI, 2008). With the rising cases of crime, safety has become an important factor in determining the wellbeing of people.

According to Gupta (n.d.), people perceive night as the most suitable time for most types of crimes due to the psychological support of the dark and less patrolling by the police. There exists a pattern in the occurrence of crime with respect to space and time. However, it would be wrong to say that all spaces at night function in a similar manner. The reasons for which people occupy and use the space during the day and night vary depending on various socio-cultural and economic factors. In Delhi, with the quickening tempo of modern life and prolonged working hours, i.e., with the coming up of BPO's and other job-related activities, there is a development of a nightlife culture that drives the economy of the city and also provides opportunity for leisure to its people. Some of the options available to the public include a number of bars, pubs, discotheques, eateries, and coffee shops.

1.1 Aim and Research Argument

In this discourse, where most of the studies have associated nighttime with anti-social uses and crime, this paper attempts to draw attention to the opportunities that the night time presents to the people of a city. It is argued in this paper that a healthy night time culture could help in improving the well-being of a city. The aim is to provide a theoretical framework for understanding the inter-relationship between the production, regulation and consumption of a safe urban nightlife in a city. The objective of the study is to revisit the concepts of urban safety through the lens of "time" and understand how public spaces are appropriated by various activities during the night time.

Some of the research questions are as follows:

Who uses the space in the night and for what purpose?

Do activities in public spaces improve or threaten nightlife?

Does a sense of territoriality at night reduce the fear of crime among the people?

The underlying hypothesis is that a more varied pattern of overlapping activities and attractions involving a more diverse range of participants is likely to be better for public order, for sustaining essential public services and for the long-term viability of the place.

1.2 Methodology

In this paper, a range of literature reviews have been conducted to gather information and understanding from previous research on Urban Nightlife and its relationship with Safety. The literature review is divided into two parts. The first part looks into the theories of Urban Nightlife from socio-economic perspective. It explores the various modalities through which Urban Spaces and Nightlife can be channeled for the well-being of a city and its people. The works of Robert Williams, Jane Jacob and Oscar Newmann serve very well in formulating a framework that is applied to the selected cases of Delhi to measure the level of safety and well-being of a nightlife. The second part attempts to define Safety based on the perception of crime in a given space and time.

The next section of the paper explores city dynamics. The night time usage has been analyzed for the four study areas of Delhi namely Matia Mahal, Jama Masjid, Nehru Place Complex, Connaught Place and India Gate Precinct. The case study selection is based on the level of activities present during the night time in these public spaces. The intent of choosing the public spaces is to explore the multiple variables responsible for an active nightlife in a city. The area of study is limited to public hangouts, street eateries and open restaurants. Pubs, discotheques and 24x7 retail shops are not included in the study as they function in a closed and controlled environment.

All the cases are documented and analyzed through an exploratory and observational method. A gender-based user count is conducted to understand how many people use the place at a given time of the night. The perception of fear is analyzed in detail through a manual interview method for a sample size of 20 users for each case study. The role of Government with respect to nightlife has also been analyzed by studying the government regulations and recommendations of Delhi Master Plan 2041. To further enhance the investigation, the parameters drawn from the literature reviews are linked to the three modalities proposed by Robert Williams. This helped in developing a structured framework to study the safety conditions of the selected cases. These parameters are territoriality, inclusivity of genders, visibility, diverse activities and surveillance.

Based on the analysis, the paper identifies the potential and possible gaps in each case study. The case studies are compared to measure the perception of fear and the results are drawn with suggestions to improve the nightlife for the well-being and safety of the people.

Chart 1: Methodology Diagram

Source: Author

2. READING THE URBAN NIGHTLIFE

The night is a part of us and influences our social, cultural and economic lives. From the early 1990s onwards, the evening and night economies and, more broadly, the 24-hour city started to develop, with many metropolitan cities including the nightlife sector in their regeneration plans in various countries. Just like the daytime economy, the night time economy has become vital for the regeneration of cities. Active night spaces are among the city's urban cultures that possess a rich source of everyday life. This can be regarded as an important part of establishing a city's cultural identity and improving the wellbeing of the city.

As a result, nightlife districts with a variety of restaurants and clubs have started to develop in various larger cities, providing jobs and attracting tourists and visitors. There is, however, a pervasive culture of fear surrounding nightlife districts, which makes the nightlife different from the day. People who go out at night are usually seen as problematic in discourses that involve negative cultural signifiers such as drinking, making noise, and hanging out in groups. (Ilse van Liempt et al., 2014)

Urban environments are created by a complex range of “*social, cultural, legal, spatial, and temporal dimensions*” and characterized by particular “*physical infrastructure of buildings, roads, transit systems, land uses, design and architecture*”. In studying the urban night time spaces, it is imperative to understand the complexities of these dimensions.

In an attempt to understand the concept of nightlife, several scholarly studies have been discussed. In 'The Production of Spaces' Henri Lefebvre distinguishes various types of spaces. He proposes the division of space into designated (signified, specialized) areas and into areas that are prohibited, spaces of work and spaces for leisure, and into daytime and night time spaces. He further explains how certain activities came to be permitted in particular areas at night that are prohibited during the day. (Lefebvre, 1991)

(Williams, 2008) builds on the works of Henri Lefebvre in reference to "night time spaces". He refers to night spaces as being socially mediated. He states that these spaces do not exist prior to, or apart from, human practices and the social relationships that seek to appropriate the darkness in its numerous human uses and meanings. Williams argues that night time is a vital dimension of daily activities and needs to be distinguished from the day to better interpret spatial practices after dark. He suggests theorizing night's implications for societal order and disorder by spatializing time and temporalizing space. His work is very useful in understanding the social construction of the night. Williams, in his work, provides strategies to affect the reordering of the space at night. He delineates three modalities, namely: channeling, marginalization, and exclusion. The intention of these modalities is to bring safety by asserting social order at night. The modality of channeling directs activities into socially appropriate places. As a reterritorializing modality, Channeling involves strategies of surveillance, illumination, and other discourses that stipulate the appropriate places to be at night. The second modality of marginalization spatially segregates people from other parts of the city by categorizing them as socially inferior and dangerous. A common form of marginalization is informal social code and zoning regulations. The third modality of exclusion is a type of spatial segregation that involves erecting barriers to create a protected space. It uses the technology of access control. Defensible spaces are one such example where people lock themselves away by using the technologies of surveillance and by installing lights.

These three modalities have been applied on the selected case studies as a framework to identify the factors that bring safety in the night spaces.

Other than Lefebvre and Williams, there are other scholars who have theorized the spatial aspect of the night. (Bretthauer, 1999) stated that the night spaces of a city change the social practices and meanings of the physical landscape which otherwise contains the same features throughout the 24-hour cycle. (Cresswell, 1996) examined the officially permitted and unofficially appropriated discourses in a city at night. To make the city run efficiently and safely, businesses order night by depicting it in commercial terms for consumption of their products. Businesses and governments often work together. **This proposition has been explored in this paper by selecting night spaces that are mostly commercial in nature and by examining the role of government in regulating these spaces at night.**

2.1 Theorizing Urban Nightlife, Crime and Safety

Having explored the social theories on nightlife production in the aforementioned section, in this section, the paper deliberates on the co-relation between nightlife and crime. The paper critically examines the theory of perceptions of fear at night time. Later in this section, the concept of Urban Safety is reviewed to identify ways in which nightlife could be appropriated for safe public uses.

A study on Understanding and Preventing Violence, examines the current state of evidence on public perceptions and reactions to violent offenses and violent victimization. It examines

the cues to danger that individuals confront in everyday life. It is evident that people perceive crime in geographic terms as dangerous or safe zones. It was observed from the study that known places were perceived as safer than the unknown places due to cognitive consistency. This means that territoriality plays an important role in instilling a sense of fear or safety in the people. Another cue to danger is darkness. Fear of crime is generally higher at night, and usually people avoid going out at night due to fear. The second cue as per the study is the presence of bystanders or companions; the presence of others normally acts to reduce or alleviate the fear that individuals would feel if alone (Warr, 1994).

This brings us to look at the work of Jane Jacobs in her book 'The Death and Life of Great American Cities' where she introduces the concept of "eyes on the street". She has argued that people on the street provide informal surveillance, leading to a safe urban environment. The study by (Jacob, 1992) and (Warr, 1994) provides a first reference point to classify a space as safe or unsafe. This concept can be applied to nightlife spaces as well.

At this point, it is much needed to look into the meanings of safety with respect to the urban environment as discussed by various scholars to formulate an assessment tool that can be applied to nightlife spaces.

O.A. Rastyapina and N.V. Korosteleva, in their research article titled 'Urban Safety Development Methods', define Urban Safety as a built environment that ensures safe life of the population on the basis of a combination of factors. These factors forming local urban safety are divided into groups: natural, architectural, social, environmental, techno-genic, infrastructural, and urban. They argue that an analysis of urban safety factors allows one to assess the level of livability and safety of an inhabited area. (Rastyapina O.A, Korosteleva N.V, 2016)

Making cities safe is one of the aspirations reflected in Goal 11 of the Agenda 2030 and the New Urban Agenda. The United Nations Guidelines on Safer Cities and Settlements provide a conceptual framework for safety and security. There are two aspects of safety and security mentioned: actual and perceived. The perceived component describes how people see insecurity via the prism of fear and anxiety, while the actual dimension pertains to the possibility of being a victim.

The concept starts with the observation that inadequate urban development and local governance, along with patterns of social and territorial exclusion, can result in crime and violence. Given this perspective, ensuring urban safety and security requires a citywide and participatory process to address the multiple causes and risk factors for crime, violence and insecurity in cities and human settlements and to put in place the factors that protect against those causes and risks. (UN-Habitat, 2012)

In the above statement, local governance and social and spatial inclusion are identified as the essential components of maintaining safety and security in cities.

Oscar Newmann's literary work "Defensible Space" is based on the research conducted by him to investigate the reasons for crime and social isolation in housing areas. In this research, a set of parameters were identified that are linked with crime and disorder, making the place "unsafe". He outlined five factors that would need to be present to make a space safe. (HRF, n.d.)

1. **Territory** - There must be a sense of belonging to the space.
2. **Surveillance** - The physical characteristics of a space must offer a person the ability to know what is happening around them.

3. **Image** - The space must be structured in such a way that it can provide a sense of security, when it is being used.
4. **Milieu** - Features of the space must provide a sense of security, such as its proximity to a police station, or a busy commercial area near a police station.
5. **Safe Areas** - There must be a secure adjacent area that offers higher-level services in the other four important points that can be accessed if the primary space is occupied.

Most of the scholarship on nightlife discussed above puts night time under the pervasive notion of fear and crime. However, safety is also attributed to the spatiality of time and temporality of space. Another significant work by (Zaki & Ngesan, 2012) has been reviewed as it discusses the opportunities that nightlife offers. The study proposed the concept of 'Night City' which was based on the agglomeration of night activities that create momentum and create different attractions to attract people. The research argued that nocturnal life improves the quality of city environment at night time as it increases the economic value of the place. As an outcome of this study, the town of Alor Gajah was redesigned to attract local and foreign visitors.

These theories help to draw certain parameters that can be used to identify the safety condition of the place. These parameters are **active surveillance, social inclusion, territoriality, diverse activity, image, visibility and public presence**.

3. SITUATING THE URBAN NIGHTLIFE IN INDIAN CONTEXT

The growth of night time activities over the past few decades has driven the entertainment economy around the world. In recent years, many governments across the world have crystallized around the vision to create the '24-hour city'. Such initiatives focus on extending the working hours of the day and integrating them with the night time economy, thereby stretching the 'vitality and viability' of urban areas across a longer time span. (Hadfield, 2011)

Although the concept of nightlife culture is not new to Indian society, the pattern of nightlife utility is changing in light of the contemporary environment due to changes in working culture and an increase in the availability of disposable income and leisure time. This section looks at the current status of nightlife culture in Delhi with respect to safety of the people.

For the purpose of this study, four urban areas with concentrated socio-economic activities are investigated for their nightlife culture. All the cases hold a strong potential to attract people at varying times of the day and night. The activity pattern of these spaces has been studied with respect to the services, time of use, connectivity, participant profiling and government regulations. Urban spaces with inactive nightlife are also analyzed to draw a comparison between the active and inactive spaces. The first area of study is the street of Matia Mahal in Jama Masjid, which has a mix of activities during the night time. The second study area is Nehru Place which is a commercial and financial district center of Delhi. The third area is Connaught Place and the fourth area is India Gate Precinct. It is an urban public space that attracts tourists and is a site for picnics and weekend hangouts.

3.1 Times of Use

To identify the night time activity pattern, various time slots were identified during which the activity of the space usually changes. The time period ranges from 6:00 p.m. to 12:00 a.m. Each case study area was analyzed on the basis of the dominant practices.

3.2 Dominant Practices

The spatial distribution of dominant practices

- Where is it happening?
- What is happening
- Participant profiling: who is involved
- Governance and regulation: signage and zones of illegality, visible police, and private security practices

A user count was conducted to measure the number of men and women in the selected cases. A 20-minute time slot at two consecutive time frames was chosen based on the presence of maximum activity in those time slots.

4. CASE STUDIES

Delhi is fast developing into a huge nightlife hub. The major nightlife venues in the city are either in the central or southern parts of Delhi. The major activities happening in these venues are related to entertainment, leisure or food.

4.1 Matia Mahal, Jama Masjid

Old Delhi, popularly known as “purani dilli”, has few streets that are wide awake during the night time. Matia Mahal is one such area, exactly opposite Gate No. 1 of Jama Masjid. The place gets its name from an actual palace that once existed in the area. Today, the area has a presence of many restaurants and hotels that function beyond midnight. It is a high-density area and encounters huge footfalls throughout the day. The visitors are both locals and tourists.

Figure 1: Map showing Matia Mahal and its neighborhood

Source: Author

- Commercial (Eateries and Shops)
- ⊘ Metro Station (Jama Masjid)
- ⋯ Vehicular Road/ Potential Axis for Street Revitalization

4.1.1 Factors influencing the nightlife

- Matia Mahal Street is famous for its late-night makeshift eateries and restaurants. The street has a mixed-use typology with shops and eateries on the ground floor and residential space on the upper floors. There are few guest houses and hotels along the street. It is observed that most of the eateries close their shops post-midnight.
- The road abutting Jama Masjid is known as Urdu Bazaar. This road has a presence of publishers, calligraphers and many eateries. Other than eateries, most of the shops shut by evening. It is the informal hawkers that continue their business until late at night. The activity pattern shows that loading and unloading of goods also keeps the place quite active during the night.

- **Connectivity:** The street is well connected with the main road. As far as public transportation is concerned, Metro provides an affordable and convenient mode of travel.
- **Policing and Crime:** Since this area is in close proximity to a monument, it attracts tourists. There are many constables posted in the area. CCTV cameras are installed at multiple locations. There are ample street lights in the area.

Time of Use	Activities	Participant Profiling
06:00 p.m. – 08:00 p.m.	Shopping	Men, Women, Children
08:00 p.m. – 11:00 p.m.	Shopping, Eating, Loading and Unloading of Goods	Men, Women
11:00 p.m. – 12:00 a.m.	Eating, Loading and Unloading of Goods	Men

Table 1: Time of Use versus Activities & Participant Profiling – Matia Mahal, Jama Masjid
Source: Author

Timing	Men	Women	Ratio of Women to Men
10:40 p.m. – 11:00 p.m.	102	32	1:3.2
11:00 p.m. – 11:20 p.m.	90	18	1:5

Table 2: User Count at the entry of the Street from Jama Masjid Gate Number 1 on a weekday
Source: Author

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 2: Late-night activities on Urdu Bazaar Road and Figure 3: Vibrant Street of Matia Mahal at midnight
Source: Author

4.1.2 Safety Analysis

The Likert scale method is used to analyze the user perception of safety for each case study. This is done by interviewing a random sample size of 20 people. The safety component is measured on five parameters and scores are given using the Measurable Indicator Scoring

Technique as used by (Ngesan & Karim, 2011). Indicator 5 being the highest and 1 being the lowest.

Parameters	Safety Indicators (1-5)					Mean	Score (1-5)				
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5
Lighting	0	0	9	6	5	3.8					
Police Surveillance	2	4	14	0	0	2.6					
Accessibility	0	0	5	9	6	4.05					
Presence of Public	0	0	2	9	9	4.35					
Sense of Belonging	0	1	10	5	4	3.6					
Score							0	0	1	3	1
Percentage Score							-	-	20	60	20

Table 3: User Perception Safety Score for Matia Mahal, Jama Masjid
Source: Author

Chart 2: Chart showing the User Perception on Safety
Source: Author

4.1.3 Findings

It is observed that the area experiences a mix of footfall owing to a diverse range of activities. Both men and women use the space. However, at night, the women-to-men percentage decreases gradually from a ratio of 1:3.2 to 1:5. This is due to the closing of shops and loading and unloading activities. The user perception of safety is average or above average, as people rated the area between 4-5 (scores) on all the parameters.

4.2 Nehru Place District Centre

Nehru Place is an important commercial, financial, and business center in Delhi. It was planned in the 1960s by Delhi Development Authority as a local community center and was originally called Kalkaji Complex. By the 1980s, it was renamed Nehru Place. Over the years, it has started functioning as a Regional Commercial Centre and is now widely considered to be a major information technology hub in South Asia. It is a confluence of the informal and formal sectors, with a footfall of nearly 1,30,000 people daily from all corners of Delhi. However, only 7% of visitors come from a 2 km radius. The main complex is four stories, with many offices, computer retailers, printing shops and eateries and hundreds of informal hawkers occupying the open spaces of the complex.(Shakti Sustainable Energy Foundation, 2017)

Figure 4: Map showing Nehru Place District Centre and its neighborhood

Source: Author

- Commercial (Nehru Place Complex)
- Institutional (Eros Hotel)
- Residential Area
- Metro Line
- Bus Stop

Figure 5: Map showing Entry/ Exit to Nehru Place and Inactive Spaces during the Night
Source: Author

4.2.1 Factors influencing the nightlife

- Nehru Place complex shuts down at 8:00 p.m., after which the area becomes completely inactive. There are no regulated night time activities in the complex making the place extremely isolated and secluded.
- There are several entry and exit points to the complex. But they are inconspicuous and unwelcoming. There is no clear physical axis for visual connectivity. In the night, there is not enough street lighting which again creates a sense of fear, making it a dull space during late evenings.
- The northern edge of the complex facing the Astha Kunj Road attracts few visitors in the late evenings due to the presence of Inox Insignia. Both men and women can be seen using this public space.
- The arterial and sub-arterial roads offset the complex in such a way that they create a non-physical boundary between the complex and the residential colonies in close proximity.
- **Connectivity:** Nehru Place is well connected with the other parts of the city through the Outer Ring Road. It is easily accessible through the metro and buses; however, the operating time of these public transport services is only before midnight.
- **Policing and Crime:** There are many negative/inactive spaces in the complex that invite illegal activities and increase the risk of crime, especially at night. In the past decade, various cases of robbery and a terrorist attack on December 28, 2005, have been noted in the Nehru Place area. A rape case was reported on April 27, 2012, and another terror attack happened on September 25, 2009.

Time of Use	Activities	Participant Profiling
06:00 p.m. – 08:00 p.m.	Office Crowd, Shopping, Eating	Men, Women
08:00 p.m. – 11:00 p.m.	Inactive	Mostly Men
11:00 p.m. – 12:00 a.m.	Inactive	Men

Table 4: Time of Use versus Activities & Participant Profiling – Nehru Place District Centre
Source: Author

Timing	Men	Women	Ratio of Women to Men
09:00 p.m. – 09:20 p.m.	40	2	1:20
09:20 p.m. – 09:40 p.m.	19	0	0:19

Table 5: User Count at Entry Point A on a weekday
Source: Author

Timing	Men	Women	Ratio of Women to Men
09:00 p.m. – 09:20 p.m.	60	19	1:3.1
09:20 p.m. – 09:40 p.m.	31	7	1:4.4

Table 6: User Count at Entry Point B on a weekday
Source: Author

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 6: Activities in front of the Entry Point A; Figure 7: Open Plaza at 8:00 p.m. (Space-2)
Source: Author

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 8: Open Plaza at 11:00 p.m. (Space-3); Figure 9: Entry Point B from the Aastha Kunj Road

Source: Author

4.2.2 Safety Analysis

Parameters	Safety Indicators (1-5)					Mean	Score (1-5)				
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5
Lighting	4	8	8	0	0	2.2					
Police Surveillance	3	10	5	1	0	2.1					
Accessibility	1	11	7	1	0	2.4					
Presence of Public	12	8	0	0	0	1.4					
Sense of Belonging	10	10	0	0	0	1.5					
Score							0	4	1	0	0
Percentage Score							-	80	20	-	-

Table 7: User Perception Safety Score for Nehru Place District Centre

Source: Author

Chart 3: Chart showing the User Perception on Safety for Nehru Place District Centre

Source: Author

4.2.3 Findings

A user count was conducted at two main entry and exit points. It is observed that at entry point A, the presence of women is negligible, with a ratio of 1 woman per 20 men. This is

apparent due to an inactive edge with minimal activities. The other entry/ exit point B close to INOX showed comparatively a better ratio of 1: 4 due to the presence of a cinema hall and small eateries. Based on the survey Nehru Place scored very low on safety.

4.3 Connaught Place

Connaught Place, ‘CP’ is one of the largest financial, commercial and business centers in Delhi. It is a vibrant recreational and institutional space that attracts local, regional, and international visitors throughout the year.

Figure 10: Map showing Connaught Place
Source: Author

4.3.1 Factors influencing the nightlife

- The closing time of most of the formal establishments at CP is 9:00 p.m. Being a low-density area with low residential profile, this area mostly remains inactive during night time. The only active places are the bars and pubs, a few eateries and street dhaba's.¹ P and L-Block of the outercircle continues to operate till 11:00 p.m. – 12:00 a.m. Urban Space-1 marked in Figure 10 represents an active night space due to the presence of an eatery (Jain Chawal Vale) and Urban Space-2 in the same figure represents an entire edge of L-Block lined by eateries.
- There is enough street lighting and CCTV surveillance, but still the activities are concentrated only in and around a few eateries and restaurants. These spots are identified as potential nodes that can be further redesigned to make the area vibrant and safe during the night.
- **Connectivity:** This area is the heart of Delhi and is easily accessible from every part of the city. There are many modes of public transportation available for the people. Apart from auto-rickshaws, cab and bus services, Metro provides an affordable transport facility.

¹ As per Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary, Dhaba is a small cheap restaurant where Punjabi food is served, with basic furniture and facilities, and often with an open front and tables outside.

- Policing and Crime:** The majority of the reported robberies and assaults in and around Connaught Place are purportedly carried out by vagrants and addicts who squat on the pavements of CP. Most of the victims are women and party crowds who frequent late-night clubs and eateries. In 2012, a notorious gang targeted and robbed customers who were using ATMs after hours. After Sashastra Seema Bal jawan was fatally stabbed in 2015, it sparked worry from the Ministry of Home Affairs, which claimed that the rag picker was to blame (Sharma, 2016)

Figure 11: Connaught Place Market at 11:00 p.m.

Source: Author

Time of Use	Activities	Participant Profiling
06:00 p.m. – 08:00 p.m.	Shopping	Men, Women, Children
08:00 p.m. – 11:00 p.m.	Mostly Inactive (Eateries only at a few locations)	Men, Women
11:00 p.m. – 12:00 a.m.	Mostly Inactive (Eateries only at a few locations)	Men, Women

Table 8: Time of Use versus Activities & Participant Profiling – Connaught Place

Source: Author

Figure 12: Map showing Urban Space-1 at CP
Source: Author

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figure 13: Active space outside an eatery in P-Block, CP
Figure 14: Area close to the active space in P-Block with a cinema hall across the road
Source: Author

Timing	Men	Women	Ratio of Women to Men
10:40 p.m. – 11:00 p.m.	95	45	1:2
11:00 p.m. – 11:20 p.m.	90	38	1:2.4

Table 9: User Count at the Urban Space-1 on a weekday
Source: Author

Figure 15: Map showing Urban Space-2 at CP
Source: Author

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 16: Active space outside eateries in L-Block, CP.
Figure 17: Restaurants and cafes in front of the eateries across the road
Source: Author

Timing	Men	Women	Ratio of Women to Men
10:40 p.m. – 11:00 p.m.	24	10	1:2.4
11:00 p.m. – 11:20 p.m.	23	10	1:2.3

Table 10: User Count at the Urban Space-2 on a weekday
Source: Author

4.3.2 Safety Analysis

Parameters	Safety Indicators (1-5)					Mean	Score (1-5)				
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5
Lighting	0	0	8	10	2	3.7					
Police Surveillance	0	0	2	8	10	4.4					
Accessibility	0	2	5	8	5	3.8					
Presence of Public	0	0	4	10	6	4.1					
Sense of Belonging	0	5	8	5	2	3.2					
Score							0	0	1	4	0
Percentage Score							-	-	20	80	-

Table 11: User Perception Safety Score for Connaught Place Eateries in P and L Block
Source: Author

Chart 4: User Perception on Safety for Connaught Place Eateries at P and L Block
Source: Author

4.3.3 Findings

The eateries at Connaught Place attracts young crowd, both men and women. The women to men ratio in this case is 1:2. As per the survey, people rated the area on the higher side of the coring scale. 80% of the score was given to rating 4. **4.4 India Gate**

India Gate was designed by Sir Edwin Lutyens in 1931. It is situated in the heart of New Delhi, is a prominent landmark and commemorates the 90,000 soldiers of the Indian Army.

India Gate is a part of Central Vista, a 3.2 km stretch that houses Rashtrapati Bhawan, India Gate, Parliament House, North and South Block among others. It is the monument that celebrates India and its achievements and is a venue for the mass celebrations. In 2019, the Central Government announced the redevelopment of the Central Vista to give the place a new identity. After three years, on September 08, 2022, the area was inaugurated by the P.M. and was thrown open to the public. The revamping consisted of the reorganization of public spaces and strengthening of recreational facilities. For better connectivity a pedestrian underpass has been developed to manage public footfall and ensure smooth public transit of the public. There are defined parking spaces for visitors and tourists and for surveillance 300 CCTV cameras have been installed.

Figure 18: Map showing India Gate Precinct

Source: Author

4.4.1 Factors influencing the nightlife

- India Gate is a public space that caters to all age groups. India Gate is one of the most visited public spaces in Delhi at night. It is a place for social interactions, casual meetings and family picnics. The informal vendors occupy the space, selling go-to snacks; and toys for the children.
- The activity pattern of the area shows high public footfall during the day until 11:00 p.m. at night. Earlier, the space was less regulated and the India Gate precinct was open to the public until late at night. However, after the revamping, the space gets closed at 11:00 p.m., and heavy police surveillance is seen in and around the area. Once a vibrant space, this regulatory move has reduced it into an inactive and dull space post 11:00 p.m.
- **Connectivity:** India Gate is accessible by Metro, buses, and private vehicles. However, the nearest metro stations and bus stops are 7-10 minutes walking distance from India Gate. The last bus service is at 09:00 p.m. which is again a 10-minute walk from the area.

- Policing and Crime:** There is an ample surveillance in and around the area making the space less prone to crime. Yet, due to heavy regulations, the inactivity post 11:00 p.m. makes the space extremely dull and beyond the reach of people.

Figure 19: India Gate at 11:00 p.m.

Source: Author

Figure 20

Figure 21

Figure 20 Figure 21: Active public spaces at India Gate at 10:30 p.m.

Source: Author

Time of Use	Activities	Public Profiling
06:00 p.m. – 08:00 p.m.	Active Public Space	Men, Women, Children
08:00 p.m. – 11:00 p.m.	Active Public Space	Men, Women, Children
11:00 p.m. – 12:00 a.m.	Inactive	Men, Women, Children

Table 12: Time of Use versus Activities & Participant Profiling – India Gate

Source: Author

4.4.2 Safety Analysis

Parameters	Safety Indicators (1-5)					Mean	Score (1-5)				
	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5
Lighting	0	0	0	8	12	4.6					
Police Surveillance	0	0	0	2	18	4.9					
Accessibility	0	0	0	10	10	4.5					
Presence of Public	0	0	3	9	8	4.25					
Sense of Belonging	0	0	4	10	6	4.1					
Score							0	0	0	2	3
Percentage Score							-	-	-	40	60

Table 13: User Perception Safety Score for India Gate Precinct

Source: Author

Chart 5: User Perception on Safety for India Gate Precinct

Source: Author

4.4.3 Findings

In this case instead of the User Count Survey, manually the men-to-women ratio was manually calculated through observation. The user count was not conducted due to the multiple entry and exit points in the area. It was observed that per 100 men there were 70 women present at the place, making the ratio as 1:1.4 (women: men). India Gate is a public

space and scored the highest on safety parameters. 60% people rated the area with a score of 5 and 40% rated the area with a score of 4.

4.5 Modality Analysis on Case Studies

In all four case studies, the spaces are appropriate for night time activities. The paper applies Robert Williams modality model to the case studies to investigate the nightlife structure and its safety components. It was found that Channeling as a strategy dominates all the study areas. Marginalization is seen to work in the form of official zoning regulations in all the cases and Exclusion could be seen in the case of India Gate where physical barriers and manual policing limit the people's use the space after 11:00 p.m. Hence, the paper further investigates the strategy of channeling by sub-categorizing it into the five parameters from the literature review. This analysis is based on the presence or absence of the five parameters as observed by the author.

	Active Surveillance		Social Inclusion				Diverse Activity	Permeability & Visibility	Territoriality/ Sense of Belonging
	CCT V	Police	Men	Women	Elderly	Children			
Matia Mahal	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	Y	Y	Y	Y
Nehru Place	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N
CP (eateries)	Y	Y	Y	Y	-	Y	N	-	N
India Gate	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

Table 14: Safety Parameter Matrix for the Study Areas at Night (Observational) where Y denotes a Yes and N denotes a No.

Source: Author

5. REGULATIONS ON NIGHTLIFE IN DELHI

The Government of Delhi governs the working hours and hence the closing time of “commercial outlets” in the city. One of the objectives is to identify the role of government in regulating the nightlife culture. This paper also attempts to analyze the rationale behind the regulation of closing hours of nightlife venues in Delhi. For the purpose of this study, the regulations for Eating Houses and Shopping Areas have been examined. This is done keeping in mind the prevalence of nightlife activities around these spaces.

5.1 Eating Houses²

Laws regarding closing time

Opening and Closing Timings differ during the summers and winters by half an hour or so. In addition, a coffee shop in a hotel is allowed to stay open for 24 hours while discotheques are allowed to open until midnight. Tea stalls are required to close their outlets by 11:00 p.m. Mobile hawkers selling eatables are allowed to enter any area according to the directives of the concerned Resident Welfare Association (RWA). (Daga, n.d.) Any eating house has to acquire a trade license from the Municipal Corporation of Delhi (MCD). These licenses state the working hours according to the zone of operation, whether it is conforming or non-conforming.

The Police regulate the closing hours of eating houses because these are places where public assemblies, and so there the question of public security. They govern the activities to keep a check on the crime rate.

5.2 Shops and Shopping Areas

Laws regarding closing timings

All shopkeepers and occupiers of establishments carrying on any business or profession or rendering any service are required to be registered under the Delhi Shops and Establishments Act, 1954. Thus, this Act stipulates the closing time of shops. Section 15 of the Act says that-

(1) No shop or commercial establishment on any day shall be opened earlier than such hour or closed later than such hour, as may be fixed by the Government by general or special order made on that behalf. (The Delhi Shops and Establishments Act, 1954, n.d.)

(2) The Government may, for the purpose of this section, fix different opening hours and different closing hours for different classes of shops or commercial establishments, for different areas or for different times of the year. The timings as per Sec 15 are as follows: (The Delhi Shops and Establishments Act, 1954, n.d.)

² The Delhi Police Act, 1978, defines “Eating Houses” as follows: Eating house means any place to which the public are admitted and where any kind of food or drink is supplied for consumption on the premises by any person owning or having any interest in managing such place.

Nature of Establishment	Opening Hour	Closing Hour
Shops (during summers)	9:30 a.m.	7:30 p.m.
Shops (during winters)	9:00 a.m.	7:00 p.m.
Commercial Establishment	8:00 a.m.	6:00 p.m.

Table 15: Shops Opening and Closing Timing

Source: (The Delhi Shops and Establishments Act, 1954, n.d.)

The closing time of shops is regulated in order to make sure that the employees do not have to work over-time; they reach home in time and get to spend some quality time with their family. In the case of women, the question of their security assumes greater importance. So, it is mentioned in the Act that no women shall be put to work after 9:00 p.m. during the summer season and after 8:00 p.m. during the winter season.

In 2004, changes were made to the Act to boost employment generation and promote a positive and favourable business environment that are prerequisites for economic growth and the opening time of the establishments was extended to 11:00 p.m. This, however, was not mandatory. According to the new norms, exemptions under Sections 14, 15 and 16 were provided. This makes it possible for businesses to be open 24X7 as long as certain requirements for the security of the workforce are met. (Express News Service, 2022) In 2022 budget of the Delhi government, Former Finance Minister Manish Sisodia announced the preparation of a policy that would allow food trucks to operate at designated places in the city from 8:00 p.m. to 2:00 a.m.

5.3 Master Plan of Delhi and Its Take on Nightlife

The Master Plan 2041 provides various approaches for development and strengthening of economic centres. One of the approaches mentioned in MPD-2041 is Fostering Night Time Economy (NTE). It provides a brief mention of the concept of '24-hour city' as per Model Shops and Establishments (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Services) Act 2015 as well as the NTE policy at the national level. The MPD provides suggestions to attract tourists and locals by identifying nodes, precincts or circuits for continuing work, cultural activity and entertainment at night.

6. CONCLUSION

Cities must be seen as attractive, accessible, safe and unthreatening places to be in at all times of the day and night. The development of urban nightlife is a tool for regeneration. Active night spaces are among the city's urban cultures that possess a rich source of everyday life and play an important role in establishing a city's cultural identities. The growth of safe nightlife is a major challenge for cities, and we have to learn how to manage this activity in the interests of all the many stakeholders involved. Many cities around the world have adopted a 24x7 city concept to boost their economies, and in turn, these cities have become safer for their citizens during the night.

In this paper, theories on urban nightlife and safety provide a framework to analyze the Urban Nightlife of Delhi. Delhi presented itself as an interesting case with a multitude of spaces to examine. In Delhi, both State Government as well as DDA Master Plan have advocated for a "24x7 Delhi".

Four areas of Delhi were selected based on the level of activities during the late evening hours and the typology of the space. The first case study of Matia Mahal, Jama Masjid showed a diverse range of activities that operates until late at night making the area relatively safer. The study area of Connaught Place attracts young crowd in spite of the closing of the entire market at 09:00 p.m. Nehru Place shuts at 08:00 p.m. and becomes mostly inactive with minimal activities. India Gate case is different as it is the strategy of exclusion that governs the closing of the place.

The debates on urban nightlife scarcely discuss the impact of **social inclusion** on urban safety. This, however, is one of the key factors responsible for a healthy and vibrant nightlife. Places that are gender inclusive are comparatively safer than their counterparts which only attract male visitors. One thing emerged clearly: the ratio of females to males during the night is limited in all the study areas. Most of the study areas are male-dominated. There is a sense of fear among the women about using the space at night for recreational and leisure purposes. The study recognized a co-relation between social inclusion and diversity of activities for a safe and active nightlife. India Gate with a mix of activities, has a genuine share of women and children. Matia Mahal does have a mix of activities, but the majority of visitors are men. This can be attributed to the decreasing range of activities at night. In the case of Connaught Place, mostly families and young crowds are seen as the visitors.

Another factor responsible for creating a sense of safety is the level of **permeability and legibility**. In the case of Matia Mahal, a clear axis exists that runs from Jama Masjid and continues along the street. The active public space at India Gate is a part of an axis that is clearly visible and accessible. The study areas of Connaught Place behave as active nodes where the activity is concentrated and limited. Nehru Place District Centre is the only case among the four that happens to have impermeable spaces inside as well as outside the complex.

A **sense of belonging** can be felt at Matia Mahal which is not just a tourist attraction but represents cultural values and community bonds. India Gate is unique as it brings the idea of India into the urban space, instilling a sense of territoriality and belonging among the visitors. It is observed that **surveillance** is present in all the four case studies except for Nehru Place which requires police surveillance post 08:00 p.m.

Isolated places were found to be more vulnerable to threats as compared to lively active places. According to the personal interviews conducted in the study areas, people felt comfortable and safe in the presence of hawkers. The most inactive space of all the case studies was Nehru Place District Centre. In spite of good connectivity and provision of public transportation in Nehru Place, it is perceived as unsafe. There are issues of legibility, negative space and lack of activities. This area requires a more rational use of space. Certain inactive areas are identified in the paper which can be redesigned by connecting them with the outer edges of the complex and by introducing new activities like cultural events that can operate till 11:00 p.m. Entry and Exit points should be made legible and clear signage should be added.

To improve the nightlife of Matia Mahal, a street revitalization project should be considered. New activities with extended working hours should be promoted to boost the night time economy. The study areas in Connaught Place should also be redesigned as active nodes in the city centre that can operate for longer durations.

After examining the government regulations on nightlife, it is apparent that the government has favored the operation of nightlife establishments by bringing amendments to the existing acts over the time. It is suggested that the government should build on the examples of best practices to develop a more sustainable and safer nightlife. It should promote culturally diverse activities at night at certain specified city centers and nodes away from the residential colonies, which will encourage a range of people to use the areas at night. However, it must be ensured that the security setup is effectively beefed up so that the criminals do not use the situation to their advantage.

To summarize, the future of the city lies in its night time economy, which would not only bring economic growth but also create a safer place for its citizens.

While this paper is hopefully useful in understanding the complexity of urban nightlife with respect to safety in the case of Delhi. Still, additional theoretical and empirical research can be done to study the following threads within the domain of Urban Nightlife as identified in this study. Firstly, the role of social inclusion and diverse range of activities on nightlife can be explored further. Secondly, there is a scope to do a comparative study of Delhi with other metropolitan cities. Lastly, the findings of this study can be applied on her domains to develop and identify new research gaps.

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Emerging Technological Advancements to Safety and Security Systems in Smart Urban Public Spaces

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Abstract

This research delves into perceptions of emerging technological tools to suffice safety and security in urban public space formulations in line with the intentions of many cities around the world and as envisioned by CPTED concepts. As cities evolve into technologically advanced hubs, popularly termed as Smart cities, enhancing citizen well-being, and promoting sustainable urban living become paramount. The study co-relates urban scenarios of pre-smart city eras with post eras in terms of liveability aspects. This technological transformation, while promising, confronts challenges, notably data security concerns and the seamless integration of the physical devices of IoT (Internet of Things) within urban designs. This study addresses the second challenge through the exploration of three aspects of smart systems: intelligent public lighting, smart surveillance, and interactive digital platforms adopting case study method. It attempts to bridge the gap between safety measures and technological interventions with twofold objectives: to understand the role of technology in fostering urban environments and to propose an integrative framework of digital security systems in the physical public realms. This proposed framework for digital ecosystem intends to create awareness on possibilities and serve as a guide for municipal decisions under architectural and urban design contexts for amicable accommodation of the ‘physical components’ of such smart systems.

1. Introduction

The world is becoming increasingly urbanized. As per United Nations (UN), more than half of the global population lives in urban areas, while the urban share worldwide is rising from around one third in 1950 to around two thirds in 2050. The emphasis on sustainability and technologically advanced urban development is the primary movement in current times. Urban services are aiming to make lives easier, more comfortable, and luxurious, while complexity of the infrastructure is equally increasing, relying on information and communication technology (ICT) and digital advancements.

Writer and activist Jane Jacobs was the intellectual pioneer to steer the paradigm on urban planning, architecture, and crime in her seminal book ‘The Death & Life of Great American

Cities (1961) with the core concepts such as ‘Eyes on the Street’. Many theories emerged thereupon by eminent planners, designers, architects, and policy makers in the years to come. One such theory under urban security systems has been Crime prevention through environmental design, popularly termed CPTED, a six-decade-old concept defined as a multi-disciplinary approach to prevent the occurrence of crime in cities through suitable environmental designs (International CPTED Association). It employs elements of design for built and natural environments to enable control of crime and provide safer environments to people in their neighborhoods.

The popular criminologist Professor C. Ray Jeffery coined the name CPTED in his book of 1971. Further, this was elaborated by Architect Oscar Newman in his book on Defensible Space in 1972. ICA's (The International CPTED Association) mission is: To create safer environments and improve the quality of life using CPTED principles and strategies (<https://www.cpted.net/A-brief-history>). The vision outlined that such design strategies deter offender decisions that precede criminal acts. Popularly known as ‘designing out crime’, it includes aspects of natural surveillance, access control and territoriality. As times progress and human societies evolve, concepts too advance to adapt and reconfigure to suit newer aspirations. Likewise, safety and security designs in cities are becoming smarter, though the question lingers on its long term efficacy, survival and if at all it reinforces the CPTED ideologies. This paper shall understand the fundamental aspects of CPTED, characteristics of smart cities, and exploration of three cases of technological safety systems in cities. It compares the urban scenarios of ‘pre-smart’ city public spaces to ‘smart’ spaces under attributes of liveability aspects. The study attempts to fill in one gap in the contemporary times on imposition of technical-smartness and impact on physical realms of urban public spaces.

2. Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design

One of the most important aspects of a good city is the sense of ‘safety and security’ (Lynch, 1984), and being free of crime or scared of crime. 1st Generation CPTED had 4 components originally- territoriality, natural surveillance, image and milieu, and access control. The 2nd Generation CPTED founded by Cleveland & Saville was introduced formally at the annual conference of the International CPTED Association in 1997 with the reintroduction of social concepts back into CPTED with focus on small-scale environments termed as proximal orientation (Cleveland and Saville, 1997). The development of 2nd Generation was a reaction against the target hardening, and the removal of social programming from 1st Generation CPTED (then termed as “motive reinforcement”).

Figure 1: 1st and 2nd Generation CPTED components (Source: <https://www.cpted.net/Primer-in-CPTED>)

Hence, while the 1st Generation aimed at reducing the scope of crime through physical space designs alone, the 2nd Generation identified that social ecology, neighborhood health, and collective efficacy (Fig 1) were prerogative to prevent crime (Mihiniac and Saville, 2019). Research conducted in Australia in the context of a secondary school annual year-end celebration event and prevention of crime revealed that 1st Generation proved ineffective as a stand-alone strategy whereas garnered better results coupled with 2nd Generation tools to foster social cohesion and increased threshold capacity (Letch et al., 2011). Core understanding of the fundamental concepts becomes the foundation to further applications in progressing smart cities safety ideologies (Table 1).

	1st Generation CPTED	2nd Generation CPTED
Primary concept	Territoriality	Sense of Community
With focus on	Architecture & physical designs	Social ecology, neighborhood planning & collective efficacy, small-scale environments termed as proximal orientation
Initiation	1970s	1997
Proponents	Ray Jeffrey and Newman & Rand (Defensible theory) as a start-off from Jane Jacob's 'eyes on the street' theory	Greg Saville & Gerry Cleveland
Crime addressal	Physical designs to discourage occurrence of crime	Positive social relations between residents, Neighborhood watch initiatives to control crime
Main components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Territoriality ▪ Natural surveillance ▪ Image and Milieu ▪ Access control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Social cohesion ▪ Community culture ▪ Connectivity ▪ Threshold capacity
Timeframe for implications	Short-time frames	Longer periods

Table 1: CPTED components derived from various literature cited in this study

In 2011, a Joint project was presented in Milan by the United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute (UNICRI) and Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) *Senseable City Lab* under the UNICRI's Security Governance/Counter-Terrorism Laboratory held to assist effective policy decisions in the field of security (http://www.unicri.eu/news/article/1104-2_urban_security). The MIT Lab researched the security in cities based on green urban design and eco-solutions in cities. It proposed a next Generation CPTED inculcating the evolving digital advancements of modern times. This renewed model termed as 3rd Generation in the report (2011) wished to seek community involvement along with creating better inclusive urban spaces and hosting well-equipped infrastructure to include certain aspects in city designs such as:

- enough urban public spaces for community gatherings
- efficient waste management system adopting the latest technologies

- efficient natural surveillance system—sufficient street light network, active streets, and public spaces always
- robust public transportation
- financial set-up towards the maintenance of civic spaces.

The UNICRI-MIT report concludes with a set of proposals for the 3rd Generation CPTED (http://www.unicri.eu/news/article/1104-2_urban_security) and a broader vision encompassing diverse aspects of urban designs to prevent crime and enhance perception of safety. It introduced additional principles of green environmental design to the core ideas and expanded security perceptions as a global issue with geo-political and socio-cultural divisions. This in conjunction with the era of technological spike and converging with the green objectives of sustainability tended to become synonymous with each other (UNICRI Report, 2011). Originally, the evolution of 3rd Generation CPTED was viewed within the urban planning principle called liveability (Mihinjac & Saville, 2019), which has become one of the most critical aspects of designing urban neighborhoods and streets as better places to live, to use, and to flourish (Appleyard, 1981).

However, as the intent of this study is the exploration of technological aspects to reinforce safety in city space designs, the paper steers in that direction without debating whatsoever the original social systems or CPTED ideologies that have always been self-reliant, cohesive entities to defend crime and maintain secure communities. CPTED becomes a backdrop, whereas given the fact that ever-evolving human societies either intend to make lives safer or indulge in showcasing dominance via technology, it is imperative that man adapt to these changing times effortlessly. Hence, the study attempts to fill in one gap in the contemporary times on imposition of techno-smartness and impact on urban public spaces.

3. Objectives & Methodology of the Study

This paper takes off from the thought of emerging concepts of technology in designing safety in public realms and qualitative exploration adopting ‘case study’ methodology. It searches for the possibilities of these concepts to induce resilience to crime and enhance the liveability of smart urban spaces and does not necessarily connect this aspect to any Generation CPTED in part or in totality. The main objectives are to perceive in these smart spaces innovative urban design concepts with the hypothetical proposition: ‘Liveability can be enhanced adopting technology towards stimulation of resilience to crime and induction of safety in the design of urban spaces.’ Hence, questions raised are-

How and in what ways do technological applications enable creating ‘safer and greener’ urban spaces?

What are the potentials and issues encountered in digitally equipped ‘physical environments’ of urban spaces?

To answer these queries, the explorative study adopts a qualitative methodology of case studies of smart urban systems. The intent is to perceive instances where cities have experimented with creative and systematic public space design for better urban experiences.

A sample selection of three basic parameters, namely- 'lighting, security, and signage' is chosen from the deduced essential design characteristics of urban spaces discussed in the next section.

Thus, the three cases explored include:

1. Intelligent Lighting Systems
2. Smart Surveillance and Security systems
3. Signage and Interactive Applications

Under each of these three aspects, at least three case studies are undertaken that offer wider perspectives on smart designs and their implications.

4. Smart Urban Spaces

A smart city is commonly understood as the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Internet of Things (IoT) to sense, analyze, and integrate the key information of core systems in the functioning of a city (IBM, 2010). The 'smart' determines how the city optimizes urban functions to promote growth along with improving quality of life (TWI Global).

While it becomes seamless for developed countries to adopt technology in urban spaces with fewer space-related convolutions to people usage but 'big brother surveillance' raising certain ethical aspects, developing countries rather face the first more severely than the second concern. Cities in richer countries are large as they build 'out' and build 'up' whereas cities in poorer countries become large by crowding 'in' (Jedwab et al., 2021). Consequentially, bleak differences are witnessed in physical environments across cities. The focus here shall remain limited to the aspect of physical space connotations owing to smart designs. Population, crowding, and density result in natural surveillance but concerns of clutter due to over-consumption of urban space impact the public realm.

In the instance of India as well, one of the fastest developing nations in Asia, the smart city mission (SCM) was introduced by the government in 2015 with the objective of promoting cities that provide core infrastructure and give a decent quality of life to its citizens, a clean and sustainable environment through the application of 'Smart' solutions (SCM, Government of India, 2015). These cities embed physical safety and citizen security, women's safety, crime reduction and smart surveillance tools across urban centers through smart and safe city programs (Rao, BW Smart Cities, 2021). Urban designs are being supported with various technology-based tools introduced for safety designs, monitoring and execution in Smart cities with IoT tools (Fig 2). Smart cities have adopted CPTED strategies as an initiative towards creating safer neighborhoods. While it can be noted that many social concepts of CPTED have always been implanted in Indian traditional settlements since times with cohesive neighborhood designs hosting visible courtyards as centers, but which were lost out due to impacts of modernity and urbanization (Sarangi & Kapoor, 2021). The convergence of traditional ideologies of design and technological safety measures shall ensure a possible renewed holistic safety system in place. Safety schemes include responsive tools such as

smart policing, predictive policing, smart stations, resource allocation, and crime management systems.

Figure 2: Main aspects of Smart Safety Systems collated from cited literature and Smart City Mission Portal, Government of India

Urban public spaces are one of the most crucial components in any city’s spatial layout, that all citizens use and enjoy for various aspects ranging from basic needs of shopping, work, accessing amenities or leisure. Hence, it is understood that these spaces need to be democratic in nature and conducive to use, for which four criteria become fundamental: comfort (Nemanja & Marc, 2010), function (Whyte, 1980), safety, and vitality (Lynch, 1981) (Fig 3).

Figure 3: Main design aspects to create Smart urban spaces and selected three aspects for exploration in this study

In this research, the sample set for qualitative exploration includes the selection of two parameters under ‘safety’ aspect viz., ‘lighting & security’ along with one parameter under ‘vitality’ viz, ‘signage’ which essentially reinforces the former aspect of ‘safety’ (Fig 3). Safety & vitality are closely related variables determining secure places because vital spaces

are actively used by people thus leading to safe places (Lynch,1981 & Jacobs, 1961). Hence, safety and vitality are chosen to explore with the three parameters under them to initiate correlation equation between public realms and technology in terms of liveability.

Figure 4: The three parameters of safety

The sample essentially encompasses the most fundamental smart components of digital ecosystem- 1st order of lighting, 2nd order of security/ surveillance systems and 3rd order of signage in hierarchy of safety degree for people in public spaces (Fig. 4). Each of these systems involve functioning in terms of backend operation and physical elements in the public realm, which becomes interesting aspect of influence on urban design.

5. Three Cases of Smart Safety Systems

The focus is on examining smart public space designs for streets, intersections, parks, plazas, and commercial nodes. Though natural vigilance, surveillance, traditional setups, or policing cannot be replaced, technology is envisioned to enable a reinforced system of enhanced safety ecosystems. Smart cities embed this in their overall scheme of planning and design. For CPTED to be popular, it must continually respond to changing times of rapid urbanization, demographic profiles, diversities, evolving lifestyles, emerging crime profiles and newer technologies or products in the market as well (Cozens & Love, 2015). Hence, what are the ways in which technological tools can be embedded in public space design, planning, and maintenance?

5.1 Case 1- Intelligent Lighting Systems

Street lighting in neighborhoods is an important factor for a safe urban realm and an evident investment by cities to reduce the occurrence of crime (Painter and Farrington, 1999). It has been identified as a key aspect under CPTED core strategies (Robinson, 2013). In recent times, however, when viewed with the demands of efficiency or sustainability in design, several factors become crucial such as energy consumption, context-driven detailing and intelligent lighting incorporating LED, solar-powered lights, or sensor-triggered lights.

The first case study of innovative safety design is observed in the city of Brussels, Belgium municipality, Molenbeek-Saint-Jean, who in collaboration with Sibelga, implemented 'smart lighting' cycling paths in public spaces in 2022. The broad aim was the well-being and safety of cyclists coupled with sustainable forms of energy. The design involves a light bubble that follows the cyclist along the path. Similarly, in Woluwe-Saint-Pierre district there are pedestrian crossings equipped with 'presence sensor lights' (The Brussels Times, July 2022).

The second case study in the city of Stonnington, Australia involves design strategies for street lighting lamp posts which became creative elements in the urban design framework, with interesting designs and embedded multiple features including cameras, Wi-Fi modems and emergency call-points. Public lights are equipped with sensors to convey real-time data to the municipality through a dashboard for efficient maintenance purposes (Stonnington city web portal). A similar instance is seen in the *LuxTurrim* 5G project undertaken by a consortium of cell phone companies and research universities that devised a smart light pole-based 5G infrastructure with the goal of integrating several smart features (Fig 5). The project aims at technical innovations in conjunction with business opportunities to collate various services in an amicable manner (Varis, 2019).

Figure 5: *LuxTurrim* 5G light pole with integrated components of smart features- sensors and cameras (Source: <https://ercim-news.ercim.eu/en117/special/luxturrim5g-smart-5g-light-pole-infrastructure-for-digital-service-ecosystems-in-cities>)

The third case study refers to one of the features of smart cities in India that envisages additional functions for the illumination of urban spaces to enhance the quality of life, services, and experiences for people and sustainability. This vision is taken ahead by various innovators such as Bajaj, Wipro, HPL and Philips Lighting India, which enlists 4 key urban areas of contribution (EPR Magazine Editorial, 2017) (Fig 6). The framework outlines a systematic and hierarchical approach from the scale of the urban network up to details on the lighting specifics, rendering a complete overview of the lighting ecosystem.

Figure 6: Four aspects of 'Smart City Lighting' in Urban areas (Compiled by Authors based on an article available at <https://www.eprmagazine.com/features/powering-the-smart-cities-with-intelligent-lighting/>)

Thus, lighting innovations for safety and sustainability can be achieved at different scales of planning and design of public spaces with specific objectives in line with the larger vision and aspirations of the city for its people. Also, light pole designs offer potential to host several other smart features pointing at integrated and compact entities.

5.2 Case 2- Smart Surveillance and Security Systems

Video surveillance by installing closed-circuit television (CCTV) in urban spaces is becoming common in the present time to enable real-time monitoring and reduce patrolling personnel. This technology has been revolutionized with innovations in high computing power, huge memory potential and ample processing capabilities. The system comprises cameras, transmission media, image analysis equipment, monitors, recording and storage systems. Camera resolutions come in varied capacities and quality of capturing the images, hence as per the expected degree of security, the right cameras need to be adopted.

Additionally, surrounding lighting, background clutter, crowding of people or objects, day or night etc. impact the system selection, higher the possibilities of crime, higher the expected resolution. Operational attributes, software and hardware components need to be outlined while, sound detection, biometry, and CBRN-E sensors are adopted as per contextual demands (European Commission, Sept 2020).

The first case study looks at research that has developed a futuristic urban design tool, viz., the *LookCrim* application (Freitas, 2011). This tool gathers geo-tagged information on various locations in the city. It intends to map the four basic CPTED parameters from urban documentation and adopt a spatial-temporal analysis of crime-enabling data organization and apt urban design decisions thereupon. Studies based on this application have been published, which revealed its benefits in safety design resolutions.

The second case study is in the case of Detroit smart city, where under the 'Project Green Light' crime was reduced by 50% by the adoption of a network of public and private cameras across the neighborhoods with two main objectives to provide critical evidence for investigations and discourage potential crimes since the cameras came with a green identification light. They are fitted with audio detectors as well to spot adverse noises such as glass-breaking or shouting to enable action before the escalation of crime; the sensors aid the Fire department in spotting fire as well as in cases of arson. Surveillance has been used to prevent railway suicides to a greater extent. However, to keep the security systems themselves protected, physical access control is enabled, which includes video capture, QR Codes, visitor badges, and facial recognition to screen authorized personnel access exclusively (Sori; Axis Communications, 2020).

The third case study points to Cell phone applications (Apps) in general that make it inclusive for citizens to have an easy and immediate interface to communicate with respective authorities and be participants in the protection of public spaces (European Commission, 2020). Hence, public spaces are expected to be Wi-Fi enabled, equipped for easy and quick access to required phone services to be used in the case of dire circumstances, and report to concerned support lines. It is recommended that every city develop an App with a user-friendly interface for any citizen to use with ease.

The fourth case study looks at the application of Drones or Unmanned Aircraft systems (UAS) considered as technology's latest innovations, being adopted by cities to monitor public space security, as in the instance of Turin, Italy. Drones can work in integration with ground surveillance for effective outcomes across smaller and to larger public spaces. In Madrid, Spain drones are extensively used by municipal departments for monitoring and surveillance during daytime and nighttime, public announcements, accident reconstruction, and disaster management (EFUS, 2022).

Thus, digital surveillance is going beyond the basics of CCTV applications to innovations that equip citizens to report crimes, aerial surveillance by drones and software development for prevention of crime or its escalation.

5.3 Case 3- Signage and Digital Interactive Applications

A legible system of urban spaces in a city becomes a step towards a safer city; when a citizen knows his city well and navigates with confidence, he is at ease, and the likelihood of being subjected to crime is lesser. Signage aids in wayfinding and supports branding, commerce, and economy, as well as helping businesses sustain themselves. While static signboards have been around for long, smart cities are embracing innovations in technological tools, and designs of signage are now human-centered in approach (Sloly, 2023). Digital signage comprises of networked electronic displays in public spaces coupled with interactive features, where displays offer consumers the possibility to interact with the system (Bauer, Dohmen and Strauss, 2011). They provide a range of interactive facilities for information on city services, public transport schedules, local community updates, free public Wi-Fi, emergency warnings, advertisements, green walls, phone charging, or game pods (Fig 7) (Smart Cities, Pavegen).

The first case study looks at the application of kinetic technology to generate energy from people's footsteps and power interactive applications by Pavegen, a UK-based company. This is called 'people power,' which envisions in helping society to be sustainable while being progressive and involve fun-filled engagements for the people. Interactive signage adds to the interest level of city designs for residents and visitors alike.

Figure 7: Pavegen Green system installed by Easy Freight in Karanga Plaza, Auckland, New Zealand (Source: <https://www.pavegen.com/>)

The second case study highlights a new perspective on interactive signage by a democratic built-in system that gives consumers opportunity of expression of opinion on the sign content. For example, if a person dislikes a 'macabre' in the display or any other discriminating content in the advertisement, he may use his phone to vote on the issue immediately with a simple user interface. The platform provider further collates such votes to enable suitable action on the signage (Bauer, Dohmen and Strauss, 2011). This gives cue to create an easy and quick interface App for the user to contact services instantly with real-time location sensors.

The third case study looks at a project proposal titled *Pointsoft* for the Naples Circumvesuviana in Italy comprising five crucial railway lines serving over two million commuters (Rocca, 2014). The project involved rejuvenation of the stations with a system of interactive multimedia installations aimed to enhance services, offer required information to commuters about rail schedule, connectivity, emergency numbers, and elevate the perception of safety in the stations and trains. The interactive screens played videos on the history of the

place along with primary information. These displays allowed social control, an increased sense of security, and awareness of place and orientation (Rocca, 2014).

Thus, digital innovation offers wide possibilities for a common man-to-technology interface under information signage, along with inducing safety strategies from a personal phone App level to a public display interface. They are two-way and interactive in nature, making responses quicker and more efficient for concerned teams.

Figure 8: Deductions from Case studies on the three aspects of smart safety measures

The case studies thus present possibilities of innovations across various hierarchies (scales) of planning and urban design with the three cases of smart systems and deductions of salient aspects under each (Fig 8).

6. Challenges to Smart Safety Systems in cities

Crime detection, prevention, and people protection components of tech-enabled CPTED proposes a fool-proof security system, accompanied with certain challenges to be addressed to make the spaces liveable as well. They are meant to induce safety to common public and not intimidate with complex user interfaces or bulky equipment occupying public spaces. Smart security systems in cities face two main challenges – firstly, concerns regarding breach of information confidentiality as data is on the global network, secondly the accommodation and integration of the physical components of the systems in the public space design. The study addresses the second concern within the scope of this research. For example, in the context of Indian cities which are in most cases highly populated, demographically diverse with urban spaces becoming zones of high activity, crowding and multiple stakeholders, urban spaces become contested spaces for several entities vying for space. The streets are occupied with- people, vegetation, vehicles, hawkers, stray animals, signage & hoardings, waste dumps, shop spillovers, private encroachments by residents and commercial shop owners and infrastructure elements such as utility units and poles (Patil & Raj, 2019).

Figure 9: Sidewalks cluttered with multiple components including utilities & their physical units impacting liveability in terms of safe pedestrian navigation in public spaces (Date of capture- October 20, 2017, 11 AM, Basavanagudi, Bangalore)

To compare the scenarios of urban spaces before and after smart city implementations, a study is referred to here- doctoral research conducted by authors during the pre-smart city implementation period in the city of Bangalore (capital of Karnataka state, India, and a globally progressive metropolitan city). The research developed a methodology to audit neighborhood streets and public spaces for elderly walkability. Results showed that the infrastructure elements accounted for nearly 80% of the barriers to walkability in the surveyed four neighborhoods. These overground utility units, comprising electrical transformers, light poles, cables, manholes, or control units for electricity, telecommunication & water supply services were observed to be placed and spread randomly occupying much of the sidewalks along the streets in an uncoordinated manner leading to discontinuous pedestrian paths forcing pedestrian to get down to traffic laden roads proving unsafe causing accidents (Figs. 9 & 10). Hence, it was observed that the utility or infrastructure elements adversely impacted the urban place-making and overall liveability (Patil & Raj, 2019).

Figure 10: The clutter of utility elements- poles, control units, signage, traffic police/control units (Date of capture- September 2, 2023, 10 PM, Bangalore city center)

One definition refers to smart city as - an instrumented, interconnected, and intelligent city (IBM, 2008); 'instrumented' pertaining to the modes of capturing and integrating real-time data using sensors, meters, appliances, and a range of other devices (Praharaj & Han, 2019). Embedding these physical components of the security devices into the architecture of urban space becomes critical for better designs that keep up the aesthetic value of the place and be user-friendly to all citizens. The right placement of equipment—light posts, surveillance cameras, cables, sensors, and access boxes—in such a manner as to:

- not hinder people's movement or comfortable usage of the public space
- not ruin the aesthetic realm
- not add to unsightly clutter & perils of crowding
- not hamper routine or regular maintenance of devices by personnel
- not to be impacted by weather forces
- not easy to be destroyed or vandalized
- not economically demanding nor environmentally harmful in any way.

The case studies under intelligent lighting presented scope of design for compact physical units embedding various smart security features to combat the concerns of bulky, multiple-unit components and space-consuming infrastructure. This poses a potential advantage, especially in dense city center public spaces, to resolve clutter and thereupon, enhance the public realm for walking, smooth access, aesthetics, and overall ambience while being well equipped to be smart places. This elevates the degree of liveability factor of the city.

7. Proposed Framework

From general understanding, it is observed that four aspects ensue safety in cities- urban governance (policies), police force, urban planning & design strategies, and technological adaptations. The last two being the focus here, the study hypothesized that liveability can be enhanced by adopting technology for the stimulation of resilience to crime and induction of safety in the design of urban spaces. Under the scope of the study, was the concern pertaining to accommodation of the physical components of smart systems in public space designs.

From the case studies it is noted that smart systems of lighting, surveillance, and signage have created innovative solutions, one of the important outcomes being integrated and compact physical modules (Fig. 8). While the research conducted in pre-smart city scenario showed adverse impact on public realms, on liveability aspects with unsafe and barrier-laden sidewalks due to independent services and their corresponding physical components being spaced out or strewn in the public spaces. Thus, technological advancements that converge various security systems and services aid in creating amicable and user-friendly public realms in cities. Hence, proving the hypothetical assertion of smart urban spaces paving way for liveable conditions, to an extent.

Given the scope to collate safety systems/services and reduce complexity in urban design, this led to conceptualizing a proposal for an 'integrated, inclusive, and collaborative' system of IoT with a proposed network called as 'mesh of smart safety ecosystem' concept in city designs (Fig. 11). Such a coherent system that integrates all services and security measures

leads to effective utilization of the valuable open spaces in the city for better socially enriched spaces, creating walkways, public seating, parklets, or amenities. While the software and hardware of the ecosystem become the backdrop, physical components become of immediate concern to architecture and urban design schemes with experiential attributes for users. Smart physical units can integrate- intelligent lighting, smart surveillance cameras, Wi-Fi, digital parking, environmental monitoring (pollution), a public information system for the visually challenged, charging points, fire safety measures, smart direction systems, interactive maps, and emergency calling stations (Colclough, 2021).

The proposed smart ecosystem involves five broad criteria: Core safety & security measures, Response, Legibility, Amenities and Management (Fig. 11). Such a system relies on principles of innovative, collaborative, integrative, advanced, inclusive, and participatory methodologies for a wholesome and efficient functioning to mitigate noted issues.

Figure 11: Mesh of Smart Safety Ecosystem

This framework shall enable resolutions under the twofold objectives of technology to foster urban environments and a system for amicable public realms. The smart ecosystem enabled by the two main aspects of physical designs and systems management leads to a liveability anchored in safe and conducive public spaces in cities, proving the hypothetical assumption (Fig. 12).

Figure 12: From Smart systems to Liveability- Resolution & mitigation under physical space planning and system security management

Firstly, it is realized that to achieve coordination between the physical components, innovation of system designs to consume less space with the right choice of devices is fundamental. Secondly, though not in the scope of this study, assumption points at a collaborated ecosystem to reduce vulnerabilities of the systems with a single control/operational point and specific sub-points while dispersing such elements in the public spaces (this needs substantiation). The study proposes to initiate further research on this second aspect and explore smart urban space designs addressing each specific utility system in the available spatial and contextual typologies. The qualitative assessment in the second phase of the study in the upcoming research shall include people-based opinion surveys in selected neighborhoods to reinforce the case study analytical results. However, a robust people-centric approach to techno-safety designs of urban spaces becomes necessary for architects and designers in conjunction with CPTED strategies.

8. Conclusions

The research highlights qualitative explorations of emerging concepts with the adoption of technology in designing public realms in cities as possibilities to induce resilience to crime while enhancing liveability as well, with a focus on nascent smart urban spaces. The study attempted to fill in one gap in contemporary times on imposition of technical-smartness and impact on physical realms of urban public spaces. This was conducted by way of case studies under three parameters, deducing that smart security features are collaborative in nature with multiple attributes acting towards a wholesome system of functioning. And a comparative analysis of pre-smart era and current smart scenarios was undertaken, that showed that in the first case, infrastructure remained independent, creating overtly laden sidewalks and public spaces impacting liveability in terms of public realms.

It concludes with a proposed ideology of a 'mesh of smart safety ecosystem' as an integrated mechanism. This further leads the way to develop in Indian urban contexts with the impending complexities and multiple components in public realm, architectural and urban

design guidelines imbibing essential principles of CPTED for effective and progressive safety systems.

The study proposes to further the research in terms of qualitative assessment involving people perspectives based on age-based user group opinions with on-field surveys to substantiate the learnings from case studies and arrive upon context-specific attributes to the CPTED principles of safety designs.

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“Understanding how the design of urban areas can negate the anti-social behavior and criminal activity.”
- Taking the example of Hyderabad Urban Areas as Case-Studies

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PHOTO-

THEME- URBAN DESIGN AND THE ROLE OF CPTED IN PLANNING URBAN AREAS

Cities and towns are developing into well-defined, heavily populated areas, but these areas have advantages and disadvantages of their own. With more residents, a city becomes more diverse, with individuals of all different classes and races. Yet, this diversity frequently breeds crime and a fear of victimization for people living in urban areas.

Most of these antisocial behaviors occur in public and neighborhood areas.

This paper tries to identify why public spaces are frequently the scene of antisocial behavior and other approaches to criminal and antisocial behavior beyond simply installing surveillance cameras. It examines the root causes and pressing needs for CPTED and offers a critical assessment of the evidence supporting this approach's effectiveness in crime prevention. It also discusses situational and dispositional approaches to preventing crime based on urban design modules and how designing cities based on opportunity reduction techniques with key themes of activity, surveillance, territorial, definition, and control impacts criminal activity in public spaces based on existing models.

A mixed **design technique/ Methodology** is employed, which includes the following steps:

1. Qualitative method- Insights and analysis of other publications and research papers.
2. Quantitative analysis in the form of a survey and an analysis of the existing urban area with and without the CPTED design measures incorporated in the metropolitan area.

It is done via an informal survey of approximately 30 people living in Gachibowli.

Limitation-

Despite lacking conclusive empirical evidence, the paper concludes that a substantial body of research supports the idea that environmental design is a practical and successful strategy for preventing crime.

Keywords-

CPTED; Public space; Urban design; Opportunity reduction methods; Neighbourhood.

Highlights- The paper intends to identify how the CPTED principles can be incorporated more humanly in the cities to create a sense of belonging among the citizens and between them and the city.

“Understanding how the design of urban areas can negate the anti-social behavior and criminal activity.”

- Taking the example of Hyderabad Urban Areas as Case-Studies

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Cities and towns are developing into well-defined, heavily populated areas, but these areas have advantages and disadvantages of their own. With a steady rise in population, a

city becomes more diverse, yet this leads to crime and a fear of victimization. People face various threats in urban areas, such as **crimes, street barbarism, acts of terrorism, incivility, fast-moving traffic, natural phenomena, and unseen problems.** Heath, T., Oc, T., & Tiesdell, S. (2012). *Public places Urban space*. In Routledge ebooks.

The public sphere and the development of better places are threatened by crime, safety and security, lack of security, perceptions of safety, and fear of victimization. These dangers result from the way metropolitan areas are developed.

The leading factor that gives rise to crime in urban areas are:

- People who need to be utilizing a specific location or setting. They do this because the way the urban environment is designed or because it is not being used makes them feel uneasy or unsafe. Poorly designed urban neighborhoods, including those with dark alleys, visually and physically separated places, subways, and graffiti-covered areas, are to blame for this sensation of unease.

Carmona, M., Tiedell, S., (2003). *Public Places- Urban Spaces*.

Residential flats have the same problem. That we have adopted is one out of many. Secondly, the concept can quickly become rigid and be used for far from scientific purposes.

Urban settings frequently cause a dread of victimization. Physical or visual barriers are being built in more and more urban locations to stop this victimization. This results in the physical separation and segregation of communities.

The term ‘territory’ is ambiguous—first, the definition is based on identity. Secondly, the concept can quickly become overly rigid and used for far from scientific purposes.

The overlapping of territories, however, usually leads to various types of tension.

Territoriality leads to segregation; the building of New Delhi in the 1910s and 1920s offers an excellent example of urban planning based on segregation, Dupont (2001). The empire was deliberately built at a distance from the existing ‘native’ town, Old Delhi. A vast stretch of land was cleared, left underdeveloped, and used to make the boundary between the two urban areas.

Dupont, V., Landy, F., *Segregation and Territory: What do we mean? A discussion in the Indian and South African Context*.

CPTED is an acronym for Crime Prevention through Environmental Design, which asserts that “the proper design and effective use of the built environment can lead to a reduction in the fear and incidence of crime and improvement in the quality of life.” Crowe, (2000, p.46).

This **paper** analyses CPTED principles and how they are used but tries to suggest other ways in which they can be used that are humane and do not segregate communities or spaces.

It talks about how CPTED principles have been used in different cities, taking the example of **Chandni Chowk** and **Gachibowli**.

These two places are selected as they have a combination of both private and public spaces. Numerous people visit this area.

1.1.1 NEED FOR CPTED STUDY

CPTED is a proactive or reactive action that leverages present environmental factors or changes them to lessen the likelihood of criminal conduct. The environment can be changed by making existing structures open towards the streets or by altering the flow of traffic for cars or people on foot such that there is no blind zone. *Huges, G., Mclaughlin, E., Muncie, J., & University, O. (2002). Crime prevention and Community Safety: New Directions. SAGE.*

If the opportunity to perpetrate crime is diminished or gone, crime declines. CPTED reduces the likelihood of crime occurring in and around your home. This may make your property less desirable as a target. People frequently feel insecure and believe that unpleasant conduct happens where there is a lack of maintenance.

1.1.2 DESCRIPTION

CPTED has five principles: **Natural access control, natural surveillance, territoriality, activity support, and maintenance.**

The two principles we will look at in detail are- **Natural Surveillance** and **Territoriality**. Moreover, how to incorporate these two principles into the design of Urban areas.

a) **Territoriality:**

Territoriality is the claim to a particular place; this claim prevents people from misusing the city or acting impolitely. This principle's design element tries to show who owns the land and other assets. This ownership can be done in two significant ways:

Symbolic barriers are signage, gardens, and landscaping-.

Natural barriers include fences delineating between private, semi-private, and public areas.

b) **Natural- Surveillance:**

The main goal of natural surveillance is to deter criminal conduct by making public areas easily visible. Even though official surveillance methods might use covert cameras and security guards, illegal activity is not hampered by a lack of personal contact.

c) **Natural access control:**

The construction of physical or perceptual barriers to restrict or reroute movement within a space is required by the third main idea of CPTED (this can be in line with or linked to territoriality). These are designed to prevent possible targets from entering or allow authorized people to exit (Cozens et al., 2005). Some examples are widening walkways, establishing straightforward entry and exit points, controlling access to certain areas (such as a housing complex), installing automatic gates or turnstiles to deter evasion, and installing bulletproof barriers at banks.

d) **Maintenance:**

The upkeep of a location fosters a favorable perception and demonstrates guardianship; lighting fixtures, driveways, paths, sidewalks, and gardens direct traffic through the site and make it so there are no hiding places for prospective offenders. Graffiti on public property or buildings, "broken windows" in homes or businesses, and litter are all examples of disorder and unfavorable perceptions undermining informal social control and cohesion.

Cozens et al., (2005).

e) **Activity Support:**

The community, the target group, picnicking, and park play are all encouraged by activity support. Design and signage that promote the desired use patterns are part of this. Although more pedestrians may act as more "eyes on the street" and possibly deter some crimes, this could also encourage crime and present new targets (such as pickpocketing). Cozens et al., (2005, p. 337).

These principles create areas that demotivate people to do criminal activities, increasing the risk of criminal activities in urban areas.

1.2 LITERATURE STUDY

To reduce the likelihood that crimes will occur, the Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) concept provides crime prevention from the very beginning of planning through the following methods:

- **Natural access control, natural surveillance, territoriality, activity support, and maintenance.**

Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) is a concept that focuses on locations that frequently become targets of criminal activity before highlighting methods that can lower criminal activity in the impacted areas (Taylor & Harrel, 1996). The criminologist and sociologist Ray Jeffery (1971), motivated by Jane Jacobs (1961), proposed CPTED in his study that linked crime to land uses and road designs in American towns designed for public safety.

Newman (1972) expanded this research by introducing the defensible space theory through investigations on the influences of physical environmental construction on criminal activities. Other researchers (Brown & Bentley, 1993; Shaw & Gifford, 1994) later followed suit, concentrating more on elements thought to serve as mediators in the decline of criminal activity.

A different method of preventing crime is called CPTED. It can be described as physical environmental designs that, through natural, mechanical, and procedural mechanisms, may lower the potential for criminal activity and the fear of crime.

Natural Methods

1. Dumpsters should not create blind spots or hiding areas, mainly when located in lanes.
2. Recessed doorways, alcoves, or other dark niches should not be created or removed to eliminate hiding places for potential assailant vandals or other criminal activity.
3. Loading areas should not create hiding places.
4. Signs placed within windows should cover at most 15% of the window area to ensure natural surveillance.
5. The lower branches of existing trees should be kept at least 10 feet off the ground.
6. Parking areas should be visible from the building.
7. Paths in commercial areas should be provided in a location with good surveillance, not blocked in by blank walls and dense landscaping.
8. The exterior of a building should be well-lit.
9. The mixing of uses should be encouraged.

Territorial

1. Public events such as festivals and outdoor concerts help to increase activity.
2. Property boundaries should be marked with hedges, low fences, or gates.
3. Private and Semi-private areas should be easily distinguishable from public places.
4. Lanes should be well-maintained with pavement and landscaping.
5. Use of furniture.

Mucano, K., Duda-Banwar, J., Klofas, J., (2018). Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design [CPTED]: Designing Out Opportunity and Fear: Rochester Institute Technology College of Liberal Arts.

The absence of design features that help in surveillance provides an opportunity for people to commit anti-social behavior.

In terms of design, if all the urban areas are designed very privately and inside gated communities, it leads to the opportunity for criminal activities on the main road as there is no direct link between inside and people outside. This does not mean that the privacies of the people should be compromised, and everything should open towards the main road, but specific design standards such as:

1. Designing areas in such a way that does not segregate communities.
2. Constructing amenities that people on the road can use.
3. Designating areas for informal activities as these people help in natural surveillance.
4. Designing third places such as cafes and small shops. These create activities that help in surveillance.

Similarly, areas are built inside fences and boundary walls to create territoriality and are majorly privatized. This leads to not knowing what happens outside these bound areas, often increasing opportunities for criminal activities.

1.3 RESEARCH GAP:

Even if both barriers serve to dissuade criminal activity, they can also result in the segregation of communities, and there is no way to predict what will happen when space is divided into Public, Private, and Semi-Public spaces. Lack of activity in the semi-public area may trigger uncontrollable actions. One such example is gated communities, which display social division, polarisation, and fragmentation. Walls and gates surrounding the gated community block public access to areas that would otherwise be accessible to all and easily supervised, such as playgrounds, parks, beaches, rivers, and trails.

How can CPTED principles be used without segregating communities and keeping a sense of belonging between the communities? This sense of belonging makes people more conscious of their environment and want to protect it.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A mixed approach is used in the research methodology:

1. Qualitative method- Insights and analysis of other publications and research papers.
2. Quantitative analysis in the form of a survey and an analysis of the existing urban area with and without the CPTED design measures incorporated in the metropolitan area.

2.1 SURVEY

From an informal survey of around 30 people, it is noted that people living in areas with little to no activities outside their perimeter on the road feel a sense of insecurity after 9 PM. In contrast, the presence of any activity reduces this sense. This is done due to natural surveillance. This natural surveillance is done via informal training, a connection with different communities, and when infrastructure is provided on the street that anyone can use.

2.2 CASE- STUDY

Two areas have been selected from different states to analyze how planning and the absence of CPTED principles affect how people perceive the physical environment.

Chandni Chowk-

One of the oldest and busiest markets in Old Delhi, India, is Chandni **Chowk**. Nearby is the **Old Delhi Railway Station**, where it is situated. The **Red Fort** monument is located at Chandni Chowk's easternmost point. Shah Jahan, the Indian Mughal Emperor at the time, constructed it in the 17th century. Canals used initially to partition the market and reflect moonlight are now closed. It is still one of the biggest wholesale markets in India. Chandni Chowk has a rich history of traditionally built structures and historic dwellings. Initially, even though Chandni Chowk was small and needed separate roads for cars and pedestrians, it was hectic. Following its renovation, Chandni Chowk is now a hive of activity that attracts people from all social and economic backgrounds.

The mixed-use dwelling and the numerous activities happening in the area were the primary criteria for selecting this space.

Gachibowli

Gachibowli is a neighborhood in the **Serilingampally** mandal of the **Rangareddy** District of Hyderabad, Telangana, India. Hitech City, another IT hotspot, is located around 5 km away. Numerous IT businesses, commercial spaces, and housing units are in Gachibowli. It covers a large size and is peppered with hillocks and rocky terrain.

Gachibowli was chosen primarily due to its mixed-use buildings, integration of many purposes in one area, and future center location where most social contact occurs.

3. ANALYSIS

3.1 SURVEY

When there is no sufficient visual link to the road or when open spaces are provided that are distant from the main road and have objects built in front of them that block visibility, unsafe conditions in the physical environment are created. Most people feel that POSH areas segregate communities. When there is no sufficient visual link to the road or when open spaces are provided that are distant from the main road and have objects built in front of them that block visibility, unsafe conditions in the physical environment are created. Most people feel that POSH areas segregate communities.

The divided residential neighborhoods need direct access to the main road. The vicinity of the gated community is also devoid of unauthorized activity.

Graph-3.1(a) Feeling Unsafe and its causes.

Graph-3.1(b)

Source- Author

Illustrations based on the analysis of these two surveys

Figure 3.1 (a) How the vision is obstructed due to boundary walls greater than 4m and trees with branches.

Figure 3.1 (b) Loss of vision when the loading areas are placed in an alley away from direct vision. Giving rise to sense of unsafety.

Figure 3.1(c) No direct vision in the parking areas leads to a sense of unsafety in the parking lots.

Figure 3.1 (d) Creating openings of spaces away from the main road and near vacant lots creates a blind spot and an area for illegal activities.

Source- Author

Figure 3.1(e) Levels with no direct surveillance or vision often leads to a sense of feeling unsafe and leads to a place where illegal activities can happen.

Figure 3.1(f) Placements of openings towards the main road create a sense of safety for the pedestrians; still, to maintain the occupants' privacy, personal spaces should be oriented inwards, but balconies should be oriented outwards.

3.2 CASE-STUDY

3.2.2 CHANDNI CHOWK

Figure 3.2.2 (a) Chandni Chowk

Source- The Print <https://theprint.in/india/delhis-chandni-chowk-gets-new-look-a-restoration-of-not-just-facade-but-400-yr-old-legacy/697319/>

Chandni Chowk stretches from Jama Masjid to Lal Quila. The stretch contains formal and informal markets, mixed-use buildings, and street furniture.

With street décor and lighting at strategic locations, the length is pedestrian-friendly. Additionally, many impromptu vendors, shops, and homes are on the top floors of the streets. In addition to houses, the road is dotted with hotels and shrines.

Combining all these actions makes the roadways safer, and others who use this area sense their safety.

In Chandni Chowk, the streets are designed to provide a sense of safety through the natural surveillance method, one of the CPTED principles. This natural surveillance is achieved through the following activities:

Analysis of CPTED Principles found in Chandni Chowk:

1. The maximum number of openings helps in natural surveillance, and as most of the shops open towards the roads, there is no blind spot.
2. Segregation of vehicular and pedestrian roads is present, yet the numerous activities in the streets deter incivility.
3. There is a smooth transition from public to private with no clear distinction; there is no segregation, yet it aids in deterring incivility.

No specific boundary walls or fences deter the segregation of communities. There is a gradual transition from the main road to the inner shops, yet that does not create blind spots where harmful activities can occur.

Figure 3.2.2 (b) Different types of buildings help in surveillance.

Figure 3.2.2 (c) Paratransit and Informal vendors on the roads help in natural surveillance.

Figure 3.2.2 (d) Informal activity around the main road that makes people.

u

Illustrations based on the case study

Figure 3.2.2 (e) Shops are placed on different levels of the road that helps in surveillance.

Figure 3.2.2 (f) Open spaces in front of the shops helps in surveillance.

Figure 3.2.2 (g) Informal activities.

3.2.3 GACHIBOWLI

Figure 3.2.3 (a) Gachibowli
 Source- The Print <https://theprint.in/india/delhis-chandni-chowk-gets-new-look-a-restoration-of-not-just-facade-but-400-yr-old-legacy/697319/>

Commercial, residential, hospital, and office buildings can be found there. One of the social hubs is this neighborhood, which is dotted with cafes. Gachibowli is built in a very upscale manner, with tall structures and extensive commercial areas covered in hoardings that obstruct the view of the road. This frequently results in a little less clear vision of the road. Parking is commonly used in the areas in front of commercial buildings, obstructing natural vision.

Traffic is not adequately segregated. Because the residential areas are supplied distance from the main road and have open spaces surrounding them, the risk necessary to engage in criminal activity there is reduced.

Border walls and fences divide communities and destroy their sense of belonging. Behind these boundary walls, there is no direct connectivity to the offices. With a smooth transition between spaces, some actions that are easier to govern occur.

Open lots are behind boundary walls, and mitigating the activities inside is challenging.

The space underneath flyovers is vacant, surrounded by boundary walls, often where illegal activities occur.

Some informal activities and shops do look towards the roads, but they are towards the inside and look inward, with no activities towards the main roads.

Analysis of CPTED Principles found in Gachibowli:

1. Informal shops are there that help in natural surveillance.
2. The presence of territoriality with fences and boundary walls.
3. Commercial buildings open towards the pedestrian roads help in natural surveillance.

Figure 3.2.3 (b) Parking between road and pedestrian space disrupts visibility.

Figure 3.2.3 (c) Informal activities.

Figure 3.2.3 (d) Residential areas away from the road with boundary wall.

Figure 3.2.3 (e) Obstruction and a break in visibility

Figure 3.2.3 (f) Residences away from the main road with open areas.

Figure 3.2.3 (g) Parking between shops and the main road.

Figure 3.2.3 (h) Informal activities away from the pedestrian road and parking in between the shops and pedestrian road.

Figure 3.2.3 (i) Boundary walls and spaces near flyovers creates a break in vision.

3. RESULTS

From the two case studies, it is derived that crime in urban areas arises due to poor management of the space and when there is minimal visibility of the room. Crime in urban areas cannot be mitigated entirely, but certain design principles can help to reduce crime. The design principle that was seen in both these two areas is natural surveillance. Vision/Eyes on streets cannot entirely eradicate crime in urban areas but can visibly lower it. When the reported crime rates for two social housing projects in New York (Brownsville and Van Dyke) were compared and studied, it was found that the high-rise blocks of the Van Dyke project had significantly higher crime rates than the low-level structures of Brownsville. Newman contended that the environmental design of the buildings was a causal element explaining the different crime rates between the two housing complexes despite the tenant populations in both projects being generally identical. The Van Dyke developments' high-rise apartments had a labyrinth of meandering hallways and public spaces with few places to be watched. According to Newman, more than half of all crimes were perpetrated in less obvious settings or where there was a chance of hiding.

Cozens, P., Love, T., (2015). A Review and Current Status of Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED). *Journal of Planning and Literature*, page- 393–412.

4. CONCLUSION

Jeffery (1971) argued in *Crime Prevention through Environmental Design* that the social reasons for crime had been exaggerated and that corruption's biological and environmental factors needed to be examined. He drew on social, behavioral, political, psychological, and physical characteristics to have a more multidisciplinary and comprehensive view of the causes of crime. Criminal behavior is influenced by both the internal environment of the brain and the outward physical environment.

The design of the physical environment plays a significant role in regulating urban space. It not only makes the environment usable for all but, through design, incivility and criminal activities can be deterred; as seen in the above case studies, making an environment safe is not just adding fences, segregating communities, and adding cameras. Like CPTED helps to lower the crime rate, Opportunity reduction methods create an environment where it is difficult to commit a crime.

Their primary goal is to reduce the likelihood of crime, using diverse strategies to deter even those inclined to do so. Situational crime prevention strategies can effectively combat some of the most bothersome types of crime, even though they may result in only modest decreases in crime.

A safe environment can be designed by incorporating **Opportunity Reduction Methods** in Planning.

It can be done in the following ways:

1. Increasing the perceived effort of the offense.
2. Increasing the perceived risk of the offense.
3. Reducing the reward from the offense.
4. Removing excuses for the offense.

Opportunity reduction methods can be used in planning the urban area. It is under surveillance most of the time by opening the windows toward the street, having informal activities, and providing amenities on the road. Good planning or an urban environment will make the space safer and deter criminal activity due to constant surveillance.

This constant surveillance of space makes it harder for people to commit crimes and increases the effort to commit a crime as people watch the area; it also increases the risk of committing crimes.

Planning also helps people to use the area appropriately without any excuses for harmful actions.

All of these plans that help in natural surveillance can be seen and found in old Indian cities; the main aim of the paper is to understand what these methods are that are more humane and do not segregate any community and how they can be used better.

Segregation can be mitigated by providing amenities outside the gated communities that prompt people to use them.

This doesn't mean these planning methods should be copied and pasted in the present context but should be thought about and modified to make it work in the current context.

This study concludes that a mixed-use setting is much more appreciated than standard zoning, bringing all the communities close.

5. CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Approaches to reducing opportunity are criticized primarily for their reputation and the potential for displacement.

The employment of opportunity reduction strategies has frequently raised concerns concerning the picture sent and the atmosphere of the resulting environment. For instance, expressed security concerns, crime prevention, and a heightened sense of safety have led to highly defensive urbanism. Nevertheless, urban areas and public spaces were made safe, but they lost their allure or began to frighten and intimidate potential users. Environments that are overly policed are oppressive to others.

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Women in Slum, Risking Their Safety to Access and Usage of Basic Sanitation Facilities-A Literature Review

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Abstract

The paper focuses on the safety of women in slums in accessing sanitation facilities. Various factors affect the safety of women while accessing or using sanitation facilities in slums. These factors are related to the infrastructure of toilet blocks, the location of the toilet, the route to the toilet, the timing of toilet use, and the number of toilets. Most of the women face sexual abuse or rape while visiting or using toilets or due to open defecation. The papers that were examined contained a variety of slums around the world, including industrial to coastal slums. The entire sample size (the number of individuals living in slum households and the number of slum homes) researched through the literature was 6663, and the period of the study is from past 12 years, i.e., from 2010 to 2022. The study found that most cases of violence or crime against women are due to a lack of lighting in and on the route to access sanitation and water facilities, lack of access to the toilet block, as well as the dangerous location of Public Toilets (PTs) and Common toilet complexes (CTCs). This paper is an attempt to solve problems related to women's safety while accessing or using basic water and sanitation facilities.

Keywords: Safety, Women, slums, Access, Water, Sanitation.

1. Introduction

The UN operationally defines a slum as “one or a group of individuals living under the same roof in an urban area, lacking in one or more of the following five amenities”: 1) Durable housing (a permanent structure providing protection from extreme climatic conditions); 2) Sufficient living area (no more than three people sharing a room); 3) Access to improved water (water that is sufficient, affordable, and can be obtained without extreme effort); 4) Access to improved sanitation facilities (a private toilet or a public one shared with a reasonable number of people); and 5) Secure tenure (Rev., 2015). In developing nations, urbanization leads to the establishment of slums, which are typified by environmental deterioration, a lack of access to clean water and sanitation, expensive electricity, and outdated housing stock (Belur, Parikh, Daruwalla, Joshi, & Fernandes, 2016). Sanitation denotes the access to and use of amenities and facilities for the safe disposal of human feces and urine. Men and women experience access to water and sanitation services and the fulfillment of these essential human rights differently. Lack of access to clean water and sanitation has a disproportionately negative impact on women and girls' health and dignity, making them more vulnerable and undermining attempts to empower women to live healthy, economically productive lives. When commuting to and from public restrooms, using public restrooms, or having to relieve themselves in the open because there are no facilities nearby, women who lack access to water and toilets in their houses may be at risk of sexual assault. Sexual assault against women is a major problem and Human rights violation (Lennon, 2011). Despite repeated attempts over the past several decades to reduce the number of people lacking access to adequate sanitation around the world, 2.3 billion people still live without basic sanitation facilities like toilets or latrines (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018). Due to a lack of facilities, women are sometimes forced to defecate in the open because there are no other options. The definition of sanitation can be broadened to encompass tasks like fetching water for sanitation activities, bathing, changing, and managing menstruation in order to gain a comprehensive picture of women's vulnerability with regard to sanitation-related activities (Banka, Joshi, & Kale, 2021). Women are expected to shoulder a lot of responsibility, and

because of the pressure to satisfy both family and personal needs, they are forced to accept dangerous circumstances and endure assault and abuse (Gowtham, 2020). In the case of Public Toilets (PT's), they may serve as crime generators if they are not strategically placed and correctly structured to prevent gender-based crimes like eye teasing, assault, and rape (Belur, Parikh, Daruwalla, Joshi, & Fernandes, 2016). PTs are viewed as the best choice for managing slum sanitation, but unless they are well-planned, they bring gendered dangers for women and children (Kulkarni, O'Reilly, & Bhat, 2017). Other reasons for violence against women with reference to sanitation and water facilities are poverty, lack of education as well as knowledge, old cultural beliefs, and lack of personal space. Specifically, poor or inadequate lighting in public toilets gives rise to feelings of insecurity and fear of being attacked. Inadequate toilet locations and dangerous routes to public facilities, as well as poor upkeep, encourage crimes against women. Some examples include broken windows and doors, missing locks, insufficient lighting, difficult bathroom accessibility, and a lack of guardianship (Belur, Parikh, Daruwalla, Joshi, & Fernandes, 2016). Due to such factors, women have had to resort to open defecation (OD). OD is the practice of defecating in open spaces that lack sanitation facilities (Banka, Joshi, & Kale, 2021). Fear of rape, especially at night, can lead to women not drinking fluids, experiencing chronic constipation, and using a bucket in their home as a toilet (Hildebrand, 2015). Moreover, the impact of abuse, violence, and harassment affects women and girls in many ways, not only physically but also mentally and psychologically.

Women "discipline their bodies" and restrict their food and drink intake in order to visit the toilet less frequently out of fear of harassment at public defecation places. According to the report, many of these women experienced urinary tract infections and required hospitalization as a result. According to other studies, such punishment might cause persistent constipation, diarrhea, increased rates of maternal mortality, and worsened menstrual and pregnancy symptoms (Banka, Joshi, & Kale, 2021). Poor sanitation is associated with transmission of several communicable diseases, including cholera, diarrhea, dysentery, and typhoid, as well as neglected tropical diseases such as schistosomiasis and trachoma (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018). As a result of sexual and other gender-based violence, women and children are at risk of contracting HIV/AIDS. Infected women experience more discrimination than men do as a result of the stigma associated with HIV/AIDS (International, 2010). To overcome such problems of harassment and violence against women living in slums to access and use basic water and sanitation, the implementation of policies that are easy to apply and will directly contribute to ending practices of OD in slums and informal settlements is necessary. The gravity of this issue demands increased attention and action as a vital element of the global effort to provide sanitation for all (Massey, 2011) The entire study is based on secondary survey, taking into consideration the time period of the academic semester, even though the indicators were validated through primary data collection through interviews. The paper focuses on problems faced by women due to lack of access and poor toilet infrastructure. The crimes faced by women have an adverse effect on their physical and emotional wellbeing.

2. Literature Review

The relationship between a lack of access to water and sanitary services and sexual assault against women remains underexplored and has not received enough attention to date. Women bear the brunt of inadequate sanitation services in cities, particularly in informal settlements,

often referred to as slums, which are impoverished urban neighborhoods. Inadequate sanitation is a major source of insecurity and indignity for women and girls (Hildebrand, 2015). The lack of toilets and bathrooms near their homes, especially after dark, puts women at significant risk of violence, including rape. People living in slums are subjected to a life devoid of dignity and are not protected from human rights violations. Inadequate water and sanitation facilities have been identified as potential influencing factors for this (Gowtham, 2020). Sometimes, women resort to washing their clothes or using the toilet in groups, or they ask male family members for accompaniment at night. However, this does not change the fact that the facilities are substandard and inaccessible. Many unmarried women who run households alone are unable to reach out to male relatives for help (International, 2010).

Most women are forced to rely on public restrooms that are inadequate and difficult to use due to a lack of personal water connections and toilet facilities at home. Despite an expansion in public water infrastructure, slum dwellers struggle daily, enduring both mental and physical discomfort, to fill their water containers. Women often wait for long periods, resort to shouting, fighting, and behaving aggressively to fill their 'allotted' canisters, and experience verbal, physical, and sexual violence. The use of facilities exposes them to foul and abusive language, which disturbs their mental health and sometimes leads to violent attacks. The same women who mistreat others also become victims when they are fighting for water. In addition to being assaulted by other women, men have also been known to commit acts of violence against women, most often verbal abuse that has occasionally escalated to sexual abuse. Women are often dissuaded from using the few available latrines in their communities due to a combination of distaste for the current state of the facilities, prohibitive costs, and fear of illness or violence. There was widespread use of so-called "home toilets"—buckets or plastic bags used within the home as toilets. However, this method came with its own set of problems, primarily a profound sense of shame (Massey, 2011). The use of a 'home toilet' was universally condemned, but there appeared to be no other viable options as women encountered the seemingly insurmountable hurdles of high cost, lack of cleanliness, and threat of personal harm associated with communal latrines (Massey, 2011).

In coastal slums, women face a high rate of sexual assault when using the restrooms. The lack of public restrooms forces women in coastal slums to walk long distances in search of secluded spots or to urinate in open areas along the beach. This situation increases their vulnerability to strangers or abusers and is a major contributing factor to the high incidence of sexual violence in these areas. Interactions with unfamiliar males can heighten anxiety for the woman and her entire family. Women in resettlement colonies face significantly less violence while accessing water and sanitation services than in slums, thanks to built-in toilets and water points close to their homes (Gowtham, 2020). An urban sanitation policy solely based on technical solutions will not ensure access to modern sanitation for everyone. Beyond technical and infrastructural challenges, unequal social dynamics, such as gender inequality and its intersections with other forms of inequality like religion and caste, also contribute to discrimination and inequality. These factors result in diverse experiences with sanitation. Some literature on gender and sanitation acknowledges identity-based discrimination against women due to their religion or caste, as well as prohibitive costs and bans on women using facilities at the whim of attendants (Kulkarni, O'Reilly, & Bhat, 2017). Open defecation (OD) sites increase risk and susceptibility for women as they are often located far from their homes and have additional risk-increasing characteristics. These sites

are typically situated in scrubland, undergrowth-filled woodlands, along canals and railway tracks, as well as on hillsides and erosion gullies. OD sites are generally poorly lit, if at all.

Regarding the issue of violence, women reported little trust in the willingness of the police to protect them from attackers or to take incidences of assault and rape seriously. The perceived unlikelihood of a fellow community member coming to the rescue of a woman under attack was also discussed (Massey, 2011). Other factors, including privacy, cost of toilets/inability to pay, cultural rules (e.g., 'it is a must'), and accessibility (e.g., hours of operation, proximity, and temporary closures), also emerged as considerations for women. For instance, the inability to pay emerged as a common factor for women who regularly chose to use bags, buckets, or open defecation during the day. This factor did not emerge for women who reported regularly using plots, buildings, or private facilities. These findings suggest that the inability to pay could influence women's sanitation practices (e.g., women opt to use bags, buckets, or open defecation—free options—when they lack the money to go to a public toilet). However, it may also suggest the opposite relationship (e.g., having access to sanitation alternatives other than public toilets, such as plots, buildings, or private toilets, eliminates the need to pay to urinate or defecate) (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018).

3. Methodology

The current paper is a review of previous research papers and the methods used in addressing women's safety in slums while using water and basic sanitation facilities. The papers that were reviewed included diverse slums, from coastal slums to industrial slums, from various parts of the world. The total sample size studied through the literature was 6663 (number of people in slum households and number of slum dwellings). The period of the study is from the year 2010 -2022. Figure 1 shows PRISMA flow diagram of literature review process for studies on violence against women and its impact on them while accessing basic sanitation facilities. Based on the papers reviewed, 12 indicators were finalized, and the related causes were identified. Through the papers reviewed, Table 1 was prepared, which highlighted the leading indicators for violence against women while accessing basic sanitation and water facilities in different slum locations. The literature that was reviewed presented various effects on women, taking into consideration the indicators shown in Table 2.

Various crimes against women and their impact on them while accessing and using sanitation and water facilities were identified, and the leading indicators were determined by studying various slums; the primary causes of violence were identified.

LOCATION	Bhalswa and Sunder Nagar and Sarapuri (North East district of Delhi)	Mithare is a collection of slums in Nairobi, Kenya	Nehru Nagar	Mukur	Mangolpuria	Chennai City (A total of nine slums and two resettlement colonies were included)	Slum communities of Jambula, Kiganda and Kifumbira in Kampala, Uganda	Katpuli, Kalakar, and Lal Khan and Swanton Ki Basti in Jaipur, Rajasthan; Anbedkar Nagar, Khadda West, Brasdar Nagar, Gosai Vast, Larmi Nagar, Lokamaya Nagar, Ganesh Nagar, Samantha Nagar, Rajiv Chand Nagar, Gulab Nagar, and Jabhim Nagar	39 slums in 4 cities: Kolhapur, Pimpri-Chinchwad, Navi Mumbai and Thane	Mithare Valley Informal Settlement (Mithare) in Nairobi, Kenya	Kanyamba compound, Lusaka - Zambia	Total
SAMPLE SIZE	N=42	N=65	N=142	N=77	N=31	N=50	N=32	N=112	N=531	N=55	N=26	N=663
INDICATORS												
Insufficient lighting/lighting	I	I	I	I	I						I	6
Lack of access to the Toilets	I	I		I		I					I	5
Dangerous location of toilet	I		I	I	I							4
Poor Infrastructure/Lack of Infrastructure in toilets		I				I	I					3
Insufficient timings to use toilets						I	I					2
High Cost for using Public toilets							I					1
Caste Related discrimination								I				1
Lack of Space for toilets											I	1
Lack of safety of toilet and surroundings of toilets			I		I				I		I	4
Lack of action taken by police				I								1
Less number of toilets							I					1
Lack of water in PT's								I				1

Table 1. Location, Sample Size, and Indicators for various forms of violence against women while accessing basic sanitation and water facilities. (I- represents an indicator specified by the authors of the reviewed literature) (Source: Authors)

EFFECTS	Sexual Abuse/Violence	Verbal Violence	Physical violence	Fear	Shame	Rape	Stress
INDICATORS							
Insufficient lighting lighting	IIII	I		I		I	I
Lack of access to the Toilets	II						
Dangerous location of toilet	IIIIII	II	I	I			
Poor Infrastructure /Lack of Infrastructure in toilets	IIII	II	I	I	I		
Insufficient timings to use toilets	II	II	I				
High Cost for using Public toilets	I			I	I		
Caste Related discrimination	I	I					
Lack of safety of toilet and surroundings of toilets	II	I		I		I	I
Lack of action taken by police	I						
Less number of toilets	II			I	I		
Lack of water in PT's	I	I					
TOTAL	27	10	2	6	3	2	2

Table 2. Effects and Indicators for various forms of violence against women while accessing basic sanitation and water facilities and its impact on them (I- represents an indicator specified by the authors of the reviewed literature) (Source: Authors)

4. Results

Figure 2. Percentage of various forms of Violence against women and its impact on them with respect to the indicators. (Source: Authors)

Through the literature review of the studied slums and the from the samples collected from the literature review as shown in table 1 and table 2, the percentages of various forms of violence against women and its impact on them were determined, as shown in Figure 2. Even though the indicators were verified through primary data collection through interviews, the study as a whole is based on secondary survey and takes into account the time period of the academic semester. Sexual abuse is one of the leading crimes against women, and the driving cause for it is the lack of access to toilets as well as the lack of action taken by the police. Moreover, the second most significant cause is verbal violence, which women face due to a lack of water in public toilets, causing them to resort to open defecation at locations where men are loitering. This issue is compounded by caste discrimination, which is also a leading cause for verbal violence; women of a higher caste often verbally abuse women of a lower caste. Other effects of crime include physical violence, fear, shame, rape, and stress. The causes or indicators for these issues are insufficient lighting, lack of access to toilets, dangerous toilet locations, poor or lacking toilet infrastructure, insufficient toilet usage times, high costs for using public toilets, caste-related discrimination, lack of safety in and around toilets, lack of police action, a limited number of toilets, and a lack of water in public toilets.

5. Discussion

The lack of access to and usage of water and basic sanitation is a problem faced by women living in slums all around the world. Moreover, access to sanitation and water are basic human rights, regardless of gender. There are many factors that affect the safety of women while accessing or using sanitation and water facilities, some of which are:

5.1. Poor Toilet Infrastructure – lack of privacy in public restrooms led women to use bags, buckets, or open defecation instead of going to the restroom. Women stated that “those toilets

are made with iron sheets, so you can see me if I am there inside. When people walk by” (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018). As shown in images 2A and 2B, women demonstrate how men can peep due to the lack of a roof and the presence of peepholes, leading to harassment and shame (Tembo, 2022). Many slum areas have community toilet complexes (CTCs) which often lack water access and are connected to septic tanks with the promise of future sewer connections. This rarely happens, as the politicians who gained favor by having them built may no longer be there to help the community, ensure water tankers arrive, or ensure the toilets are cleaned and tanks emptied. Due to overcrowding caused by an insufficient number of seats for the number of residents and because septic tanks are more prone to clogs than those connected to sewage lines, the CTCs soon become filthy and unsanitary. As a result, women and girls often have little choice but to resume using risky areas for open defecation (OD) (Kalita, 2017). The lack of a bin for sanitary pads in the current CTC design contributes directly to their uncleanness.

Image 1-Lack of privacy due to infrastructure
(Source -Amnesty International)

Image 2A

Image 2B

Figure 2A-Woman demonstrating how people peep inside her toilet, 2B- A toilet without roof and peepholes on doors. (Source- K Tembo)

5.2. Lack of Illumination or Lights in the Toilets as well as along the Access Path – Poor or insufficient lighting in public toilets can make people feel uneasy and fearful of being attacked. Insufficient lighting was considered a source of insecurity and a catalyst for crime. According to a systematic review, well-lit neighborhoods reduced property crimes like theft and burglary but had no effect on violent crimes (Belur, Parikh, Daruwalla, Joshi, & Fernandes, 2016).

5.3. Lack of Security – Whether it be open defecation (OD) sites, community toilet complexes (CTCs), public toilets (PTs) or community toilets (CTs), the security of women is a significant concern. Women often have to find someone to accompany them to the toilet, which wastes a considerable amount of their time. The location of the toilets plays a major role in women’s security; in some cases, there were liquor shops around the toilet, which compromised women’s safety. The OD sites are more prone to lack of safety as men often loiter around these areas, impacting women’s safety. Lack of police interest also hampers women’s safety and allows offenders to go unpunished. Sometimes, caretakers demand money from the visitors, which impacts the economic condition of women.

5.4. Lack of Access to Water and Sanitation Facilities – Many women claimed to use toilets in their homes or buildings frequently, while a few claimed to use public restrooms, at least during the day, simply because they were “nearby.” However, some women stated that

the lack of accessible restrooms in their neighborhood prevented them from using a toilet at all (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018). Those with access to a private or private-shared restroom acknowledged that women, including themselves, would occasionally use buckets or bags inside the home out of fear of being attacked (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018). Women often try to avoid going to public toilets due to unhygienic or inadequate routes to the toilet, as shown in Image 3. Moreover, the routes to the toilet are also unsafe, as depicted in Image 4, which shows a map produced by women of the Bhalswa slums.

Image 3 -Improper /Unhygienic routes to toilet block in slums of Kampala, Uganda (Source - WaterAid/Benedicte Desrus)

Image 4- Translated copy of map produced by women from Bhalswa slum (Source -Water Aid /Jon Spaul)

5.5. Improper Public Toilet Timings – In many slums, public toilets are closed at night. Women in the sample reported that their regular restrooms were closed or locked at night, and several others stated that the gates to their residences were also shut at that time, preventing them from leaving to use the restroom (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018). They often faced brief closures due to blockages, which prevented them from accessing their restrooms whenever they needed, even during the day. When the toilets became temporarily unusable, such as during blockages, it took time to reopen them, forcing women to resort to bags, buckets, or open defecation. Temporary closures, like blockages, frequently influenced women’s sanitation habits, leading them to use a different toilet nearby, within the building, or on the plot, or to return to using bags or buckets.

5.6. High Cost of Toilet Visits – Lack of money was a primary factor that led women in slums to avoid using toilets, instead resorting to bags, buckets, or open defecation. Most women stated that while they could afford a fee to use a public restroom during the day to urinate, they could not afford to do so consistently. Even paying to use a public toilet to urinate often proved too expensive for a number of the female participants in the sample (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018).

5.7. Dangerous Locations of OD Sites The dangerous location of toilets /OD sites refers to the area that is not safe for women, and the toilets/OD sites are located in those areas that are unsafe. To avoid going outside at night, most of the women in the study reported using open defecation areas near their homes or bags or buckets within their homes. Most female respondents claimed that their return to using bags, buckets, or open defecation was primarily driven by fear of being attacked or “bad things” happening if they ventured outside at night.

Due to this fear, women often defecated in nearby OD sites or used “flying toilets” or buckets, as shown in Image-1. The OD sites are more vulnerable to assault and harassment, as men hide, throw stones at women from behind bushes, verbally abuse them, and make offensive comments while women are defecating. This leads to a lot of fear, embarrassment, and can sometimes escalate to sexual violence. Men loitering or gambling around OD sites induces a lot of fear in women, but often there are no alternatives to OD sites.

Image 5-Use of plastic bags, buckets, or open defecation common practise by Women in Mathare

Image 6-Existing CTC in Kusumpur Pahari

5.8. Lack of Policies and Improper Planning and Designing of Toilets – Governments often favor communal and public restrooms as solutions to provide sanitation in slums, as they are less expensive, easier to implement in terms of constructing drainage lines and overseeing construction, and have fewer disadvantages. However, they do not address gender-specific issues, which persist in open defecation sites but with less strain on government resources (Winter, Barchi, & Dzombo, 2018). There is a lack of political will at all levels of the Indian state to develop, construct, and systematically maintain sanitation infrastructure. In the case of Community Toilet Complexes (CTCs), inadequate regular cleaning, maintenance, and water supply, as well as the failure of urban local bodies and agencies to take responsibility for designing toilets that cater to women’s biological and sociocultural requirements, frequently render them unfit for use. This happens because government sanitation policies have not been based on financing the development and maintenance of the entire sanitation service chain, which includes toilets, access pits, septic tanks, sewers that transport waste across cities, waste treatment facilities, and disposal and reuse systems (Kalita, 2017). Current toilet designs do not address two key needs of women and girls: biological needs and socio-cultural concerns. “Gender-responsive facilities are those that not only serve the physical requirements of women and men but also those that consider the social norms regulating intimate needs and translate these into sanitation architecture, which factors in the spatial situation, accounts for gender-specific constraints with respect to mobility and exposure, and offers more than one function (i.e., urinating/defecating)” (Kalita, 2017). An example of improper planning is shown in Image 2 of the existing CTC in Kusumpur Pahari. One can see why current designs do not satisfy women’s need for privacy with doors that only reach about head height. Note that the caretaker is on the roof doing repairs but could very easily peep into toilet cubicles.

6. Conclusion

Women living in slums are often deprived of their fundamental human rights to access and use basic water and sanitation facilities. The papers reviewed in this study highlighted the problems faced by women in slums around the world concerning sanitation. Each paper underscored the factors that render women vulnerable to violence, harassment, and sexual abuse in relation to sanitation and water facilities. The papers also critiqued the insufficiency and lack of planning in government policies. While toilets are constructed, there is often inadequate sanitation, hazardous locations, or the toilet itself becomes a site of crime. Many women are left with no choice but to resort to open defecation sites or use “flying toilets” (buckets or bags), as illustrated in Image 5. The impact of sexual abuse, violence, and sexual harassment greatly affects women, not only physically but also psychologically. This paper aims to spotlight issues related to women’s sanitation and safety, drawing attention to the problems faced by women and the correlation between poor sanitation and water facilities and sexual violence against women living in slums. There is a need for further research to find additional problems faced by women and to require innovative thinking to make sanitation facilities more accessible and safe for women in slums. Moreover the finding expose the need of further research on rethink and reviving current sanitation policies and include gender as an important driving factor.

7. Recommendations

In accordance with the literature reviewed, there is an urgent need to address women’s water and sanitation problems and propose suggestions and solutions.

1. The government’s strategies for slum sanitation and water facilities lack consideration for the location of public and community toilet complexes and the examination of gender as a factor in policy construction Therefore, sanitation policymakers, researchers, and developers might need to broaden their understanding of the types of interventions and policies that may yield the best results for access to and utilization of sanitation in informal settlements, particularly for women
2. Local community involvement in the provision, supervision, and evaluation of water and sanitation services is essential
3. Additionally, as men predominantly make decisions and formulate policies, there is a pressing need for women to serve as decision-makers, implement policies, and oversee their execution in the areas of water and sanitation
4. Proper and sufficient lighting should be ensured in and around sanitation facilities. Lighting not only enhances visibility but also signifies investment in the community, fostering community pride and informal social control, and sending the message that the area is under the guardianship of civic authorities Well-lit neighborhoods have been found to reduce property crimes as well as violent crimes, specifically assaults against women in public places such as toilets

5. The authorities, including police chiefs, should be encouraged to take sexual assaults seriously to deter potential offenders. The most effective strategies have been found to focus on both improving toilet security and enhancing toilet guardianship, either through increased police presence, vigilant community action programs, or the provision of suitable caretakers provided by private entities.
6. Women should be afforded access to loans or financing to install household toilets, given their frequent direct influence on household decision-making
7. The fees for Community Toilet Complexes (CTCs) should be reduced or made flexible.
8. The practice of issuing monthly passes for household members with unlimited visits should be considered over charging fees for single visits
9. Toilets need to have an adequate water supply, as well as improved infrastructure features such as trash cans for discarding sanitary napkins, to help protect women from violence and sexual harassment.
10. The construction of CTCs or public toilets (PTs) alone is not sufficient; they also need to be well-maintained, with local people involved in overseeing their upkeep.
11. The operating hours of CTCs and PTs should be extended to accommodate women's schedules and needs.
12. Toilets for men and women should be separated to enhance privacy and should be situated in easily accessible locations for women.
13. Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and local communities should be encouraged to use community mobilization strategies to map, monitor, and evaluate water and sanitation services. This will allow service users to hold service providers accountable.
14. The stigma regarding gender and diseases shall be well addressed and people shall be educated regarding the same.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
OD	Open Defecation
CTC	Common Toilet Complex
PT	Public Toilet
CT	Common Toilet

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Women are humans,
Accessing sanitation is their basic rights.
Sanitation is a basic need,
Whether women are living in slums,
Or living in city lights,
Walking to sanitation are their basic human rights.
Fights are there for sanitation,
Leaders are ignorant,
toward women fighting and crying.
There are problems.
Which are needed to be solved,
Policies are there, but not designed,
Gender is ignored while policies are awarded.
Public toilets are mess,
With dirty faces.
Toilets are there,
But safety is not.
Rapes are happening, but policies are still.
Women you need to stand,
Make place at the table,
You will sometimes fumble as well as stumble.
If there is no seat at the policy making table,
Make your own table and make this nation stable.
Make goddess Hygieia proud,
And fight for hygiene, cleanliness and a loud.
Good sanitation is a need of every nation.
There is no time to whine,
Standup and fight against crime
Women's sanitation safety is problem,
Leading to harassment, violence, rape, and crime
making women defamed
My review paper has claimed.

– By Ayush Prakash Hazare

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Analysing the conglomeration of various urban pockets through the lens of environmental design for crime prevention: A case of Kolkata

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Abstract

Historically, the built fabric of Kolkata had a dynamic morphological influence. The influences transfigured from the rulers; nawabs to British capitalism; zamindaris to political sweepstakes. This dynamism is not idiosyncratic and can essentially be distinctive upon closer inspection of the morphological carpet of Kolkata. Upon inspection, it becomes evident how, from the very beginning, crime prevention was catered to through the built fabric, irrespective of changes in architectural styles over time. Thus, be it central or north Kolkata or suburbs, the buildings would often have elevated, publicly accessible sitting platforms in front of houses, often referred to as 'Dalan'. These 'Dalan's' served multiple purposes, but most importantly, they catered to the four principles of Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) guidebook.

With the increasing demand, the housing market bloomed to the construction of just one particular type of building in Kolkata. This typology is apartment, be it apartment buildings or complexes. This scenario has created a cacophony of built fabric, slowly resulting in losing the city's identity. Most importantly, resulting in the loss of the natural security systems of the city. Thus, to maintain the natural security system, addressing the discombobulated policy, planning, and political juxtaposition is a subject on its own. However, denominating simple measures towards the problem that can bring out the desired outcome is the way forward. Measures related to case-wise urban design, planning, and design interventions

The research paper aims to address the issue and provide simple, implementable environmental design measures through a detailed survey in selected localities. The

methodology of the research paper focuses on area-based, requirement-wise intervention. These area-based selections are made across the Kolkata Metropolitan Area (KMA). The selection of areas would provide an opportunity to gaze across the KMA urban to sub-urban morphological carpet. The paper's key findings are based on the areas where a major role is played by the residential morphology, i.e., areas where people can be found 24x7. This is in relation to areas with time-bound use, such as institutional areas. Upon selection, the probable solution is to have a holistic approach. An approach that would also incorporate the 'Defensible Space Theory' by Oscar Newman. Furthermore, the approach to solution would help create the 'fit-all' category. With this category, the solution can easily be acquired and thereafter implemented in urban Kolkata core to sub-urban Barrackpore. Though, the scope of the paper will be limited to KMA. However, the 'fit-all' category would have the potential to be implemented in other urban areas as well.

Keywords: Built Fabric, Spatial Planning, Crime Prevention, Territorial Reinforcement, Defensible Space, Eyes on Street, Urban Planning, Urban Design.

1. Introduction

The conurbation of urban agglomeration is a natural way forward to the proliferation of the population. This synonym creates a conglomerate quality in urban fabric which dictates the behavioural pattern of the stakeholder (Shaw Clifford R, 1931). This behavioural pattern was taken into consideration early on for historic cities across the globe. The pattern here is dominated by socio-economic causes. Causes, which are a direct analogy of urbanization as mentioned in the 'Economics of Crime' (Bruce L. Benson, 2010). A relatively new field caused by rapid urbanization is a form of development that includes industrialization, specialization, and economic development (Malik, 2016). Development, which is also a conglomerate aspect of labour market pooling, trade, services, education, higher income, economic relations, and sumptuous lifestyle, becomes the pillars of urbanization (Malik, 2016). These pillars affect the architectural styles and their changes, which is directly related to the impetuous urbanized behavioural pattern.

The human behavioural pattern with urbanization is a conundrum of necessity and inducement. Crime becomes the inevitable part of the inducement. Thus, the need for crime prevention arose. Multiple approaches were formulated namely the legal system, social approaches, approaches related to crime perpetrators, and environmental design (M.Hedayati Marzbali, 2012). The methods for crime prevention are designed to influence fear towards crime, as mentioned in Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED); which is perceived to be a better solution. However, architecture also influences crime and reduces it. The design of the building and its exterior function have the ability to deter crime in an area (Newman, 1973).

CPTED has formulated various guidelines for crime prevention, though the guidelines are difficult to put through in the Indian urban context. Furthermore, residential areas are catered based solely on the observation method which again is based on perception, responsibility and action (Minnery, 2005) (Hedayati, 2009). This observation method is also influenced by the surrounding built fabric (Newman, 1973). Urban agglomerations in India can be contextualized with all the aspects of being historic conurbations with modern issues related to crime. Thus, addressing CPTED guidelines with architectural design in cities becomes crucial. Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify and analyze the architecture and planning-wise perception of people towards CPTED elements in regard to

crime. The analysis is intended to validate crime prevention and understanding of the present context of a particular urban agglomeration of India. In this instance, the case of Kolkata

The research topic here focuses on various urban pockets of Kolkata. Pockets as in areas where a distinct user can be identified and a commonality can be linked within these various pockets. The built fabric in historic cities like Kolkata plays a major role in user behaviour and the implications of security systems. These cities have witnessed gentrification and reverse gentrification creating a problem statement concerning user-based security systems. Thus, the paper focuses on understanding the present context through an extensive survey. This is to understand and compare the CPTED guidelines with historic conglomerative areas and find an approach to cater to the issues related to crime prevention.

2. Literature Review

The physical environment has a great influence on crime, fear of crime, and the quality of life. That relationship has become more evident in recent decades, as mentioned in designing safer communities: NCPC (Council, 1997). Crime Prevention through environmental design reveals multifarious, varied landscapes that weave Urban Planning, Architecture, Psychology and Criminology. Researchers, professionals, and practitioners have explored the tangled relationship between Built environments and Crime rates, attempting to understand the influence of design elements on criminal behaviour.

The word 'Crime' is defined from the Latin word *Krinios* which means 'to accuse' (Jahnavi S, 2020). In India, the definition of crime can be found in the Indian Penal Code (IPC), which is the primary criminal code of the country. The IPC defines various offence and provides the legal framework for dealing with criminal activities. The basic definition of a crime in Indian law revolves around the concept of an "offence." Section 40 of the Indian Penal Code defines "offence" as follows: "An offence is a thing made punishable by this Code." Section 2(n) of the IPC defines "punishable offence" as follows: "Punishable offence" means an offence for which, under this Code, the offender is, by a competent court, liable to be punished." In brief, a crime, or offence, in Indian law refers to an act or omission that is specifically listed in the Indian Penal Code or any other law and is punishable by a court of law. The "offences" are classified under broad categories such as: Against persons, Against property, Against Public order, Against Decency and Morality, Against the state, Against Public Health and Safety, Against Women, Against Children, Against Marriage and Family, Cyber Crimes, Economic Offenses, and Environmental Offenses. Moreover, there is no specific enumeration of "types of crimes" in the IPC. Hence, conceptualizing the term "Crime" remains ambiguous and so does "Crime prevention". Till today, there is no one comprehensive guideline for our country's context available, leaving apart a particular state. The crime Prevention field needs a document that could introduce CPTED concepts in practical terms for people working in communities.

According to the 2019 report from the National Crime Record Bureau, property crimes such as theft, burglary, and dacoity stand out as the most prevalent offences. Subsequently, crimes like assault, kidnapping, and sexual offences, including rape, come in the following ranks. According to NCRB data, the national average crime rate per lakh population of India stood at 2.1. West Bengal stands to be 4th in India in crime against minors. In 2021, among all the crimes committed against minors 2021, 67% of cases were related to kidnapping and abduction. Though Kolkata has been ranked as the safest city, the number of 'serious offences' increased to 1080 in 2021, from 981 in 2020 and 961 in 2019. In terms of Kidnapping of women, West Bengal is in the third position with 7,403 cases after

Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra as per the newspaper 'The Siasat Daily'. This manifold increase in the crime rate over the years has increased a lot of fear and anxiety in the public domain.

Fear towards crime can be explained as an emotional reaction as well as a sense of fear and anxiety that compels the individual to believe himself to be in a state of danger from the threat of crime (Stephen Farrall, 2007). Hence, it is important to engage in crime prevention measures to decrease both the occurrences of criminal activities and the sense of fear associated with them.

Crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED) is a tool for identifying, preventing, and solving local crime problems (Council, 1997). CPTED comprises four essential components: (a) Territoriality: This concept reinforces the sense of ownership and proprietary concern among legitimate space users, discouraging potential offenders and minimizing opportunities for criminal acts by deterring unauthorized users. (b) Surveillance: Rooted in physical design, surveillance facilitates natural monitoring by residents and their representatives. It contributes to effective guardianship by fostering an environment where potential wrongdoers recognize the possibility of being observed. This increased risk of intervention, capture, and legal action can dissuade offenders. (c) Maintenance and Target Hardening: This facet emphasizes sustaining a positive image and consistent upkeep of the physical environment, sending affirmative signals to all users. Introducing elements of target hardening elevates the efforts required for criminals to execute their activities, acting as a deterrent. (d) Access Control: The notion of access control restricts criminals' access to potential targets while amplifying their perception of risk. By denying easy access to targets and creating an atmosphere of heightened risk, this element diminishes crime opportunities. CPTED's four elements collaboratively shape a safer environment by reducing crime opportunities, enhancing guardianship, and curbing the appeal for criminal activities.

However, the measurement of all these elements of CPTED within research is still found to be limited (M.Hedayati Marzbali, 2012) (Stephen Farrall, 2007). Analyzing various Indian Cities has revealed the significance of the CPTED essential components in deterring criminal activities. While existing studies underscore the potential efficacy of CPTED principles, there remains a gap for further research and implementation, considering the dynamic nature of urbanization and its impact on crime patterns across India (Pandey, 2023) (M.Hedayati Marzbali, 2012).

In The Image of the City Lynch describes how individuals perceive and recall features in urban spaces. The most distinctive elements in the urban landscape - categorized in paths, nodes, edges, districts, and landmarks - give shape to individuals' mental representation of the city. In continuity with these, some localities constitute dual characteristics, i.e. the characteristics of the spaces change based on the functionality of the built environment at specific hours of the day. Thus, cropping up an inquisitive topic of understanding and perceiving a space in relation to the safety context, considering the dichotomy of the locality. Nevertheless, an explicit link between CPTED parameters and the duality of locality has not been explored yet.

In this study, three entirely different spatial localities have been considered with a common character in all of them. For the research paper, all four CPTED indicators have been considered for the analysis along with the observation method in context to the surrounding built environment of the localities to get a comprehensive result.

3. Methodology

The study involves three residential areas with an institution in each of the selected localities in Kolkata. The chosen sites are spread across Kolkata Metropolitan Area (KMA) with each site depicting a distinct perspective-based behavioural pattern analogy. **Site A** is chosen in the central core where the urban fabric had witnessed reverse gentrification and their correlation with an educational institute in terms of crime. **Site B** is adjacent to the city centre but a planned area where the planning was done to accommodate middle-income groups (Saha, 2021). However, at present residing high-income groups, thus, an area depicting gentrification. This is done in the context of an educational institute that caters to students from across Kolkata and outside. **Site C** is chosen on the outskirts of Kolkata in Rahara, with a nationally renowned educational institute encompassed in residential typology.

The sites chosen primarily are non-gated residence characteristics with an educational institute. This would not only help understand the correlation of perception towards timed activity spaces and twenty-four-hour activity spaces. Furthermore, this selection of areas was adopted from the guidelines specified in the report 'An Exploration of Sense of Community and Fear of Crime in Gated and non-gated communities' by Wilson and Doenges.

The criteria of selection of the site are followed as mentioned in the report, however, adopted and altered in the context of the city. The criteria's are as follows.

- a) Residential area with a prominent educational institute in the vicinity.
- b) The size of the residential property area. In the context of Kolkata, which is measured in 'Katha', the size taken is at least 0.5 'Katha'.

- c) A stable community with occupancy for a period of five years or more. In the case of Kolkata taken the occupancy period of more than ten years.
- d) Ethnic or racial composition. In this context, the change of ownership and the belief system are taken into consideration to understand gentrification and the correlation with crime if any.
- e) House design. In the case of Kolkata typology such as detached, semi-detached, and row housing is considered.
- f) House with accessible terrace/balcony units.
- g) Level of income. For the study income of the inhabitants in the selected locality is not considered to get a holistic perspective towards crime.

Based on these selection criteria the mentioned sites A, B, and C are chosen which were found to fulfil the criteria.

A population survey was conducted for the selected area in reference to the geoIQ population chart showing approximately 53000 people per sq. km. for the College Street area. From which the selected site is 0.25 sq. km. with an approximate population of 13000 for site A. Similarly for Salt Lake Kolkata, FE block the approximate population is 10000 people per sq. km. From which the selected site is 0.12 sq. km. with an approximate population of 1200 for site B. Furthermore, Rahara has an approximate population of 9000 people per sq. km. From which the selected site is 0.15 sq. km. with an approximate population of 1300.

From the conducted survey 300 samples were taken. The surveys were based on willing participation of the residents. However, only one member of a family was considered for the questionnaire survey. A face-to-face survey approach was conducted with random sampling to ensure that the participants fully understood the questions and that genuine answers were received. The respondents include homeowners, workers and regular passersby. This point was important to understand the viewpoints of various people along with their sense of responsibility towards that area. The survey was conducted in the morning and evening, both between 7 am/pm to 8 am/pm for a period of five consecutive days.

Thus, to understand the process of finding a solution, figure 1, below, shows a step-by-step process on how a conclusion has been drawn.

Figure 1 Methodology

4. Results and Discussions

The agenda of conducting this research was to analyze and understand the effect of CPTED principles consisting of Territoriality, Surveillance, Maintenance and Access Control, with the observation method with its base on the surrounding built fabric. In this particular research, each of the principles was assigned five parameters, to analyse the specific head. The items under respective principles were selected based on previous research papers and guidelines. Further, the parameters were measured using a Likert scale and validation of the items was done by conducting a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) using AMOS and SPSS software. The precedence of this research was conducted on the aspect of non-gated community in the research paper “Validating Crime Prevention through Environmental Design Using Structural Equation”. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a statistical technique used to verify the factor structure of a set of observed variables. CFA is a measurement model that is developed by the correlation between latent variables and several indicators (items) or known as variables and error manifests (M.Hedayati Marzbali, 2012). Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) serves as a statistical method employed to validate the underlying factor arrangement within a given set of observable variables. CFA permits researchers to assess the proposition that a connection between observable variables and their latent constructs beneath them is present. Latent variables are those variables that can be deduced indirectly using a mathematical model, derived from other directly observable or measurable variables.

To validate and establish a confirmatory test, an appropriate number of samples have been considered for the analysis. The measurement model for each of the parameters is developed through the software as shown in the figure below.

Figure 2 CFA Model for CPTED elements

Source: Validating Crime Prevention through Environmental Design by Structural Equation

The figure depicts that one latent variable, in this instance Territoriality consists of five items (observable variables) that measure its value. Factor loading value in CFA refers to the correlation between the original variables and the underlying latent variables or factors.

Fundamentally, these factor loadings indicate the extent to which each variable is connected to a specific factor. Therefore, factor loadings provide insights into the variables that exhibit the strongest connections with a given factor. In Figure 2, each of these individual items has its measurement error, and the quality of the individual items is determined by the factor loading **lambda**. Factor loading imparts information about the total number of variances contributed by each item towards the measured construct, and the factor loading value of 0.3 is used as a cut-off value to determine the suitability of the item in measuring the latent variable (M.Hedayati Marzbali, 2012).

Figure 3: CFA model for all the four elements of CPTED

Moreover, the level of reliability is determined by calculating Cronbach’s Alpha value as shown in table e below. The Alpha is a probability value which decides whether the data is reliable to analyze or not. The table shows that the Access Control Point has a reliability factor in negative whereas natural surveillance has a factor of 0.56 which indicates a good reliability value. Based on the model, the analysis that can be drawn is that the Natural Surveillance ($r = 0.56$) represented CPTED better than the other two dimensions (Territorial reinforcement $r=0.383$ and Maintenance and Management; $r= 0.366$). As the Access control point has a reliability factor in negative, hence it will be eliminated for further consideration as it does not contribute to CPTED in the chosen localities.

Table 1 Result of the measurement model of the CPTED elements

CPTED Dimension	Items	Description of Items	Factor Loading	Reliability
Natural Surveillance	Item 1	Clear sight lines.	0.58	0.56

	Item 2	Adequate lighting on the street.	0.84	
	Item 3	Large windows promote casual supervision of the street.	-0.26	
	Item 4	The exterior of the building is well-illuminated.	0.77	
	Item 5	Keeping shrubs and plants below window levels.	0.66	
Access Control	Item 6	Points of entry	0.33	0.18
	Item 7	Barriers to preventing unauthorized use of private spaces.	0.5	
	Item 8	Low, open-type fencing that indicates private space, but does not prevent natural surveillance.	0.82	
	Item 9	Eliminating design features that grant access to roofs or higher windows.	0.65	
	Item 10	Defensive plants around potential points of access act as a formidable barrier.	0.44	
Territorial Reinforcement	Item 11	Presence of sidewalks	-0.21	0.383
	Item 12	Fences—when kept see-through and low to the ground—provide not only territorial reinforcement but also natural surveillance and access control, Landscaping, which shows an active presence and often provides some level of access control.	-1.04	

	Item 13	Marked boundaries of private, semi-private, and public space via signage, change of material	-0.7	
	Item 14	Security cameras or other security measures	-0.18	
	Item 15	Areas like Dalan segregate between public and private spaces.	0.21	
Maintenance and Management	Item 16	Pruning and upkeep of lawns, gardens, or any other landscaping elements	-0.55	0.366
	Item 17	Regulated removal of trash and other debris	-0.14	
	Item 18	Strategically placed benches to motivate residents to sit and chat or people watch	-0.13	
	Item 19	Timely repair of broken equipment and replacement of burnt-out light bulbs	-0.28	
	Item 20	Activating public spaces through community engagement activities	-0.38	

The results achieved for the CPTED elements are bifurcated into five items each. These items are finalized based on the five pillars of CPTED by Pat Pellington. These items are analyzed further based on radar charts to get a clear understanding of the present scenario.

Figure 4 Radar Chart of Natural Surveillance

The radar charts of natural surveillance and access control indicate that outliers regarding eyes on the street from window openings become a contrasting feature with central Kolkata thus the parameter is showing a divergent graph. Contrastingly, access control is higher in planned areas like Salt Lake creating a deflating understanding of how the building works in correlation with the user in terms of crime.

Figure 5 Radar Chart of Access Control

Figure 6 Radar Chart of Territorial Reinforcement

The radar chart for territorial reinforcement, along with maintenance and management shows that though the delineation of private, semi private and public is poor but architectural features like Dalan are being used. This is in contrast with the maintenance of public and semi-private spaces. Thus, the increasing use of informal spaces with movable street furniture.

Figure 7: Radar Chart of Maintenance and Management

The findings in the study indicate that the parameters set by the CPTED can be used to measure Indian cities like Kolkata. However, certain alterations and incorporations are required to understand the crime prevention scenario for a historic, growing city. The current

data related to survey states that the only constructive form of surveillance is natural surveillance. Thus, contradicting the survey outcome in reference to the historic element of architecture, i.e., the concept of 'Dalan'.

5. Conclusion

The research paper tried to decipher the prevalent perspective and CPTED based crime scenario across three areas in Kolkata Metropolitan Region (KMR). Other research papers found were solely based on CPTED principles which needed other parameters to understand crime in historic growing cities like Kolkata. This indicates that CPTED measurements related to attitude, responsibility, action and belief systems were not taken into consideration (M. Hedayati Marzbali, 2012). Thus, the study indicates how the CPTED principles can be correlated with other measuring tools to obtain an accurate result.

With the parameters set in the research, it can be concluded that the CFA model can be used to retrieve data based on the surveys to incorporate CPTED parameters in cities like Kolkata. In such historic cities, the duality of usage must be catered to. This duality is to be catered based on the CPTED parameters and thus incorporated accordingly.

One of the most important points that was initially raised was regarding the 'Dalan' incorporated architecture style. The effectiveness in its present context and the change in the design of the same concept for the peripheral regions. In historic cities such architectural features become a key identity factor with important underlying uses. This is a difficult factor to measure and is only based on perception. However, upon surveying it was found that this particular architectural element though extremely important and useful, has lost its relevance in terms of security. These Dalans would now become a place where holdings related to political meetings or crime initiating and nuisance making took place. Thus, people are covering these Dalans with grills or sloping the surface so that it becomes unusable. Similarly, in the peripheral areas, these outside spaces are being used for potted gardening spaces. This not only beautifies the house but also restricts its use.

Thus, based on the survey, it can be concluded that small but effective measures can be taken to enhance natural surveillance. Measures such as bringing up wall art and colours to various pockets of the neighborhood. This would not only create more engaging spaces but also reduce crime as it helps alter the negative mindset (Charlotte Brady, 2022).

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Building Design Parameters for the Safety of Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder

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Abstract:

Building secure environments is becoming a critical measure as global crime rates are constantly on the rise, whether at the level of national policy or inside the safety of our own homes. Conversations and discussions on crime against women, children, and the elderly have been at the forefront for the longest time, while the injustice against individuals with disabilities continues to remain in the shadows.

Individuals with disabilities are severely vulnerable to criminal violence, mistreatment, and victimization. This paper focuses on the crime against individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and its prevention.

Individuals with Autism may feel sensorially overwhelmed in public spaces, leading to a huge risk of losing their way or other adverse scenarios due to cognitive (and physical) disorientation.

Hence, the built-environment plays an important role in generating a sense of stability as well as security for a comfortable experience for individuals with all kinds of disabilities, be they visible or invisible.

Further, there may be traits associated with Autism that increase or decrease an individual's tendency to breach the law. They may struggle to regulate their aggressive behaviour, and emotions, and misinterpret other people's viewpoints. They could exhibit problematic behaviours that draw the authorities such as law enforcement into the picture. Nevertheless, individuals with ASD also regard laws and norms as beneficial in the context of comfortable, non-threatening surroundings.

The objective of this research is to widen the horizons of Crime Prevention Through Environment Design (CPTED) in the case of interventions for individuals with intellectual disabilities. The paper aims to open doors to this domain of research, especially with the advent of technology and subsequent crime.

The methodology of this research paper aims to study the sense of safety generated by the built-environment within an individual with Autism, and their response. Further analysis has been included on how a secure environment can be designed while keeping security systems in perspective. Case examples from parts of Australia have been reviewed in this context after having looked at the global CPTED strategies in detail. Although there is a growing

body of knowledge on this subject, the best design practices are still unclear. The research includes suggestions and recommendations on how the original CPTED guidelines can be viewed through the lens of autism and other intellectual disabilities.

Thus, this research aims to uncover and establish parameters essential to create a safe and secure built-environment for individuals with ASD within the existing CPTED guidelines. The paper focuses on establishing the eminent role of CPTED in the design of the built-environment to enhance the inclusivity at a contextual level.

Keywords: Crime; Disability; Victimization; Cognitive; Sensory

1. Introduction

A safe built-environment is an outcome of a human-centric building design approach that is not only accessible but inclusive and efficient in multiple respects. Individuals with disabilities face the brunt of fast-paced urbanization contributing to a significant increase in misconduct towards individuals. Crime and corruption are inevitable in any country, especially where there is a lack of strict regulations. A framework to create safe and secure built environments is imperative to establish a sense of relief among individuals who are more likely to be victims of adversities of this nature. In the case of individuals with disabilities, per se, for those belonging to the umbrella of neurodiversity, crime comes much later or may manifest in the form of general misconduct. Individuals with Autism may be considered the weakest in the shadow of crime in the sense that their general comprehension of their surroundings is poor and implicates negative nuances in and through their behavioural responses.

Fig. 1. Relation between Autism and Crime

Source: Author

A sense of security does not exist only on the physical level, but also at the mental and social level. Initiatives for the safety of individuals with a visible disability are being incorporated into the public sphere, while the case of invisible disabilities, such as Autism is still being

established. According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Fig 2), mentioned in his paper- "A Theory of Human Motivation" published in 1943, the needs he discusses are crucial to human survival out of which safety needs come on second place after physiological needs (Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, 2022).

Fig. 2. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Source: Simply Psychology

Globally, there are about 1000 million people with disabilities, or around 15% of the world's population, or one in every seven people. Between 110 million to 190 million of these individuals struggle significantly with daily functioning. A moderate or severe impairment is expected to affect 93 million children, or one in every twenty children under the age of 15 (World Health Organization, 2015). As populations age and the prevalence of chronic health issues rises worldwide, the number of individuals who experience impairment will continue to rise. Trends in environmental circumstances, health conditions, and other causes, such as traffic accidents, falls, violence, humanitarian catastrophes including natural disasters and armed conflict, unhealthful diets, and drug addiction, affect national patterns of disability (World Health Organization, 2015).

Approximately 15% of adults in the world have a disability, apart from which there is an increasing number of the aging population. The concerned aging population is also at a high risk of disability with an exponential rise in cardiovascular, mental, and other such illnesses (World Health Organization, 2011).

As humans are part of a biodiverse system, a lot of environmental and social factors are responsible for this phenomenon, with the recognition that "disability results from the interaction between persons with impairments and attitudinal and environmental barriers that hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others" (Hughes et al., 2012).

2. Risk Factors for Individuals with Disabilities

Around half a million adults become victims of interpersonal violence and end up losing their lives, while a few are subjected to adversity from socio-occupational consequences. Various factors, in the case of individuals with disabilities, contribute to their increased suffering from criminal offenses (Saxton et al., 2001). A few of them include exclusion from learning opportunities and employment, the need for day-to-day personal assistance, reduced physical and emotional defenses, comprehension and communication barriers that hamper the reporting of crime, societal stigma, and discrimination (Hughes et al., 2012). Some risk factors are mentioned in Table 1.

Type of Disability	Risk Factor
Physical Disability	A person with a physical disability may need assistance from others to meet their basic needs. Caregivers can play an important role in intimate care routines such as bathing, washroom, and grooming, which may give them opportunities for harming the individuals.
Cognitive Disability	A person with a cognitive disability may showcase too much faith in others and may become a victim of trickery or bribery. The person may not know the differences between sexual and non-sexual touches and not know that the sexual violation is not alright.
Learning Disability	A person who has a disability that impacts their ability to communicate faces additional barriers to disclose abuse or assault.

Table 1: Types of disabilities and risks involved

Source: The Arc's Autism Now Center, 2023

The media captures the plight of individuals with disabilities to a large extent, by reporting cases of sexual abuse, bullying and other major forms of hate crimes in different environmental settings ranging from homes to public spaces (Shamash, 2013). In a country such as India, it is a task to quantify the extent of crimes against individuals with disabilities, as the definitions of both of these terms (crime and disability) are open-ended. However, the first step in the prevention of the crime mentioned is acknowledging the existence and magnitude of the crime. This information will only be fruitful if the following four-step approach is undertaken:

Step 1: Identification of the individuals with disabilities in the country (Followed by listing their details at the city level.)

Step 2: Identification of the needs, risk factors, and violence faced by individuals with different disabilities. (This includes documentation of their experiences and requirements).

Step 3: Designing the built-environment such that it not only provides comfort but also establishes a sense of security among people (including caregivers).

Step 4: Lastly, it is important to set up a system of communication in public as well as private buildings, especially in the case of an emergency.

In many cases, individuals with a disability may inflict self-harm or harm those around them as well (The Arc's Autism Now Center, 2023). This is most prominent in the case of individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder and other neurodivergent conditions. Multiple factors create hostile situations and can result in unfavorable consequences, as listed in Table 2.

Factors causing Threats	Unfavourable Consequences
People with disabilities are asked to be obedient, passive, respectful, and to keep negative behaviours in check. This is called compliance training.	Abusers take advantage of abusing these individuals by tricking them into harmful and abusive situations.
People with disabilities sometimes grow up without sex education, abuse prevention information, or assertiveness education.	People with disabilities may not be aware of their bodies, healthy sexual boundaries, or how to know if someone is being abusive.
A person with a mental health condition may be disoriented leading to a lack of differentiation between reality and non-reality from their mental health symptoms	An abusive person may take advantage of or harm an individual with a mental condition.

Table 2: Threats leading to unfavourable consequences

Source: The Arc's Autism Now Center, 2023

3. Society and Disabilities

Individuals with disabilities have been subjected to dreadful human rights violations in the past. Yet despite well-documented and extensive regulations for the welfare of mankind, one billion persons with disabilities remain neglected by the international laws, legal processes, and institutions that seek to amend the cause of those violations, including crimes against humanity (Pons et al., 2021). Early case studies suggest an association between Autism Spectrum Disorder and violence (Baron-Cohen, 1988; Mawson et al., 1985).

The design of habitable spaces is the starting point to incorporate inclusivity into society in a holistic perspective, all the way from designing inclusive toilets, with the help of universal design standards to the addition of accessibility features such as ramps, lifts and handrails. Further, features such as cameras, access control and emergency buttons provide reassurance and a sense of comfort to individuals with disabilities.

3.1. Individuals with Autism and crime

In many instances, individuals with Autism may resort to self-harm or may cause harm to the environment by being triggered by to unfavourable environmental conditions. The difficulties in cognition of individuals with Autism adversely affect their responses in society. There

have been a lot of cases of individuals with Autism offending the US Criminal Justice System (Blackmore et al., 2022). Not only that, in their daily lives also they may face issues in comprehension of the environment and the other users in the context. The parents, teachers, doctors, and care-givers of these individuals have to be cautious at all times in order to maintain a healthy frame of mind and behavioural state. Individuals with Autism are hyper-sensitive (overstimulated) and hypo-sensitive (understimulated) to temperature, pain, sound, light, texture, and people around them and insignificant stimuli might cause discomfort or pain to them.

Further, a lot of information is available on interpersonal violence, child maltreatment, and bullying of individuals with Autism Spectrum conditions, which can further be classified as intimate partner violence, youth peer pressure, and other forms of victimization (Hamby & Grych, 2012). As it is individuals with Autism have a lot of impairments in social communication and social interaction across multiple contexts, and showcase constrained interests and/or repetitive body movements and mannerisms. (Association, 2022).

This can have an adverse impact on the functioning of their mind and body. The prevalence of crime in the environment not only accentuates the negative implications accompanying the situation but also create unfavourable scenarios for all the stakeholders mentioned above.

Silos had been created in terms of the different types of crimes, victims and criminals, causing a failure in the field of research in this domain to identify the limits and extents of the nature of interpersonal crimes in different kinds of built environments and diverse contexts. Thus, it can be noted that the stakeholders in close contact with individuals with Autism are primarily looking into this field, being enveloped in a silo.

4. Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) and the Built Environment

4.1. Global Guidelines

The Preamble from the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), quotes "Recognizing that women and girls with disabilities are often at greater risk, both within and outside the home, of violence, injury or abuse, neglect or negligent treatment, maltreatment or exploitation" (United Nations, 2008). This statement might appear to hold relevance only in the case of women and girls, however, it has proven to be crucial for the complete umbrella of disabilities. The UNCRPD (United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities) states that people with disabilities have an equal right to social protection. Safety nets are a type of social protection intervention that focuses on vulnerability and poverty (United Nations, 2007).

In the Indian context, Chapter 5: Social Security, Health, Rehabilitation, and Recreation of The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act talks about "Social Security" as a key driving force in the survival of individuals with disabilities, while Chapter 2: Rights and Entitlements looks into their protection and safety (*The Rights of Persons With Disabilities Act, 2016*).

S. No.	Section	
1.	Protection from cruelty and inhuman treatment	The appropriate Government shall take measures to protect persons with disabilities from being subjected to torture, cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment.
2.	Protection from abuse, violence and exploitation	The appropriate Government shall take measures to protect persons with disabilities from all forms of abuse, violence, and exploitation
3.	Protection and safety	Persons with disabilities shall have equal protection and safety in situations of risk, armed conflict, humanitarian emergencies, and natural disasters.

Table 3: Chapter 2: Rights and Entitlements, RPwD Act 2016

Source: The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016.

One of the most important agendas of the Smart Cities Mission, as mentioned in the Harmonised Guidelines & Standards For Universal Accessibility in India 2021, is the safety and security of individuals, apart from affordable housing, efficient urban mobility, and public transport (Government of India, Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs (MoHUA), Union Department of Public Works, 2022).

4.2. Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED)

The course of designing security as a part of a built environment is recognized as "Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design" (CPTED). It involves suitable design interventions in the built environment to reduce the opportunity for, and fear of, predacious crime against any individual. CPTED takes advantage of opportunities for natural access control, surveillance, and territorial reinforcement (Building Resilience: Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design | WBDG - Whole Building Design Guide, 2018). This process is beyond the use of locks, gates, and alarms to secure buildings. CPTED strategies are implemented through an overlap between three methods, as shown in Fig. 3. (Atlas, 2013).

Fig. 3. CPTED Strategies

Source: Randall I. Atlas

With the upcoming use of assistive technology for the comfort of individuals with disabilities and an increase in the use of Building Automation Systems (BAS) globally, the marriage of architecture and electronics in this context is a suitable one. Further, any human-centric design requires a human touch, where organizational strategies come into the foreground—security guards and police being the key role players.

The applicability of CPTED is beyond essential in the case of public buildings, especially in schools, transit hubs, and office buildings.

CPTED involves certain concepts for the fulfillment of a secure architectural design; the following is the list of the same.

- a) *Natural Surveillance*: This is an observational intervention wherein the provision of legitimate eyes on users of a space keeps them in check. The ultimate goal should be to increase the population density in areas that are more prone to crime.
- b) *Natural Access Control*: This concept dwells on the idea of boundaries, where access beyond a certain point is controlled; this may be through doors, fences, or shrubs. Psychological barriers may also play a crucial role in access control with the help of signage, nature strips, or directional pathways.
- c) *Territorial Reinforcement*: Territorial control is essential to keep intruders at bay, and this may be achieved by expressing spatial ownership. A sense of belonging among users keeps them safe and helps them extend a sphere of influence against imposters.
- d) *Maintenance and Management*: The physical image of an area may contribute to a major extent to its level of security, and this can be achieved mainly through maintenance and management of pre-existing safety systems.

4.3. Effect of the Built-Environment on Neurodiverse Individuals

A lot of research at the global level has been conducted on CPTED as a subject. Further, there is even less research on the causes of individuals with disabilities, especially Autism, and their fears as well as feelings (Rose, 2021).

The built-environment plays a crucial role in establishing a sense of security among individuals with Autism, while also instilling it in real-time. However, the reverse is also true. An unfavourable environment is adequate to disorient an individual with Autism, followed by increased crime in the picture. Thus, a sense of fear is easily generated in their minds.

5. Materials and Methods

The architecture and design of a building often depend on the presence of risk factors concerning the various, homogenous population experiencing the environment (Kazdin et al., 1997). A risk factor as also noted earlier, is “a characteristic, experience, or event that, if

present, is associated with an increase in the probability (risk) of a particular outcome over the base rate of the outcome in general (unexposed) population” (Kraemer et al., 1997).

The methodology of the paper includes taking crime prevention for environmental design into perspective as a concept in detail and understanding all the parameters that come under it. Further, a few case examples were looked into from Australia, where certain CPTED measures have been applied for the inclusion of individuals. From the overall understanding of CPTED as a concept and the case examples, suggestions or modifications for individuals with autism what defined as the starting point of research in this particular domain.

The method of research includes an overview of case examples in the form of secondary research (mainly from Australia), of environments where the role of CPTED has proven to be effective in the reduction of crime against individuals with Autism. The information gathered from the case studies has been translated into a table to accommodate recommendations specific to Neurodiversity. Australia has advanced as a country in this field, and thus, case examples from there are suitable for this study.

Multiple relationships were drawn between autism and crime or abuse against individuals with autism in society and how they can also cause self-harm or harm to caregivers and other stakeholders due to the unfavourable nature of their behaviour. The environment plays a major role in influencing the behaviour of individuals with autism which is why the environment is also crucial in curbing abuse against them. The results include recommendations for variations in the original CPTED parameters for the inclusion of all individuals in society.

5.1. Case Studies

5.1.1. Logan Central, Logan City (Queensland, Australia)

A study was conducted called “Urban Jungles Project” by the Queensland University of Technology (QUT), partnered with Logan City Council (LCC), Queensland Health and the Queensland Police, to answer a very basic question: *What prevents public urban spaces from being inclusive of everybody?*

The answer will be the guiding light to understanding the inter-relationships between the public realm and people experiencing neurodiversity (Guaralda et al., n.d.).

A series of examinations and documentation in the form of site study and mapping were conducted to find relevant data to understand the appropriate methodology applied to record the extent of inclusivity in an area and the security measures crucial for the same. Great importance was laid on the role of the same in neurodiversity.

The following are the steps included:

- a) The study aimed at examining the public space system around Logan Central while mapping the area’s sensory triggers against the existing navigational routes.
- b) This exercise was followed by a survey of all the activities and events that brought the people of the community together during the latter part of the year.
- c) An assessment of the physical state of the region is the first step in another mapping investigation. While performing the site tour, three observable conditions were

mapped: physical damage to structures; excessive ground litter; and specific locations where he saw anti-social activities (Guaralda et al., n.d.).

This research brings forth the understanding that some contextual settings may prove to be difficult to comprehend and hence navigate through, as certain sensory triggers may be absent or uncontrollable. This can hurt individuals who are unable to filter out environmental inputs.

Following are a few points that can be considered from the perspective of CPTED, in the case of Logan Central:

- The original principles of CPTED have been employed by the Logan Central Council, yet there is an absence of sensorial inputs such as proper lighting acoustics to help orient the individuals (Guaralda et al., n.d.).
- Each of us has sensory preferences (Carvill, 2001), hence, there is a need to zone areas using sensory profiling.
- It is imperative to interpret the sensory information received through cognition, perception and orientation; that is where environmental cues such as colour-coded signage (not just signage) and the use of texture come into play (Lane et al., 2009).

Thus, through a unique methodology the built-environment can be read and various sensorial applications can be incorporated to induce an enhanced experience for all users.

5.1.2. Perth Metropolitan Schools (Western Australia)

Crime in the form of bullying has taken center stage in building design. Hence, this particular study was done to record how bullying is exhibited as an ill-behaviour due to elements of the built-environment in schools located in Perth, Australia.

The research methodology included interviews and surveys, both online and face-to-face using semi-structured guides of the school staff, students, and parents (Francis et al., 2022)

The following built-environment factors are linked to bullying in school buildings:

- **Visibility and Supervision**

Visibility and supervision included lighting and windows, crowding, and school size and security cameras as sub-factors. Proper lighting played an important role in timely intervention in situations of bullying; further, the idea of supervision instilled a sense of fear in the minds of the oppressors. Crowded areas were considered negative spaces in this research due to limited supervision.

- **Physical and Psychological Comfort and Safety**

Ventilation and temperature, acoustics and noise, queues, aesthetics, vandalism, and maintenance, along with furniture and seating, were considered the major components of the physical and physiological comfort and security factors on the school premises. Transition spaces such as corridors and staircases were identified as harassment zones due to the slow

movement of the users. Many people also felt that neurodiverse students may struggle with the poor allocation of seats.

- **Social-Emotional Competencies**

This factor concentrated on elements affecting bullying through social and emotional abilities of individuals and their implications for the victims.

Lighting and crowding were equated to visibility and comfort by the participants. The study concluded with the establishment of the need for advanced research for neurodiverse victims of bullying and other such crimes, especially in schools (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, Australian Government, 2021).

6. Results

The study looked into the application of CPTED strategies in the public spaces and schools of Australia and translated the existing strategies into those suitable for neurodiversity (in the form of recommendations). The case studies provided insight into the different parameters useful in designing secure and mainly inclusive spaces for diversity in age, class, gender, and abilities. The following table (Table 4) is a cumulative pool of the built-environment parameters that can be derived from the case studies.

Case Study	Suggested Parameters	Elements of Design
Logan Central, Logan City (Queensland, Australia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation • Customizable Zones • Cognition and Wayfinding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proper lighting and acoustics • Spatial configuration and sensory profiling of space • Colour-coded signages, texture
Perth Metropolitan Schools (Western Australia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visibility and Supervision • Physical and Psychological Comfort and Safety • Social-Emotional Competencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate spatial configuration and proper lighting • Thermal comfort, acoustics, aesthetics and maintenance • Sensory profiling of space and quiet zones

Table 4: Suggested Design Parameters from Case Studies

Source: Author

This information can be converted into direct recommendations for the application of the concepts for CPTED to cater to the neurodiverse inhabitants of the place. The table given below (Table 5) showcases how the elements of CPTED can be tweaked and made comprehensive not only for architects and planners but also for the users of the space. A combination of physical, cognitive, and sensorial elements needs to be applied to create an

inclusive environment in the truest sense. This can be achieved if all the user profiles are taken into account.

In India, the Harmonised Guidelines & Standards for Universal Accessibility in India 2021, are a stepping stone in this direction. As it has been established that individuals with disabilities are more prone to abuse and crime, the curbing of these negative activities in societies is extremely crucial. However, the placement of CCTV cameras and automated access controls is not enough; constant monitoring and maintenance are even more essential. Small children and elderly should be taken into account while designing any typology of building, as they may not be disabled, but require more attention. The security of women should be taken into account at every step.

CPTED Concept	Applications	Recommendation for Neurodiverse Individuals (ASD)
Natural Surveillance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforcing Activity Generators • Design for Programming Activity Mix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluid Transition Spaces • Connected Spaces • Appropriate Lighting and Acoustics
Natural Access Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal Surveillance at Access Points 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Signage and Maps • Colour-coded Areas and Pathways • Use of Landmarks
Territorial Reinforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ownership Signages • Localized Area Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zoned Areas according to Sensory Profiles • Functional Isolation (Quiet spaces)
Maintenance and Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting Maintenance • Vandal-resistant material use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensory Sensitive material use • Regular Maintenance Overview

Table 5: CPTED Recommendations for Neurodiversity

Source: Author

The case examples taken from Australia are also a work in progress in this domain as continuous research is taking place as technology is changing, along with this the nature of crime is also changing which is a cause of concern, hence, optimal environmental design is an important driver in building security and safety.

7. Conclusion

Crime Prevention through Environment Design is a very sought-after field of research, especially with the growing population of differently-abled individuals. It plays a pivotal role in creating a holistic and universal environment that is human-centric at its core. This research has been focused on Australia as it is a continent incorporating CPTED in the design decisions for the inhabiting neurodiverse population. Many other countries, including India are moving in this direction; however, stringent measures are the need of the hour. As architects, it is our role and responsibility to incorporate the needs of all the users of the environment and chart out a human centric design system, be it in the case of crime prevention or security. In recent times, focus is being laid on Autism centres and schools for children with Autism across the globe, however the youth, adults and elderly with Autism need to be brought into the picture. The profession of architects, planners, and designers has a creative as well as a technical edge to it, such that there is a well thought out environment to live in for all.

Individuals that belong to the neurodiversity umbrella, such as Autism, already have a lot on their plate, and becoming victims of society-inflicted crimes simply adds to their melancholy. Thus, it is not only crucial but necessary to incorporate methods to prevent crime and create a secure environment for them. The parameters suggested in this research are only the tip of the iceberg, and many solutions can be integrated into the built-environment design process. It is central to be mindful right at the beginning of the concept stage as the safety and security of Individuals cannot be an afterthought. Lastly, as suggested through this research, safety is not a luxury but a human right for existence in this world and should be achieved at all costs.

8. Acknowledgements

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9. Conflicts of Interest

We wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication.

10. Funding

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Type of Disability	Risk Factor
Physical Disability	A person with a physical disability may need assistance from others to meet their basic needs. Caregivers can play an important role in intimate care routines such as bathing, washroom, and grooming, which may give them opportunities for harming the individuals.
Cognitive Disability	A person with a cognitive disability may showcase too much faith in others and may become a victim of trickery or bribery. The person may not know the differences between sexual and non-sexual touches and not know that the sexual violation is not alright.
Learning Disability	A person who has a disability that impacts their ability to communicate faces additional barriers to disclose abuse or assault.

Table 1: Types of disabilities and risks involved

Source: The Arc's Autism Now Center, 2023

Factors causing Threats	Unfavourable Consequences
People with disabilities are asked to be obedient, passive, respectful, and to keep negative behaviours in check. This is called compliance training.	Abusers take advantage of abusing these individuals by tricking them into harmful and abusive situations.
People with disabilities sometimes grow up without sex education, abuse prevention information, or assertiveness education.	People with disabilities may not be aware of their bodies, healthy sexual boundaries, or how to know if someone is being abusive.
A person with a mental health condition may be disoriented leading to a lack of differentiation between reality and non-reality from their mental health symptoms	An abusive person may take advantage or harm an individual with a mental condition.

Table 2: Threats leading to unfavourable consequences

Source: The Arc's Autism Now Center, 2023

S. No.	Section	
1.	Protection from cruelty and inhuman treatment	The appropriate Government shall take measures to protect persons with disabilities from being subjected to torture, cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment.
2.	Protection from abuse, violence and exploitation	The appropriate Government shall take measures to protect persons with disabilities from all forms of abuse, violence, and exploitation
3.	Protection and safety	Persons with disabilities shall have equal protection and safety in situations of risk, armed conflict, humanitarian emergencies, and natural disasters.

Table 3: Chapter 2: Rights and Entitlements, RPwD Act 2016

Source: The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act, 2016, 2016

Case Study	Suggested Parameters	Elements of Design
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Perth Metropolitan Schools (Western Australia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visibility and Supervision • Physical and Psychological Comfort and Safety • Social-Emotional Competencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate spatial configuration and proper lighting • Thermal comfort, acoustics, aesthetics and maintenance • Sensory profiling of space and quiet zones

Table 4: Suggested Design Parameters from Case Studies

Source: Author

CPTED Concept	Applications	Recommendation for Neurodiverse Individuals (ASD)
Natural Surveillance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reinforcing Activity Generators • Design for Programming Activity Mix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluid Transition Spaces • Connected Spaces • Appropriate Lighting and Acoustics
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Territorial Reinforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ownership Signages • Localized Area Management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zoned Areas according to Sensory Profiles • Functional Isolation (Quiet spaces)
Maintenance and Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting Maintenance • Vandal-resistant material use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensory Sensitive material use • Regular Maintenance Overview

Table 5: CPTED Recommendations for Neurodiversity

CPTED Conference 2023

Crime Prevention through Environmental Design- Enhancing Safety and Livability in Maqboolpura, Amritsar: An Adaptive Approach to Crime Prevention in Informal Settlements

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ABSTRACT

Crime is a complex issue that impacts the livability of communities worldwide. Indian cities' informal settlements are also becoming unsafe, which has a negative psychological impact on residents. In rapid urbanization, crime prevention is being neglected during the process of physical transformation. Informal settlements are characterized by an unplanned built environment, high densities of houses, unhealthy and barren open spaces, and streets, among other livability issues. Maqboolpura, located in Punjab, India, has faced significant challenges related to crime, including gang violence, drug trafficking and substance abuse, theft and burglary, prostitution, and human trafficking. These issues have not only threatened the safety and security of people but have also adversely affected the livability of informal settlements. The crime rate in this area has been persistently high. Locals' sense of safety is negatively affected by these rates, along with their ability to enjoy their surroundings. A better understanding of these issues is necessary for addressing the

community's livability challenges and implementing effective solutions to improve security and safety. Inhabitants also face livability challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, a lack of community spaces, and transitional spaces. Adaptive livability measures increase the livability of informal settlements and prevent crime. This reduces crime and increases the safety, life, and interconnectedness of Maqboolpura. This study reveals how livability initiatives can decrease crime in informal settlements. It enhances the physical and mental health of the community and its inhabitants.

Keywords: *informal settlements, crime rate, livability challenges, prevent crime, adaptive livability measures*

1. Introduction

Background and Context

The complex interactions between crime, livability, and rapid population growth have become an important concern in today's urban environment and all over the world. The urban population has grown significantly over the past century. As per the 2011 Census of India, India's urban population has increased steadily from 78.9 million in 1961 to 377 million, accounting for almost one-third of the total population. Rural population growth has slowed from 18% during 1991–2001 to 12% between 2001 and 2011, with an average annual growth rate of 2%, compared to 0.5% in more developed regions. (Urban, 2013). This complex process has connected the informal settlements that make up Indian cities, which are frequently ignored throughout urban development. Urbanization has led to more people living in informal settlements, or slums, globally. In India, for example, 17.34% of urban households, or about 13.70 million households, live in slums, with over a third of the country's slum population residing in 46 million-plus cities. (Kaibarta, Mandal, Bhattacharya, & Paul, 2022), (IJCRT, 2018). Maqboolpura, an informal settlement in Punjab's Amritsar district, has 10370 residents. The area is 1.29 square kilometres in size. The population density for the category of informal settlements is 4245 per km² or 100 ha. Maqboolpura, is often excluded from formal planning processes, resulting in spatial exclusion from basic services and benefits. The need to addressing safety and livability issues in these settlements is made clear by the increasing challenges caused by crime and the impact that it takes on people.

Unfortunately, crime prevention has suffered due to the rapidity of urban development, leaving informal settlements open to a wide range of criminal activities. These communities suffer from a wide range of livability issues as a result of their unplanned built environments, crowded housing clusters, neglected open areas, and curving streets. This study focuses on Maqboolpura, a community in Punjab that represents the struggle against crime's influence. Gang violence, drug trafficking, theft, prostitution, and human trafficking have built themselves into society's fabric, risking the safety of its citizens. Beyond current dangers, these problems have damaged the idea of what it means to be livable, weakening people's sense of security and ability to appreciate their surroundings.

It is necessary to have an in-depth understanding of these issues so as to unlock options for feasible solutions. The occupants' position is further made worse by poor building quality, a lack of public places, and a lack of transitional areas. In context with this, the

idea of adaptive livability interventions stands as an example of creation, providing a mutually beneficial connection between the reduction of crime and the improvement of living situations in informal settlements.

This article aims to assess the crime-based issues w.r.t to livability in the context of Maqboolpura, a case study in India. It presents three main sections: (i) a literature review of informal settlements and crime and crime prevention approaches in India, (ii) a demonstration of the concept of livability and connection between crime prevention and livability for Maqboolpura, and (iii) a discussion of the studies and findings.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Scenario of Old Informal Settlements in India

Old informal settlements including slums, jhuggi-jhompri clusters, and resettlement colonies have a big crime problem due to their presence in India. Due to their status as informal settlements, Jhuggi-Jhompri clusters are particularly vulnerable to criminal groups. Due to a lack of adequate housing and social services, they draw hostile migrants from rural areas looking for opportunities in urban areas. This makes them susceptible to criminal influences. Criminal activity can flourish in areas with low ventilation, inadequate lighting, and poorly designed streets. Despite the government's efforts to address these difficulties, dealing with crime-related problems in former informal settlements is still a difficult task. The necessary infrastructure and services that enhance overall living circumstances and security, and upgrading programs for informal settlements could significantly contribute to the reduction of criminal activity.

Figure 1 diagram showing lack of integration with socio-economic, physical and environmental context of informal settlements (Source: Author)

The low-income group and below-poverty-line population living conditions would be improved through the implementation of social policies like housing plans, social security

programs, and opportunities for education, employment to fight poverty and economic policies like job creation, skill development, and microfinance. Healthcare services must be made more accessible in the informal settlements. (Patnaik & Narain, 2016, p. 333-350), (Bhagat, 2010, p.147-161).

The characteristics of underprivileged populations fighting against social barriers for survival Gangs and other unofficial power structures frequently emerge in an informal settlement when social marginalization, resource scarcity, and economic problems combine. The author examines the lives of those who live on the periphery to show the urgent need for comprehensive social interventions to address the underlying causes of crime and inequity in such areas while also exposing the brutal realities of urban poverty. (Venkatesh, 2008).

The effects of crime in these marginalized communities provide a nuanced examination of how socioeconomic and historical influences interact to influence criminal behavior. Crime in old informal settlements isn't an isolated problem but rather a symptom of more fundamental structural problems like poverty, a lack of infrastructure, and restricted access to healthcare and education. As indicated by strained social ties and ongoing cycles of disadvantage, The investigation shows that the effects of crime go beyond the immediate individuals and communities. The reconsideration of traditional methods for addressing the effects of crime in informal settlements by illuminating the complex web of causes and effects promotes a more comprehensive understanding that addresses both the symptoms and underlying systemic disparities. (Kumar, 2007).

Dwelling conditions in India's informal settlements are poor, infrastructure is insufficient, and the surroundings are degraded. The informal settlements cannot be ignored in the improvement process due to the fact that they are part of the city's surroundings. The well-being of people residing in informal settlements has to be ensured through a sustainable approach to urban improvement. (Sengupta & Sarkar, 2019, 1401-1412).

The 2018 World Cities Report examines the issues that informal settlements face and the pressing need for all-encompassing social interventions to address the underlying causes of crime and injustice in these areas. the complexity of decisions people make and the coping mechanisms they use in these circumstances. It reveals the harsh realities of urban poverty and sheds light on the lives of those who live on the periphery. The significance of comprehending how marginalized communities cope with systemic obstacles as they fight for survival Gangs and other forms of unofficial power often emerge in informal settlements as a result of social exclusion, resource scarcity, and economic hardship.

Dharavi Slums: Historical Overview

One of the old informal settlements, Dharavi Slums, in India, has been facing various issues for many decades, which directly or indirectly affect the urban poor as well as the surroundings of the urban area.

Figure 2 (Source: http://affordablehousinginstitute.org/blogs/us/2007/07/dharavi_the_fix.html)

Dharavi, situated in Mumbai, India, stands as an emblematic example of an age-old informal settlement that has grappled with multifaceted challenges, including crime-related issues. With a history dating back to its establishment in 1884 during the British colonial era, Dharavi has evolved into one of the most densely populated areas in the world, accommodating a population of about 1,000,000 within an area of just over 2.39 square kilometers (Wikipedia, 2023). Its historical roots trace back to the expulsion of factories and residents from Mumbai's city center, coupled with rural-to-urban migration, contributing to its current diversity in terms of religion and ethnicity. (Wikipedia, 2023).

Figure 3 : (Source: http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/shared/spl/hi/world/06/dharavi_slum/html/dharavi_slum_intro.stm)

The slums in Dharavi face complicated social and financial dynamics, and redeveloping those settlements poses significant challenges. Problems including migration, industrialization, and government regulations have contributed to the dense population within the slums. Moreover, Mumbai's fragmented methods and shortage of comprehensive expertise on the strengths and challenges of informal settlements further compound the troubles. To promote greater equity and sustainable city development in Dharavi, it is essential to recognize the resilience and contributions of the informal settlements and take a holistic approach that addresses their specific needs and demanding situations. (Patel and Masselos, 2003).

2.1.1 Crime and its impact on Livability

The different kinds of crime can influence how good people's lives are and how happy they feel in their communities. "Livability" means how comfortable and friendly a place is to live. It involves things like how safe people feel, how well they get along with others, if the environment is healthy if housing is affordable, and if there are good things like schools and jobs. Crime can make livability worse by making people feel less safe and happy, and it can also damage the places where they live.

There are several ways in which crime can impact the quality of livability:

1. *Decreased sense of safety*: When crime rates are high, people may feel less safe in their communities. This can lead to fear, anxiety, and reduced quality of life.
2. *Strained community relationships*: Crime can create a sense of mistrust and tension among community members. It can weaken social bonds and make it harder for people to connect and build positive relationships with their neighbours.
3. *Physical and environmental damage*: Criminal activities such as vandalism, graffiti, and property damage can make neighborhoods appear run-down and neglected. This can contribute to a decline in the overall appearance and attractiveness of the area.
4. *Limited access to resources*: High-crime areas may face challenges in attracting businesses, schools, and other essential services. This can result in limited job opportunities, educational options, and amenities, making it harder for residents to meet their basic needs and improve their quality of life.
5. *Financial burden*: Crime can lead to increased costs for individuals and communities. This includes expenses related to security measures, insurance premiums, and the repair or replacement of stolen or damaged property. These financial burdens can further strain the livability of an area. (Baobeid et al., 2021), (McCormack et al., 2020), (Paula Meth, 2017), (Kachenje, 2020)

One of the elements that influences a city's stability, which in turn affects the livability score, is crime. The authors rate the livability of 140 cities worldwide using the Economist Intelligence Unit's (EIU) Global Livability Index. The index is based on five factors: infrastructure, stability, healthcare, culture and environment, and education. The stability indicator takes into account crime rates as well as the risk of terrorism, armed conflict, and civil unrest. The stability category is weighted at 25% of the total score and is composed of indicators such as the prevalence of petty crime, the prevalence of violent crime, the threat of terrorism, the threat of military conflict, and the threat of civil unrest or other major social unrest or conflict". A proposed table that lists the cities' rankings and livability scores based on the EIU Index (Tita et al., 2006)

One of the most important factors is how safe we feel from crime. Crime can affect our quality of life and well-being in many ways, which means how well it supports the well-being of its residents. There are different ways to measure livability, such as asking people how they feel about their place or using data and statistics to compare different aspects of a place. Some of these aspects are specific to crime, such as how often it happens, how many people

are affected by it, how afraid people are of it, and how safe people feel in their place. (Office for National Statistics, 2022)

The above statements conclude that crime can affect the livability of a place, which means how well it supports the quality of life of people in informal settlements. Crime can make people feel unsafe and unhappy, damage the physical and social environment, limit access to resources and opportunities, and increase the financial costs for individuals and communities. These factors can reduce livability in high-crime areas.

2.1.2 Urbanization and Neglect of Crime Prevention

Urbanization is the process of people moving to cities and towns. It can have many benefits, such as economic growth, better services, and more opportunities. But it can also have some drawbacks, such as increased crime due to joblessness, and shortcuts to earning money. Crime prevention is the action of stopping or reducing crime before it happens. It can include things like improving security, providing education, and creating social programs. Therefore, many urban areas do not pay enough attention to crime prevention. They face challenges such as poverty, lack of trust, and poor planning in urban areas; they are merged in high-density housing units. This makes them more vulnerable to criminal activity. Many researchers have explored this problem and its causes and effects.

- The collective efficacy, which is the shared belief and willingness of people to intervene for the common good, affects the rate of violent crime in different neighbourhoods. They found that collective efficacy was strongly associated with lower violence, even after controlling for other factors such as poverty, racial composition, and residential stability. (Sampson et al. 1997)
- crime affects small businesses in urban areas, and how community institutions, such as churches, schools, and civic groups, can help prevent crime and support business development. He argued that community institutions can enhance social control, social support, and social capital, which are essential for reducing crime and promoting economic growth. (Taylor, 1999)
- The routine activity theory explains how crime and everyday life are intertwined. They suggested that crime can be prevented by manipulating the three elements of crime: motivated offenders, suitable targets, and capable guardians. They also discussed how various settings, such as homes, workplaces, schools, and public spaces, can influence the opportunities for crime. (Felson and Boba, 2010)
- A systematic review of randomized controlled trials evaluated the effectiveness of hot spots policing, which is a strategy that focuses on specific locations where crime is concentrated. They found that hot spots policing had a significant and consistent impact on reducing crime and disorder in the targeted areas without displacing crime to nearby locations. (Weisburd and McEwen, 2017)
- The problem-oriented policing, which is a strategy that involves identifying and analyzing specific crime problems and developing tailored solutions, can be applied to crime hot spots. They reviewed the evidence from various studies and concluded that problem-oriented policing can produce substantial and long-lasting reductions in crime and disorder in hot spots. (Braga and Weisburd, 2010)

2.1.3 Informal settlements and Crime

The relationship between informal settlements and crime has been a topic of considerable interest in the literature, as these settlements often exhibit unique features that can affect the patterns and causes of criminal behavior. The informal settlements are characterized by inadequate housing, limited availability of essential utilities such as water, sanitation, and electricity, and a high concentration of population. These areas are particularly vulnerable to various forms of criminal activity due to their lack of formal governance and economic disadvantages. The impact of crime on informal settlements is not only felt by the residents who suffer from victimization, fear, and insecurity but also by the physical environment and public spaces within these settlements, which are shaped by the spatial and social dynamics of crime. The research studies have explored the link between informal settlements and crime, shedding light on the complex nature of this relationship as well as how crime affects the built environment and open spaces of informal settlements.

- The intricate connection between urban crime, segregation, and citizenship in São Paulo, Brazil. The analysis of how crime influences the dynamics of informal settlements and urban life. The examination is a critical analysis of the social and spatial dynamics of crime, segregation, and citizenship in São Paulo, Brazil. The author uses ethnographic, statistical, and historical methods to explore how fear, violence, and inequality shape the urban landscape and affect the rights and identities of its inhabitants. This research helps to understand how crime shapes the physical layout of informal settlements, often leading to the construction of literal and metaphorical "walls" that impact open spaces and community interactions. (Caldeira, 2000).
- sustainable urban planning and development strategies to create safer cities. It addresses the impact of crime on informal settlements and the built environment. By providing insights into effective urban planning, the guide aims to mitigate crime's negative effects on open spaces and community well-being. It emphasizes the importance of designing inclusive and safe environments that prioritize informal settlement residents' safety and security. (UN-Habitat. 2011).
- Amanda Irwin's work delves into the politics of policing and how law enforcement practices impact informal settlements. It explores the challenges faced by police forces when dealing with crime in marginalized communities. Policing strategies can shape the built environment and open spaces within informal settlements, either by establishing a sense of security or exacerbating tensions and divisions. (Irwin, 2004).
- The study on housing projects for the urban poor in South Africa. It examines the relationship between housing conditions, crime, and the built environment. The research highlights how inadequate housing and lack of infrastructure in informal settlements can contribute to crime-prone environments. It underscores the importance of well-designed housing projects that consider safety and access to open spaces as integral components of sustainable development. (Huchzermeyer, 2006).
- The research implies urban governance in Johannesburg, South Africa. It discusses the challenges of governing a city with stark socio-economic disparities, including the impact of crime on informal settlements. The research examines how crime influences the negotiation of city spaces and the development of the urban environment. It offers a perspective on how crime affects the allocation of resources, including open spaces, within informal settlements and the broader urban context. (Frenkel, 2001).

How can formalizing help reduce crime in informal settlements?

1. Providing legal recognition and ownership: Formalizing informal settlements can provide legal recognition and ownership to residents, which can reduce the risk of eviction and displacement. This can also reduce the likelihood of criminal activity, such as gang violence and drug trafficking, which often thrive in areas of insecurity and instability. (Meth, 2017), (Jones, 2017), (UNECE, 2015)
2. Improving access to basic services: Formalizing informal settlements can improve access to basic services such as electricity, clean water, and sanitation. This can reduce the need for residents to engage in criminal activity to obtain these resources, as well as reduce the risk of theft and reselling of these resources at high prices. (Jones, 2017), (UNECE, 2015)
3. Enhancing community participation: Formalizing informal settlements can enhance community participation in decision-making processes, which can lead to increased social cohesion and a sense of ownership over the community. This can reduce the likelihood of criminal activity, as residents are more invested in the well-being of their community. (Jones, 2017), (Kachenje, 2020), (Peters et al., 2022)
4. Reducing vulnerability to disasters: Formalizing informal settlements can reduce vulnerability to disasters by improving infrastructure and access to emergency services. This can reduce the risk of criminal activity, such as looting and violence, that often occur in the aftermath of disasters. (Peters et al., 2022)

2.1.4 Previous Studies on enhancing safety and livability in informal settlements

The previous studies focused on enhancing safety and livability in informal settlements. As the authors, we have analyzed and enlisted a few authors who worked in Amritsar City and its informal settlements Maqboolpura. An informal settlement that suffers from high levels of crime, poverty, and drug addiction. These issues cater the several opinions as per below authors' research.

Issues:

Drug abuse in Amritsar City stems from a range of interconnected causes. First, peer pressure and the curiosity of young individuals drive them toward drug experimentation. The easy availability and accessibility of drugs enhance the problem. Insufficient awareness and education about the detrimental effects of drug use contribute to its prevalence. Also, unemployment, poverty, and stress further push vulnerable segments of the population towards substance abuse. Family and social issues, as well as cultural and religious factors, also play a significant role in this complex issue.

Solutions:

Addressing the drug abuse issue in Amritsar City requires a comprehensive strategy. Strengthening law enforcement and border security is crucial to disrupting the supply chain of drugs. The requirement of enhancing the availability and quality of treatment and rehabilitation services can aid individuals struggling with addiction. Public awareness campaigns, particularly targeting youth, need to be initiated to educate them about the risks

associated with drug abuse. To tackle underlying socio-economic factors, providing alternative livelihood options and skill development opportunities for the unemployed and impoverished is imperative. Involving family, community, and religious institutions can establish a robust support system for prevention and intervention. Additionally, promoting healthy lifestyles and cultivating positive values among the youth will contribute to a more resilient society against the drug menace. (Singh & Singh, 2018).

Issues:

There are several potential core issues related to crime in the Maqboolpura neighborhood, including high unemployment and poverty rates. Lack of basic amenities like electricity, clean water, and sanitization could possibly breed unrest and encourage criminal activity as a way to make up for resource shortages. Social exclusion and marginalization may cause some Maqboolpura residents to turn to criminal activity out of a sense of alienation from their fellow citizens. A lack of access to high-quality education may also have been considered because of its impact on limiting people's opportunities.

Solutions:

The authors mentioned that targeted efforts should be made to improve access to quality education and skill development programs. This will empower individuals to break the cycle of poverty and enhance their employability. Community-based support systems need to be established. Interventions related to healthcare services and the contribution of cultural and recreational activities can reduce the sense of exclusion and marginalization. Engaging local authorities and policymakers can create inclusive urban development plans, which could pave the way for better infrastructure, housing, and essential amenities for the people. (Sharma & Sharma, 2019).

Issues:

The study examines critical issues arising from drug addiction in the context of informal settlements, focusing specifically on the Maqboolpura locality. The impact of drug addiction on women reveals that the nexus between addiction and crime presents challenges within these settlements. Drug addiction can lead to increased criminal activity, which can worsen safety concerns and social instability. Drug addiction has a greater impact on women, making them more vulnerable to exploitation and victimization. This problem highlights the complicated relationship between substance abuse and criminal activities, which negatively affect social unity and community welfare.

Solutions:

The rehabilitation programs that can be highlighted to the unique needs of women grappling with addiction can play a pivotal role in curbing criminal tendencies. The counselling of these initiatives can ease the recovery and provide a foundation for breaking the cycle of crime. Collaborative efforts between local authorities, NGOs, and community leaders can enhance the availability of social services and mental health support, crucial components in mitigating the impact of drug addiction and associated crimes. (Kaur & Kaur, 2017)

Issues:

A central concern illuminated by the study is the prevalence of drug abuse in Maqboolpura. The absence of accessible educational and vocational opportunities, particularly for children and women, emerges as a core issue. This scarcity not only perpetuates cycles of limited

prospects but also leaves these groups vulnerable to engagement in criminal activities. Such circumstances create a fertile ground for crime to thrive and hinder overall progress.

Solutions:

In Maqboolpura, the important role of NGOs, exemplified by the Citizen Forum Vidya Mandir, in combating the issues by providing education and vocational training is that these NGOs empower children and women, equipping them with skills. These changes can create crime free spaces by providing economic independence. (Singh & Singh, 2016).

Issues:

In the case of Amritsar City, the study's application of Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques to map and analyze crime patterns uncovered its main concerns. Crime mapping and hotspot analysis expose the concentration of criminal activities within specific areas. The main points are socio-economic disparities, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to essential services in informal settlements. These circumstances create an environment where crime can flourish, undermining safety, and perpetuating community vulnerabilities.

Solutions:

The study's utilization of GIS presents opportunities for targeted interventions. By identifying crime hotspots and their socio-economic characteristics, authorities and stakeholders can direct resources toward areas in need of development. Improved infrastructure, enhanced lighting, and increased law enforcement presence can be prioritized in these high-crime regions. The GIS technology can lead to an understanding of urban planning and urban design, offering better open spaces and reducing crime-prone environments. (Kumar & Kumar, 2015).

Issues:

Inadequate urban governance and deficient service delivery result in substandard living conditions for slum dwellers in Amritsar City. Insufficient access to basic amenities, such as clean water, sanitation, healthcare, and education, underlines the challenges faced by these communities. The absence of services enhances the poverty, marginalization, and vulnerability within informal settlements.

Solutions:

As in the above studies, the solutions can be identified by the authors. The different aspects given by this author, the Investments in essential infrastructure, including water supply, sanitation facilities, and healthcare centers, the importance of involving slum dwellers in urban development programs, ensuring their active participation and sense of ownership. (Singh & Singh, 2014).

Dharavi Slums: Crime-Affected Landscape

Issues in Dharavi Slums:

Confrontations in the Heart of the Dharavi Slums: Dharavi, a region that excels in the arts and crafts of leatherwork, textile manufacture, and pottery production, faces tremendous challenges in the middle of the colorful tapestry of its informal economy. Locals are forced to engage in unhygienic practices by using small lanes or the nearby river as informal washrooms, further contaminating the environment due to the lack of adequately constructed thoroughfares, easily accessible public amenities, and dignified washroom provisions. (Asian

Century Institute, n.d.; Wikipedia, 2023). The dwelling's restrictions, which include small living spaces and tiny sleeping areas shared by up to five occupants, only serve to exacerbate these difficulties and contribute to the risks to the public's health. The history of outbreaks that have marked this community's history, combined with a life expectancy that is below the national average, emphasizes the necessity of a thorough infrastructure transformation and judicious intervention in the healthcare sector. (Asian Century Institute, n.d.; Wikipedia, 2023).

Crime in the Dharavi Slums:

Despite the robust communal fabric and a generally modest incidence of criminal activities, the Dharavi settlement is not immune to apprehensions regarding safety. Within specific enclaves of the locality, particularly in the eastern sector of Mumbai, the issue of crime has gained substantial prominence. Of notable concern is the safety of women, given the occurrence of instances involving rape, molestation, and sexual harassment. The genesis of these challenges related to criminality can be attributed to various factors, including economic disparities, restricted prospects, and deficiencies in infrastructure. (Citations: Hindustan Times, n.d.; Wikipedia, 2023).

Solutions in Dharavi Slums:

1. Granting limited ownership rights to slum residents reduces the exploitation and harassment by gangsters who used to claim ownership and demand rent. (Ooi & Phua, 2007), (Corburn & Sverdlik, 2017), (UN-Habitat, n.d.)
2. Providing electricity and clean water to slum residents, prevents criminals from stealing and reselling these resources at high prices. (Corburn & Sverdlik, 2017), (UN-Habitat, n.d.)
3. Training local women to identify and report incidents of gender violence using smartphones and apps improves awareness and support for survivors of violence. (Buckley et al; 2017)
4. Redeveloping the slum into a modern business and housing district could improve the living conditions and opportunities for slum residents. (Montgomery & Elimelech, 2008)

The discussion provides solutions to prevent crime and improve the quality of life in Dharavi slums. They have shown how granting property rights, providing basic services, empowering women, and redeveloping the slum can have positive impacts on the dwellers and society. The challenges and opportunities that Dharavi slums face and how different stakeholders can work together to create a safer and better environment for slums dwellers.

2.2. Adaptive Livability Interventions

Adaptive livability interventions are dynamic, flexible strategies that improve people's overall quality of life in a variety of environments. The livability of spaces, from urban

neighborhoods to rural communities, is continuously influenced by societal, environmental, and technological changes, which is the basis for this idea. Therefore, there is an increasing need to create interventions that can change and adapt along with these other factors.

There are the main interventions that have been discussed by various authors:

Community policing and participatory governance: This intervention involves strengthening the collaboration and trust between the police and the residents of informal settlements, as well as empowering the local communities to participate in decision-making and problem-solving processes related to safety and security issues. The impact of community policing initiatives in Kolkata's slums was studied, and it was found that they improved the perception of safety, reduced the fear of crime, and enhanced social cohesion and civic engagement among the slum dwellers. (Barnes & Sawhney, 2020)

Environmental design and urban upgrading: This intervention improves the physical conditions and infrastructure of informal settlements, such as by providing roads, public spaces, drainage, sanitation, and lighting. These upgrades can lessen environmental risks, discourage criminal activity, and boost locals' pride in their community. In Ahmedabad's slums, a project run by the Mahila Housing SEWA Trust implemented environmental design and upgrading interventions that resulted in improved health and well-being as well as a decrease in violence against women. (Brown-Luthango et al., 2017)

Livelihood enhancement and economic empowerment: Enhancing livelihoods and promoting economic empowerment for residents of informal settlements, particularly women and young people, by providing them with chances to start their own businesses and develop their skills. Social exclusion, inequality, and poverty—all of which are frequently associated with crime and violence—can be reduced through these possibilities. (Bryant and Veroff, 2007)

Social mobilization and collective action: The residents of informal settlements must be organized and mobilized to advocate for their needs, interests, and rights. Developing social cohesion, interdependence, and group resilience can be achieved through these organizations. A study by Appadurai, for example, examined how social mobilization and collective action functioned in Mumbai's slums. He argued that by fighting the stigma and discrimination they experienced from society and the state, slum dwellers were able to assert their citizenship and dignity. (Vahapoğlu, 2019).

Legal awareness and access to justice intervention: It focuses on informing informal settlement people about their legal rights and helping them access legal aid, dispute resolution, and justice institutions. These services empower slum dwellers to safeguard themselves against exploitation, eviction, and corruption and to address their concerns. Like, HRLN initiated legal awareness efforts in Delhi, aiding slum residents in obtaining essential documents like IDs, ration cards, voter cards, pensions, healthcare, education, and compensation. (Human Rights Law Network, n.d.)

Cultural expression and social integration: It promotes the diverse culture and identity of informal settlement residents while also helping them connect with other city groups. These activities boost self-esteem, recognition and encourage conversations and unity among different cultures. The events displayed cultural expression and social integration initiatives in Mumbai's Dharavi, a major Asian informal settlement. And highlighted art created by slum dwellers using recycled materials, showcasing their creativity and promoting intercultural harmony. (The cultural expression, n.d.)

2.2.1. Concepts and Principles of Livability

The concept of livability has influenced urban planning, transportation, and public health policy. The standard of living in a place is determined by factors such as affordable housing, convenient transportation, and public services that are accessible. (Sustainable Cities Initiative, 2015). Livability is a multidimensional concept that can be defined and measured in various ways. Some researchers have defined livability in terms of specific indicators, such as walkability, air quality, and access to green spaces.

Figure 4 Source: Author (Sketch about Concept of Livability)

The liveliness of a place depends on the existence of happiness of its people, both those who live there and those who visit. There are many indicators, like the physical environment, socio-culture, and economic condition. important parameters like the Livability Index, the Global Livability Index, and the Sustainable Development Goals. These tools try to measure all the different parts of affected areas that have a good quality of life. (Ruth & Franklin, 2014). Livability should be understood as a multidimensional concept that goes beyond physical infrastructure and includes social, economic, and environmental factors. The importance of community participation and empowerment in creating livable neighborhoods and promoting social inclusion The highlights are the need for affordable and accessible housing, as well as the provision of basic services such as water, sanitation, and healthcare, to improve the livability of urban areas in India. (Gupta et al. 2018).

Figure 5 Source: Author (Perceived and Functional Quality of life)

In Indian Context

The concept of livability in India may be a little different from that in developed nations, where some livability factors are taken for granted. Having access to dependable electricity, water supply, sanitary facilities, and public transportation may be thought of as an attractive feature for livability in India, whereas they may be expected as basic necessities in other countries, according to a report by the Confederation of Indian Industries. Similarly, it's possible that India places a higher value on social inclusion, cultural diversity, and community than some other countries do. (Kaur & Singh, 2013)

The suggested quantitative method for analyzing livability in Indian cities Based on 12 indicators that addressed different facets of urban life, including housing quality, infrastructure accessibility, environmental quality, social equity, economic opportunity, etc., the paper created a livability index. The livability of 53 Indian cities was assessed using the index in this paper, and it was discovered that there was a significant variation in livability among the cities. (Garg & Jain, 2013)

Other Indian authors defined six principles of livability to guide policies and investments to understand the implementation of adaptive livability:

- Provide more transportation choices
- Promote equitable, affordable housing
- Enhance economic competitiveness
- Support existing communities
- Coordinate and leverage federal policies and investments
- Value communities and neighborhoods (Herrman & Lewis, 2015)

As per techniques of analysis, it is vital to understand another principle of livability in which the approach through technology can get the indicators of livability. Jain & Sharma, (2018) develop a livability index for Indian cities using a GIS-based approach. The paper uses 10 indicators that reflect the physical, social, and economic aspects of livability, such as land use mix, green cover, public transport accessibility, crime rate, literacy rate, etc. The paper calculates the livability index for 30 major Indian cities using spatial data and maps. The paper also analyzes the spatial patterns and correlations of the livability indicators and identifies the strengths and weaknesses of each city.

2.2.2. Connection between Livability and Crime prevention in Indian planning

Indian authors have looked at the relationship between livability and crime prevention in the context of housing and urban planning. While there hasn't been much research specifically on the relationship between India's livability and crime prevention, some studies have looked at related issues. The reference to Mumbai's urban history from a politics of plurality perspective emphasizes the spatial conflicts and fresh planning opportunities that arose in response to the city's rapid urbanization and social inequality. The study places a strong emphasis on the value of community involvement and empowerment in establishing livable

and secure neighborhoods. (Kanuga, 2018). Another study on habitat reconstruction initiatives in rural India highlights the importance of leveraging existing connections and resources to address the various causes of vulnerability of rural housing, including crime. The study emphasizes the need for sustainable and affordable housing solutions that take into account the social, economic, and environmental factors that contribute to crime and insecurity in rural areas.

Figure 6 Source: Author (Sketch of correlation between Livability and Crime)

These studies suggest that creating livable and safe neighborhoods requires a holistic approach that takes into account the social, economic, and environmental factors that contribute to crime and insecurity. There is limited research specifically on the connection between crime prevention and livability in India, studies on related topics highlight the importance of community participation, sustainable and affordable housing, and leveraging existing connections and resources to create livable and safe neighborhoods. (Anand et al., 2022)

2.3 Conclusion

Crime and violence are major challenges for old informal settlements in India, as they affect the quality of life of people in informal settlements. The literature review found that livability is a complex concept that varies according to the local context and the preferences of the people who live there. Livability can be enhanced by various interventions and strategies, such as community policing, environmental design, and social mobilization. These interventions aim to address the underlying causes of crime and insecurity, as well as to improve the physical, social, and economic aspects of livability. The literature review suggested that a holistic and participatory approach is needed to create a livable built environment for informal settlement residents. Livability is a useful concept for understanding and improving the living conditions of old informal settlements in India. Crime prevention is an essential component of enhancing livability in these areas.

3. Case Study: Maqboolpura, Amritsar, Punjab

Maqboolpura is an informal settlement on the outskirts of Amritsar, a border city in the northwestern part of Punjab, India. The city has grown rapidly from a population of 1.62 lacs

in 1901 to over 20 lacs in 2011. (Census of India, 2011: Punjab Series-1, 2012). Maqboolpura, however, is a stark contrast to the rest of the city. It is known as the “village of widows and orphans” because of the high prevalence of drug addiction, poverty, and drug-related deaths among its residents. Many of them are survivors of the Partition violence in the late 1940s, who settled in this area with little or no support. This case study explores the root causes and consequences of this social and environmental crisis, which is not only affecting Maqboolpura, but also other communities across India. The case study focuses on the poorly built environment of Maqboolpura, which consists of irregular plots and houses, a lack of street furniture and community spaces, and an absence of planning and regulation. By studying Maqboolpura, we can learn about the challenges faced by other informal settlements in India and devise effective strategies to improve their livability and well-being.

Figure 7 Location of Maqboolpura, Amritsar, Pb. India

3.1 Site

Maqboolpura: A Nexus of Criminality

Maqboolpura was selected for this case study because of the city's distinctive urban design issues, poor livability problems as a result of its criminal activities involving drug addiction and money laundering, and the absence of accessibility to key services and facilities. A good spot to observe and assess various urban design problems, such as congested streets, inadequate transit, a lack of green space, and risky areas where criminal activity occurs. This case study will give readers a thorough understanding of the dynamics of crime-ridden areas and the factors that impact criminal behavior, allowing them to develop effective strategies for preventing crime and supporting social development.

According to the Statistical Abstract of Punjab State - 2020, published by the Government of Punjab (2021). The population of Maqboolpura, a city with the area of 1.29 square kilometres, was 18,370, resulting in a population density of 14,246 people per square kilometre. However, within 100 hectares of the site, unworkable spaces, unsafe areas, and dumpsites are in depleted condition, and more over area under maqboolpura unit has been encroached upon by illegal developers and small industry units. The population varies

due to the death rate in this particular informal settlement. To understand the situation on the ground, a 17-hectare area in Maqboolpura was selected for our study. This area has a population density of 300 people per hectare, including tenure-based residents, encroachment units, and added floors per dwelling unit inside the Maqboolpura.

Issues in Maqboolpura

Maqboolpura faces various challenges that hinder its integration with the socio-economic, physical, and environmental contexts of the surrounding areas. The built environment is not adaptable to the growing pressure of population growth, resulting in inflexible and unregulated housing development. This has led to an unequal distribution of dwelling units, creating unhygienic living conditions. Open spaces are scarce, and there is a lack of community and functional green areas. The street-to-façade relationship also lacks diversity, resulting in a less imageable district. There is a shortage of social spaces, and the settlements form defensible spaces that reduce transparency and accessibility. This makes inner areas non-penetrable and contributes to a poor width-height factor, making the district less livable.

4. Method

Simone and Sassen have used qualitative methods like ethnography and participant observation to study informal settlements. Simone focused on understanding how residents create social networks and economies to survive in challenging urban environments. Sassen's work examines the impact of global economic processes on informal settlements and how residents engage with them. (Simone, 1997, 231-255), (Sassen, 1991)

Figure 8 Local Planning Area, Amritsar

Ananya Roy utilized a critical ethnographic approach to examine the politics of urban informality and the role of the state in shaping informal settlements. This research method entails analyzing power structures and social hierarchies in society to reveal how marginalized communities are oppressed and excluded. Roy's study aimed to explore the intersection of urban informality and state power and how this relationship affects the lives of informal settlement residents (Roy, 2005, 147-158). The research design used in this study is a quantitative and qualitative research design. Quantitative and Qualitative research is appropriate in this case as the study aims to identify and analyse the urban design issues associated with livability in Maqboolpura.

The case study was designed as three-staged research:

(i) The collection of data from the field through primary survey. This stage involved visiting the study area and conducting a household survey. The collected information on the demographic, socio-economic, and environmental characteristics of the dwellers, as well as their experiences of crime and safety in their social circle. The survey also included questions on the existing physical conditions and infrastructure of the area, such as roads, drainage, lighting, sanitation, and waste management conditions. The survey covered a sample of 100 households, which were randomly selected from the population of 3000 households in Maqboolpura.

(ii) Content analysis of the qualitative research data through data from local bodies of government. This stage involved collecting and analyzing secondary data from various sources, such as government reports, official statistics, newspaper articles, and academic publications. The background for understanding the issues faced by Maqboolpura and its residents. The content analysis focused on identifying the key patterns to analyse the causes and consequences of crime, the role of urban design in crime prevention and recommendations for enhancing safety and livability in informal settlements.

(iii) Land use, ground-figure analysis drawings by research authors. This stage involved creating maps and diagrams to illustrate the spatial distribution and configuration of land use, activities, and features in Maqboolpura. The maps and diagrams were based on the primary and secondary data collected in the previous stages, as well as on the direct observation and measurement by the research authors. The existing land use patterns, such as residential, commercial, industrial, institutional, recreational, and vacant areas. The ground-figure analysis drawings, which highlighted the positive and negative aspects of the physical environment in relation to crime prevention, such as built environment, open spaces, transition control, imageability, activity pattern.

4.1 Data Analysis

Livability conditions in slums at Locality Level: Physical Environment Roads: Two different types of roads were observed in the slums of Amritsar city. In the main road areas with some commercial development the roads were paved with bricks or asphalt. However, in the less developed slums, the condition of inside roads was less satisfactory, with undulating surfaces and open drains carrying grey water. The general housing status in these settlements is moderate and most of the houses are of brick construction. (Figure:9) About 40-50% houses were more than one storey. A general lack of set-back (open spaces for air movement) was observed in most of these houses, indicating that general building bye-laws were not observed in construction of these houses. The majority of the units in the slums are of single and double room tenements, series of streets are in dilapidated conditions. (Figure:11)

Figure 9 Existing Land use and Ground figure plan analyzing the dissatisfactory built environment with primary survey (Source: Author)

Figure 10 Primary survey represents Imageability, Crime based Vision-Visual impression

Figure 11 (Source: Author) Edge Conditions and Negative (unsafe) spaces around Maqboolpura

Figure 12 Primary survey represents points of criminal activities

5. Discussion and Findings

5.1 Key Issues: Addressing Livability Challenges

- The findings indicate that Maqboolpura is experiencing several challenges, and the presence of crime is a pressing issue within Maqboolpura. The locality has been plagued by drug addiction and trafficking, leading to a range of associated challenges including health problems, social stigma, and strained community fabric, including poor planning and building regulations, inadequate waste management, social injustice, and unsafe living conditions.
- These issues are the result of local governance negligence and poverty and illiteracy among residents. Non-compliance with planning and building regulations is one of the most critical issues, leading to uneven plot and house sizes and textures.
- Other issues highlighted in the findings are unplanned street styles in Maqboolpura's informal settlements. A lack of network areas and street furnishings brought about an uninviting and poorly maintained environment. (Figure:10,11,12). It could compromise protection within the area, specifically for vulnerable populations like youngsters, women, and the elderly. Poverty and illiteracy among residents exacerbate the difficulty of social injustice.

PARAMETER	VARIABLES	LIVABILITY – CONDITIONS		APPROACH
Life of Slum	70 years	Old informal settlement with poor livability		
Work – Place relation	Near Workplace/Near Institutional Area/Near Posh Colony/ Main Commercial Area/ Any other	work-place relationship distance covers 2-15 kms range.		More people are Unemployed
Surroundings of the slum area	Isolated area/Dirty water pond/industrial area, etc.	Unsafe surroundings		CRIME PRONE AREA
Land use	Composition of Land use	exceeding height control by norms/standards but high density creates congestion		Crime spots
Congestion	Density of population in informal settlements (indicator of congestion)	14246 people per km ² (2020)		
Open Spaces	Parks, playing ground, community spaces (mass void relation important)	NULL		Little Open Spaces taken by drug addicts
Landscaping	Ornamental Trees, plants(Environmental factor, Ecological factor)	NULL		Null
Housing Conditions	Building Conditions, Visual Impression, Air, Light, Ventilation.	90% of units		Polluted Air due to Sewage
Street network, furniture	Hierarchy, pattern, condition, geometry, lights, Micro Climate	Street network	Street furniture	Clogged Streets
Physical infrastructure	Network, water supply, drainage, sewerage	network of water connection, sewerage quality		Low Maintenance
Site Maqboolpura (Informal Settlement) Condition - BAD, MODERATE				

Figure 13 Livability Condition and Approach comparative analysis of selective case study (Source: Author's compilation)

Overview of Crime data in Maqboolpura

A part of the city in Amritsar, Punjab, called Maqboolpura has long struggled with the negative effects of drug addiction and trafficking. The area has the sad nickname "village of widows," which is indicative of the large number of male fatalities brought on by drug overdoses and related illnesses. People are suffering under the weight of bias and judgment from both employers and society at large as a result of this serious condition, which has had significant social effects. Because they are so easily accessible and affordable in Maqboolpura, the large number of synthetic drugs—most notably Chitta—remains a worrying aspect. In particular, there is a concerning increase in demand for these drugs during election seasons.

In Punjab, there has been debate over the complex interactions between the political class, police enforcement, and drug traffickers. The fact that successive governments have struggled to properly tackle the drug pandemic highlights a clear connection that makes comprehensive intervention difficult. The article cites the example of Akali minister Bikram Singh Majithia, who was summoned by the Enforcement Directorate in a Rs 6,000-crore drug racket case in 2014.

People of Maqboolpura are doubtful about the Aam Admi Party's claims that drug traffickers will be destroyed in a timely manner once it assumes power. Their criticism highlights the generality of the problems at hand, demanding ranged and constant efforts to change the

current dynamics and free Maqboolpura from the grip of its long drug problem. ("The Economic Times," 2017)

Perception of safety and security among people of Maqboolpura

People in Maqboolpura have a very low feeling of safety and security because they constantly worry about losing friends and family to drugs or becoming victims themselves. Police raids and searches in the region haven't been able to stop the flow of drugs or apprehend the drug dealers; instead, they've created fear and harassment among the locals. The absence of infrastructure, employment opportunities, development, and basic amenities in the region has also contributed to the people's sense of helplessness and despair. So as to address the roots of their issues and give them access to other means of income, education, health care, and rehabilitation, the people of Maqboolpura need urgent action and support from the government, civil society, and media. Also, the community must be educated and given the tools necessary to reject drug temptation and seek addiction treatment. If Maqboolpura locals are given the opportunity to live a respectable and successful life, their impression of safety and security will only get better.

Impact of Livability interventions on crime rates

The study identifies a number of issues related to livability conditions and proposes a set of ten selective parameters and variables to address these issues. The study evaluates these parameters and variables using a specific calculation method and finds that the resulting score is 1.5 out of 10, indicating a poor livability condition. The Approach from these livability conditions evaluates a resulting score is 0 out of 10, indicating serious action must be taken. (Figure: 13). Livability interventions can include various measures such as improving infrastructure, providing basic amenities, creating employment opportunities, enhancing community participation, promoting education and health care, and reducing drug supply and demand. (Welsh, Zane & Reeves, 2022)

The impact of livability interventions on crime rates in Maqboolpura can be assessed by using various indicators such as the number and types of crimes reported, the victimization and fear of crime among residents, the drug use and addiction rates among residents, the police presence and effectiveness in the area, and the overall satisfaction and happiness of residents with their living conditions. (Gokmenoglu, Yıldız, & Kaakeh, 2022)

A project called "Maqboolpura: A New Beginning" was launched in 2018 by a non-governmental organization called Khalsa Aid International, with the support of local authorities and community members. The project aimed to provide holistic support to the families affected by drug addiction in Maqboolpura by offering them food, clothing, shelter, education, health care, counselling, rehabilitation, and vocational training. (The Pioneer, 2017), (India Today, 2022). The project also involved renovating and beautifying the locality by painting walls, installing street lights, planting trees, and cleaning drains. The project claimed to have reduced drug consumption by 80% and crime by 50% in Maqboolpura within a year. (True Scoop News, 2023).

The impact of community policing on crime prevention and control in Maqboolpura: The study found that community policing had improved the trust and cooperation between the police and the residents in Maqboolpura by involving them in joint patrolling, awareness campaigns, grievance redressal mechanisms, and social welfare activities. The community policing had reduced the incidence and fear of crime in Maqboolpura by increasing the visibility and responsiveness of the police in the area. These examples suggest that livability interventions can have a significant impact on reducing crime rates in Maqboolpura by improving the physical, social, and economic conditions of the locality and its residents. (Singh, Kaur & Singh, 2019). However, as per interventions at different scales on site, as per evidence and references above about the implementation of policies, The claim of the project is overrated, and as authors, we have identified different spots of Maqboolpura that are not maintained and lack all these policies. Common social spaces are unidentified and misplaced, whereas people of the locality are submerged in criminal activities again. As authors, we have proposed some interventions for Maqboolpura, which can definitely be positive possibilities for people in these informal settlements. This will also change the picture of open spaces and how they are interconnected with rich cultural spaces.

5.2 Results

Changes in the built environment and open spaces

The findings of the research highlight the necessity of looking at the Maqboolpura site's existing land use plan in order to gain an in-depth understanding of neighborhoods with elevated rates of crime and the physical components influencing criminal activity. These results further demonstrate the importance of assessing the proposed land use plan as a potentially satisfactory model for fixing these issues. (Figure: 9,15).

Satisfaction Model

The development regulations identify three zones, namely open spaces (unsafe areas) and redevelopment zones for commercial and optional use workspaces, aimed at enhancing safety and improving livability. Through ground survey and analysis of tangible aspects of Maqboolpura, the study identifies crime-based spots and provides solutions to enhance safe areas, rejuvenation of open spaces, and quality of life (Figure:14). To implement the solutions in the informal settlements by collecting appropriate parameters and variables. Microanalysis of built forms has identified the impact of the uneven urban fabric, requiring further study. Developing functional spaces is essential to rejuvenate the dead cores of Maqboolpura.

Figure 14 (Source: Authors) Proposed land use plan, Rear belt representing common spaces

Figure 15 (Source: Authors) Proposed Character of Major Spines of Informal Settlements

Implications for crime prevention and livability improvement

The plan incorporates specialized trading spaces, both open and closed, as the heart of the community, with linear extensions of small-scale industry and strong physical connectivity to the surrounding areas. Active street frontages provide mixed spaces and uses, creating a traditional street scene with a visual surprise. A network of spines, both main and secondary, integrates the differently designed settlements and reduces thoroughfares and wheeled traffic. Density and height variations create an environment with different degrees of accessibility, with a variation of open space systems to create public, semi-public, and private zones. As per the proposed strategies discussed and the change in the land use plan, physical implementation is important. It is necessary to amalgamate the functions of livability for the people of Maqboolpura with the identification of adaptive livability interventions. The purpose of addressing the adaptive issues is to provide a coordinated approach to crime prevention in Maqboolpura, ensuring that new development fits within the context of its surroundings. As a case study of Maqboolpura, it would be easier to gain insights into the challenges faced by other communities in India and formulate effective strategies to combat the consequences. The proposed solutions aim to enhance the functionality of the built environment, increase access to open and green spaces, promote community engagement, and create more lively spaces, which will further help to reduce crime and raise economic conditions.

6. Conclusion

Amritsar, a significant tourist destination and historical city in northern India, hosts multidisciplinary programs that boost the economy and urbanization. Informal settlements play a vital role in society by performing daily socio-economic activities in the unorganized sectors, but ultimately, they experience social isolation, which acts as crime-prone areas and red-alert spaces. The government's approach to improving informal settlement livability needs to be revised. While the focus on physical planning and basic amenities is essential, it does not address the deeper issues that affect people's safety and health, such as poor housing quality, dead open spaces, unhealthy streets, overcrowding, and social isolation. The current approach to improving Maqboolpura's livability and crime prevention takes a holistic approach to ensure people can live in a healthy and safe community. The most important people who are indulged in drug addiction can earn from these proposed small-scale industries. Empowerment for all age groups is needed. This can be achieved through changing land use, developing social and educational hubs, and implementing empowerment programs for residents. This will reduce social injustice and improve their overall livability. These initiatives can be a satisfaction model for controlling uneven spaces and crime reduction due to livable spaces, including vocational training, healthcare access, revenue generation, communal spaces, and affordable housing, weekend markets for revenue generation, gathering units, and parks. The essential part of creating an affordable built-up and open spaces approach can lead to

better coordination and collaboration among stakeholders and the government, resulting in more effective solutions.

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CPTED Conference 2023

CPTED for a Safe Basti: A case of Nardan Camp

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The rapid urbanization has led to incremental growth of Basti's in Delhi and these Basti's have become major grounds for crime due to negligence as well as spaces that become prone to dumping of garbage, criminal activities as well as drug addiction. These spaces are generally located near the periphery, which generally coincides with the entry to the forest or restricted areas, as in the case of Nardan Camp, Delhi. The residents have faced criminal activities such as theft, eve teasing, robbery etc. on a daily basis and the women have been the easiest target for the same. The primary research, including the site visits, revealed that the crime was due to easy access to the Basti, lack of physical infrastructure and behavior changes in the youth. The study indicated that the problems may be addressed by a few interventions based on the concepts of CPTED. These interventions were proposed after a thorough understanding of the needs and the activity pattern with community participation to bring in a sense of belonging to the dwellers. The public spaces could be made safer by providing basic physical infrastructure such as streetlights, boundary walls, creating buffer zones on the periphery, installing cameras etc. Also, by providing safe spaces for all age groups. These small interventions can bring about a change in the Basti through CPTED and

can help transform gloomy dysfunctional public spaces into celebrated community spaces while increasing livability and quality of life.

Keywords: *Nardan Basti, CPTED, Criminal Activity, Safety, Security, Activity*

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization and city development as a result of ongoing migration have caused several challenges in Indian cities. Slum relocation, unauthorized settlement, overpopulation, and economic inequality have all contributed to an increase in crime. Urban growth and city expansion frequently result in unforeseen spaces; concealed and neglected, they can become breeding grounds for criminals and drug users or a waste dumping site. These abandoned areas are dangerous and have become hotspots for criminal activity such as theft, eve teasing, robbery, and so on.

Delhi, India's capital, faces a persistent slum problem due to rapid urbanization, rural-to-urban migration, and a growing population. The city now houses over 2,500 slums, accommodating millions of people and constituting a significant fraction of the total population. (Sinha & Shekhar, 2017) The influx of rural migrants seeking better economic opportunities has exacerbated the issue, leading to the rapid spread of slum settlements. Living conditions in these slums are characterized by overcrowding, lack of essential facilities, and inadequate housing, resulting in serious health hazards and poor overall well-being. Slum dwellers often lack proper sanitation, safe drinking water, and waste management systems. Apart from these a major problem which has been neglected is the increasing crime rate in the unauthorized settlements of Delhi. In Delhi 43% of slum residents reported that minor crimes like fights, brawls, and snatching have increased in their locality. (Jyoti Mishra, 2022)

Nardan Camp in Delhi is an unauthorized settlement located near the protected forest area in Tughlakabad. The location of the Basti and unprecedented growth have led to formation of land parcels near the approach of the Basti which has led to shady places for criminal activities. These crimes have led to unsafe environment for the people of the Basti especially for women and children. These crimes need to be addressed and prevented through design interventions in the Basti based on the methods of Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED).

Figure 1- Entry of Nardan Basti, Source: Emara Architecture and Urbanism

Figure 2 – Streets of Nardan Basti, Source: Google Earth

Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) is a multidisciplinary crime prevention method that employs urban and architectural design as well as the management of built and natural settings. CPTED tactics seek to reduce victimization, dissuade offender decisions that lead to criminal actions, and foster a sense of community among residents in order to achieve territorial control of places, reduce crime, and reduce fear of crime. (Singapore, 2003a)

1.1 Aim

The aim of the research paper is to create safe public spaces and provide solutions for increasing crimes in Nardan Basti through design interventions based on the methods of CPTED.

2. METHODOLOGY

The primary research included site visits to the Basti and qualitative method of Focused Group Discussions (FGD). The site visit was conducted to understand the ground reality and to get acquainted with the spaces. Apart from that, the focused group discussion with the women and youth of the Basti was also arranged with help of an NGO IGSSS and EMARA Architecture and Urbanism, New Delhi already working in the Basti. The discussion included approx. 20 women aged 14 to 70 and children approx. 10 in number. The base map of the Basti was used to mark spaces as indicated by the Basti people. For the Focused group discussion questionnaire was prepared with open ended questions such as-

Have you been a victim or witness of any criminal activity?

At what time are criminal activities more prone to happen?

What spaces or streets in the Basti feel unsafe?

What is the condition of streetlights?

Does the government authority provide surveillance, is it helpful?

The responses were recorded and then were used to demarcate areas on the map for better understanding and then these areas were visited to consider various factors such as approach, public use, connectivity, etc. The responses were used to propose interventions for the spaces that were more prone to crime and transform them into lively public spaces.

The secondary research includes reports regarding crime in Delhi Slums and CPTED methods for crime prevention, the guidelines, principles, and Objectives.

Figure 3- Site Visit of Nardan Basti
;Source: Emara Architecture and Urbanism

Figure 4- Focused Group discussion.; Source:Emara Architecture and Urbanism

Figure 5 – Methodology Framework, Source: Author

1.2 Study Area

Nardan Basti is present near Tughlaqabad on the Mehrauli-Badarpur road and has an area of 38757 sq km with 593 households. It is adjacent to the Asola Bhatti Wildlife Sanctuary, so the Basti site has contoured slopes and is surrounded by lush greens in the south. The designated land use in Master plan is Regional Park under Recreational spaces. Basti has 3 entry points: two from Mehrauli Badarpur road through Warsi and MST road and one entry from Khatta camp through Prem Nagar Road. The Basti has dense development set along the narrow streets with very few open areas. The frontage of the Basti near the main approach from the highway has quite a lot of open space which is acquired by parking, construction material and waste dumping. This area is the major breeding ground for criminal activities.

Figure 6- Location of Nardan Basti, Source: Author

Figure 7- Nardan Basti location in map of Southeast Delhi; Source: MapsofIndia.com

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) is a proactive or reactive strategy that modifies the environment to decrease the likelihood of criminal activity. CPTED includes six main components: territoriality, surveillance, access control, image and maintenance, activity support, and target hardening. (Cozens et al., 2005) Territoriality involves clearly identifying ownership of land or property through symbolic and real barriers. Surveillance includes formal, informal, and mechanical methods to deter potential offenders. Access control restricts or redirects movement within a location through physical or perceptual barriers. Image and maintenance promote a positive image and show guardianship through upkeep and eliminating disarray. Activity support encourages intended patterns of use and community engagement. Target hardening involves physical barriers and reinforcement to deny or limit access to a target. Excessive reliance on target hardening can create a fortress mentality and damage the self-policing capacity of the environment. CPTED can effectively reduce opportunities for crime and the fear of crime. Refinements to the strategy may include more risk assessment and socio-economic and demographic profiling. (Abdul, n.d.) CPTED strategies can be tailored to specific issues, such as reducing open-air drug sales and use.

The Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) Guidebook (Singapore, 2003b) emphasizes the role of the community, homeowners, planners, developers, and architects in integrating CPTED principles and concepts into the design and management of the physical environment for effective crime prevention and control. The designated purpose of a space can be evaluated using the Three D's (Design, Deterrence, and Detection) framework, which considers factors such as legibility, transparency, familiarity, and territorial reinforcement. Visibility and lighting play a crucial role in enhancing natural surveillance and reducing concealed or isolated routes, entrapment areas, and crime opportunities. Activity generation, including cultural and entertainment activities, can contribute to the vitality of business districts and town centers, attracting more people and tourists. Design elements such as open railings, well-defined entrances, visible washroom entrances, and sufficient lighting contribute to continuity, clear ownership, and safety.

The authors Al-Ghiyadh and Al-Khafaji in the IOP Conference have mentioned that urban planning and urban design play a crucial role in creating safe cities and improving security conditions in urban areas. The combination of urban planning and urban design is essential in the process of building safe cities.(Al-Ghiyadh & Al-Khafaji, 2021) The paper suggests that various elements of urban planning and design, such as street planning, land use, building density, and management and good governance, can reduce opportunities for crime and increase security. The authors emphasize the importance of designing for territoriality, access control, defensible space, accessibility, activity support, building image, visibility, lighting, and maintenance in order to enhance security in urban areas. The paper also highlights the need for proper organization, cooperation with city authorities, and the implementation of policies and tasks such as successful planning and design, good governance, professional police personnel, and modern surveillance technologies to create safe cities.(Al-Ghiyadh & Al-Khafaji, 2021)

The review of two decades of research on violence against women in urban slums of India concludes that crime against women in these areas is widespread and persistent. The prevalence of any form of violence against women in urban slums, as reported in the studies, ranged from 15% to 59.3%.(Jungari et al., 2022)The review also highlights that the risks of violence and crime against women in urban slums have not changed over time due to unsafe spaces in the locality and lack of physical infrastructure. The studies reviewed were mostly concentrated in Mumbai, indicating a need for in-depth studies covering slums in other major cities to gain better insights into the issue.

4. DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

4.1 Crime in Nardan Basti

Nardan Basti due to its location, unrestricted access through the highway, and proximity to the forest area has led to an increase in crime in the Basti. Eave teasing, snatching, and theft have become a daily affair and 70% of the people in FGD have been witnesses to it and 30% have been victims. The main access to the Basti is from the Mehrauli Badarpur Road but the stretch from the highway to the Basti is covered with wilderness on both sides. All the people in FGD agreed that the areas in proximity to the Forest are more prone to crime. These areas become the hiding places for thieves, they attack people in broad daylight using sharp

weapons and snatch valuable items. Also, these areas become hotspots for drug addicts. In the FGD, 80% of the people agreed that more streetlights should be installed, due to the absence of streetlights in the Basti, at night it becomes way more dangerous. The Basti although near the highway, does not have bus stop; the nearest bus stop is more than 1 km away from the Basti which makes it difficult for women, children, and the elderly to travel especially at night. In the FGD, 90% of the people agreed that a bus stop should be made near the Basti for safety concerns. The areas in the Basti adjacent to the forest areas are unsafe due to thieves entering the houses easily and then running back to the forest. Women face eve teasing while returning from work or school at the main street which makes the streets unsafe for women due to lack of lights and surveillance.

Figure 8 – Basti Base Map showing crime Hotspot and dead spaces.; *Base Map Source: Emara Architecture and Urbanism , Illustration: Author .*

Figure 9- Entry of Basti.; *Source: Google Maps*

Figure 10- Gathering at Entrance. .; *Source: Google Maps*

Figure 11- Bati open from forest side.;
Source: Emara Architecture and Urbanism

Figure 12- Poor Solid waste management;
Source: Emara Architecture and Urbanism

4.2 Aspirations of the Basti’s People

The focused group discussion with the women and youth of the Basti brought forward various problems and demands of the people for a safe environment. The people aspire to feel safe in the public spaces, also the women and children of the Basti need safe spaces for recreational activities. The elimination of criminal activity from the Basti through environmental design will lead to positive impact on the youth as these shady areas lead to breeding grounds for drug addiction. The Basti people also demand for a security check post to be established near the main entrance for the purpose of safety.

Figure 14- Safety of women;
Source: Morbi Update

Figure 15- No drug. ;
Source: Shutterstock

Figure 16- Children playing area; Source: Shutterstock.

In the FGD 95% of the people agreed safety of women should be the considered at priority, 90% of the people wanted the basti to not become a hotspot for drug addiction and 85% people wanted safe playing area for their children.

4.3 Design Interventions as per CPTED

The proposed designed interventions for the Basti are based on first generation CPTED such as natural surveillance, territoriality, access control, image and maintenance, activity support, and target hardening, and it can be made possible through second generation community engagement. The proposals include public parks, bus stops, solid waste management, creating buffer zones between the forest and Basti, installation of streetlights and CCTVs for surveillance, etc.

Figure 17- Proposed Plan for Nardan Basti; Base Map Source: Emara Architecture and Urbanism, Illustration source: Author

Figure 18-Public Park; Source: Author

Figure 19-Bus Stop; Source: Author.

Figure 20-Solid waste management; Source: Author

Figure 21-CCTV Surveillance and Street; Source: Author lights; Source: Author

4.3.1 Public Park

A public park alongside the main street connecting the highway and the Basti will help to create safe recreational space and will also lead to natural surveillance due to the presence of people in the park and keeping of eyes on the street. The development of the park will improve the image of the street. The activities in the park, such as interaction of people, swings for children, walls for kids to draw, multipurpose central space, will help provide active environment to avoid shadiness in the area.

Figure 22-Playing area - Activity., Source: *Emara Architecture and Urbanism*

Figure 23 -Children drawing on wall - Activity. ; Source: *Emara Architecture and Urbanism*

4.3.2 Bus Stop

The bus stop at the main entrance of the Basti, which was once functional, was demolished to develop a new one which is more than a kilometer away. This situation has led to various problems while travelling for women, children, and elder people. Hence, a bus stop can be proposed at the main entrance to facilitate safety and security even during the night and add a sense of Territoriality.

Figure 24-Safe Entrance of Basti due to nearby bus stop and streetlights. - Activity; Source:Author

4.3.3 Buffer Zone

Buffer Zones can be created in the areas that are adjacent to the forest to control access to the Basti. The buffer zones will have fencing made by recyclable materials such as cycle rims, tires, metal scraps etc. Apart from fencing, the buffer will be a landscaped area with a sitting area and space for urban farming. Hence, the buffer zone will control access and will also add activity and factor of image and maintenance to the area to make it lively.

Figure 25-Access control through Wheels and scraps of metal creating a boundary ; Source:Author

Figure 26- Urban Farming; Source: *Emara Architecture and Urbanism*

Figure 27- Natural Surveillance in Buffer Zones; Source:Author

5. CONCLUSION

Nardan Basti, being an unauthorized settlement, lacks physical infrastructure and is prone to criminal activities due to easy access, proximity to the forest etc. CPTED methods-based interventions such as natural surveillance through activity in public parks and buffer zones can help to reduce crime. Apart from them, access control through fencing and provision of Bus stops can add a sense of Territoriality in the Basti. The youth of the Basti are quite active to bring a change in the Basti, hence second generation CPTED community participation can be utilized for the interventions to take place. These small interventions can bring about a major change, transform dead, shady areas into lively places and ensure safety and security in the Basti.

INTERVENTION	CPTED COMPONENT
Public Park	Activity Support, Image and Maintenance, Natural Surveillance
Bus Stop	Activity Support, Territoriality
Buffer Zones	Access Control, Activity Support, Image and Maintenance, Territoriality
Streets Light and CCTV	Surveillance, Access Control

6. CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

I have no conflict of interest to disclose.

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Deconstruction of Gender Dynamics and Its Implications for Gendered Inclusive Design: Application of Urban Big Data and Interpretable Machine Learning Method in India

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Biography

Trishla Chadha is an Architect and Urban Designer completed her post-graduation in M.Arch (Master of Architecture) in Urban Design at The Bartlett of Architecture, University College London. Her personality is appended with professional experience across multiple scales and community-driven approaches. Her interests also lie in the field of architectural journalism, and her work has been published by various international digital platforms.

ABSTRACT

The vectors of inequality and difference are multiple—class, gender, race, culture, age, and sexuality - intersecting in a complex matrix. Robust studies reinforce that gender inequalities in space occupation are not necessarily the consequence of normative desires, such as "equal" or "just separate", but can also be the result of the way urban environments are structured and culturally created, implying unequal access to space

The relationship between fear experienced by women for their safety, a sense of victimization, and women's movement patterns in urban places are three phenomena that are

rarely dealt with in combination. For many years, crime prevention through environmental design has been proposed as a principle for enhancing safety in urban environments and understanding the relationship with fear and safety associated with the built environment. Yet, little is known about the application of these policies to gendered urban spaces. This study proposes qualitative surveys to depict the number of women who experience fear and the characteristics of the most frightening places. Qualitative studies, however, are said to be of limited use in understanding how fear affects social and mental processes, as well as how space is produced as a result of fear. The matter is explained in profound depth using quantitative research techniques that analyze the relationship between crime incidence and the urban environment using geo-located urban big data, such as points-of-interest (POI), crime data, and street view imagery data from the study area – New Delhi, India. This study proposes a comprehensive evaluation model for gender, crime, and safety in cities, integrating the space syntax method, neural networks for street view image feature extraction, and Twitter data on emotions experienced by people, providing both quantitative calculation and qualitative observation results. The results highlight the promising approach of using multi-methods to analyze the adequacy of urban principles and policies in encouraging greater inclusion within the context of this new paradigm by examining and compiling the available data, developing gender-sensitive frameworks, conducting case studies, and critically evaluating the study area to formulate hypotheses and apply assumptions. The proposed evaluation model serves as a useful tool for policymakers and urban planners to understand gender-related crime dynamics, leading to informed decisions and improvements in the quality of urban environments.

Relevance of the research:

The research's relevance lies in its exploration of the relationship between gender, safety, and urban spaces, using both qualitative and quantitative methods. By assessing the application of urban design and a planning approach in gendered urban spaces, the study aims to enhance safety and inclusion. Policymakers and urban planners can use the research findings to make informed decisions and improve the quality of urban environments, addressing power imbalances and creating safer spaces for everyone.

Keywords: Fear of Violence, Gender-Sensitive Design, Urban Environment, Inclusive Cities, Crime, Spatial Exclusion

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Gender-Related Urbanism

Given the evolving discussions within theoretical, historical, and critical spheres, especially in the realm of feminism, it is imperative to promptly situate the comprehension of urban environments concerning gender. 'Feeling unsafe' is portrayed within the political and public domain as a phenomenon that influences everyone in a similar manner, irrespective of gender or social differences (Gardner, 1990). The reality is that the indicated emotion has two components, which have been gradually revealed by sociological studies (Duncan, 1996): on one side, how individuals describe lack of safety in public areas, and on the other side, experiencing fear for oneself (Smith, 1986) It is impossible to discuss reactions to the fear of violence (Canter, 1977) in urban environments without taking into account the social and political relations that structure both the physical spaces and the everyday routines of the individuals involved (Pain, 2001). Women's fears are substantially different from men's fears

in terms of their extent, nature, and effects on women's lives (Pain, 2001). Feminist researchers have argued for nearly 30 years that societal structures of gender inequality need to change in order to eradicate women's personal experiences of violence (Koskela, 1997).

At a time when demographic and societal developments allow women greater autonomy in the different domains of life, including the public sphere, it is crucial to analyze the persistence of these fears and their impact on daily experience, particularly regarding women's use of public space. This research sought to investigate these issues from a spatial perspective and recognize the wider social role of CPTED in shaping crime and prevention. The spatiality of fear, refers to a more sophisticated analysis of gendered spatiality rather than a straightforward description and recognition of the most unsafe and frightening areas in the urban environment (Colomina, 1992). The intention of the study is to investigate the relationship between spatial limitations and gender-driven power relations. The production of urban space through intersubjectivity and gender relations is the focus, rather than just an individual's use of space. By using an approach in relation to the gendered social relations perspective to examine the mechanisms that engender fear, this study is an attempt to be able to negate the myth that women are naturally fearful without turning them into 'victims'.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To form the research methodology, keywords including gender inequality, urban environment, violence, and fear of crime were surveyed across journal articles, books, and various resources. The texts were analyzed to establish a theoretical framework based on literature review, guide subjective analysis, and identify the research problem. The approach appears data-driven and technology-oriented, focusing on cities in general; however, there is a disconnect between this approach and understanding human needs and concerns.

2.1 Study Area

The study focuses on New Delhi, India, with a specific focus on Central Delhi. This area was chosen due to its high incidence of gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, domestic violence, and sexual assault, as exemplified by the infamous Delhi Gang Rape case in 2012, as highlighted in the latest available statistics from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB). This underscores the urgent need for a comprehensive analysis. Central Delhi's complex urban environment, significance in policy development, and presence of cultural attractions make it an ideal location for analyzing the intersection of urban dynamics, demographics, and gender-based violence.

2.2 Research Process

The process is broken down into sections, all of which can adjust to changing data patterns and hence urban demands in New Delhi, India.

2.2.1 Data Extraction

This study utilized available data to select variables encompassing natural, socioeconomic, spatial policies, and neighborhood factors. Data from Open Street Map (OSM) and Space Syntax were employed to analyze urban patterns tied to demographics, economy, population, transportation, and intensification points in Delhi. The geolocated datasets formed a spatial computation model. Mapillary was adopted for the initial google street view image collection from all directions to build a comprehensive image segmentation model in ArcGIS, employing deep convolutional neural networks for semantic segmentation using Python to extract the greenery, road and building features of the street view data.

2.2.2 Data Analytics and Machine Learning

Linear dimensionality reduction is used to decipher correlations, and the extracted prominent datasets spread over Delhi.

2.2.3 Data Driven Site Simulations

In order to further study the spatial-temporal dynamics of spatial patterns, data driven methods are used to run site simulations to explore the relationship between urban development and relevant driving factors, like space syntax methodology for the identification of centrally located and well-integrated areas by spatial modelling. The underlying cause-effect relationships in the urban growth process were analyzed using these simulations.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

3.1 Social and Spatial Status of Women

3.1.1 The Historical Context of Women

The position of women in the society is a complicated, multidimensional concept. The access and positions available to women within social institutions are examples of structural patriarchy, which also encompasses ideologies (beliefs, norms, and ideals concerning the stature and duties of women in a society) (Barrett, 1988). In addition to the pre-existing notions, ideologies and structural inequality occur within various dimensions.

Figure 1. The feminist movements during the 1960s – 70s. *Source: Femcrunch*

Women in India went through a cultural revolution in the 2000s that placed a strong emphasis on women's rights to freedom, choice, and independence under the influence of economic liberalization and the development of modern technology (Misra, 1997). Due to the widespread use of social media, the term "fourth-wave feminism," which originated in the West, appeared almost simultaneously in India as well.

Figure 2. The Gujarat Stepwells provide a pleasant counterpoint to this paradigm by conveying stories about women, and life. *Source: Gujaratexpert*

Despite the revolutionary campaigns and noteworthy advancements, it must be underlined that the path leading toward a universal acceptance of feminist ideas and their implications for future research remains patchy. The diverse theoretical approaches for the study of gender relations put forward by feminist and non-feminist scholars are often challenging to reconcile and remain ignored in the field of architecture and design.

3.1.2 Theoretical Link Between the Status of Women and Violence

There are several theoretically viable mechanisms that connect these aspects of women's status to violence against women (Bryson, 2016). First, when men are dominant both in number and power in the family, political, economic, and other social institutions, their policies and practices are more likely to express, reinforce, and justify male dominance over women (Massey, 1994). Second, violence is a tool that males can use in institutions where men assert power and control to keep women out or under their control.

Fear among women is a key factor in this process. Criminologists have been intrigued by the "fear-victimization paradox," which holds that although men are more likely to be victims of violent crime than women, women are more fearful than men (Pain, 2014). Assumptions are made that women's fears are illogical and irrational, yet others have discovered explanations for the emotions encountered by them. According to feminist theory, men are able to control women's behavior, restrict or limit their involvement, and so maintain control over social institutions because of their ability to instill fear in them (Harvey, 2009). Men's dominance over women is secured by the instillation of a culture of fear.

3.2 Social and Spatial Domains Intertwined

3.2.1 Intersection of Gender and Built Environment

The study of space and gender must be interdisciplinary; in addition to sociology, it also considers geography, history, urban planning, and geography (Bondi & Rose 2003). Some of the strongest criticisms of conventional fear of crime theory have been made by feminist criminologists, particularly Stanko (1987, 1990a, 1997), who has highlighted the socio-political production of fear of crime, essentially its gendered form.

According to Rachel Pain, "a common assumption in a typical traditional geographical approach is that women's physical fears are more significant than the metaphorical connotations of place" (Pain, 2014). One treats space as a surface when they are only focused solely on the spatial variations in their levels of fear (Bondi, 1991). Critical social and

cultural geography discourses have long argued that space is more than merely a surface on which social behaviors take place (Harvey, 2009). Instead, space is a social category in and of itself, formed by social behaviors. Space functions as both a social practice's medium and its product (Smith, 1987).

Figure 3. Statistics depicting the unsafe experience faced by women in their daily activities.
Source: YouGov, Twitter

3.3 Linking Fear to the Built Environment

3.3.1 Fear and Emotion from a Gender-Sensitive Perspective

Feminist geographers emphasize fear as a key factor shaping the gendered experience of urban spaces. Geographies of fear research extensively explores the link between women's fear and their urban interactions. However, despite its significance, fear of crime research often overlooks the gender dimension, using gender merely as a control variable rather than exploring its impact (Kusum, 1996). Notably, the urban environment, particularly well-designed public spaces, affects women's well-being and fear reduction (Booth, 1996). Yet, research connecting various urban aspects and people's subjective well-being with gender remains scarce. This study aims to investigate how women's emotional states are influenced by their momentary satisfaction with urban public spaces, while considering personal and experiential variables.

3.3.2 Designing Out Crime: CPTED Principles

The foundation of CPTED, which stands for Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design, is rooted in the pioneering work of C. Ray Jeffrey (1971) and Oscar Newman (1973). During the 1970s, they explored the intricate relationship between crime and urban design, aiming to decipher the upsurge in crime in urban America. They coined the terms 'defensible space' (Newman) and CPTED (Jeffrey), profoundly impacting research and policy (Cozens, 2001). Despite their influence, criticisms have emerged, particularly regarding the oversight of social factors in shaping crime. This has fueled a growing CPTED discourse (Cozens, 2001).

Social processes significantly shape crime and its prevention in the urban environment, as seen in works by (Monday J, 2013), (De Souza & Miller, 2012), and (Meth, 2009), which highlight the impacts of health disparities, historical racial inequality, unemployment, political influences, and more on crime and its management. These factors align with the study's objective to recognize gender dynamics' role in shaping criminology research.

3.3.3 Intersectional Studies – Gender, Emotions and Urban Environment

The discussion on intersectionality underscores the dangers of treating categories as distinct oppressions, because doing so suggests a distinction of oppressions that could lead to an essentialist understanding of them (Lefebvre, 1974). In order to comprehend women's experience of fear in public space (Pain, 2001) and their "spatial knowledge," this study analyses how women experience fear in the urban environment. This analysis builds on studies focused on the intersections of many dimensions of power (Koskela, 1997). The study aims to make progress toward a comprehensive understanding of fear from an intersectional and urban environment perspective and to contribute to research on the relationship between women's fears for their safety, the emotional experience of a space, and women's mobility in the urban environment, three phenomena that are rarely dealt with together.

Based on the findings of the literature review, the study proposes the following research hypothesis:

1. The spatial limitations that women face in daily life are a manifestation of the gendered power relations that are assumed.
2. Women's inferior status and their personal contributions to the upkeep of gendered power in connection to space are a direct result of their experiences with fear.
3. The urban environment can convey meaning, eradicate 'fear' and elicit urban emotions to implicate a gendered spatial context.

4. ANALYTICAL RESULTS

4.1 Data compilation and Data mapping

The aim of this process is to explore the built environment from a ‘macro’ to ‘micro’ scale. Qualitative data extracted from OSM includes datasets with significant social and spatial characteristics that define the urban environment and its use. Datasets such as road network, residential densities, pedestrianization levels, permeable neighborhood density, economic development levels, population density, transportation, and people’s perception of the public areas were mapped using GIS to study the complexity of patterns formed by the data across Central Delhi. To understand the significance of social qualities of space in relation to the built environment, data from Twitter related to keywords signifying negative and positive emotions such as ‘fear’, ‘happy’, ‘calm’, ‘sad’ was extracted and mapped on QGIS.

Figure 4. Land use and Mobility; **Figure 5.** Pedestrian Density; **Figure 6.** Economic Density; **Figure 7.** Crime Rate (Top to Bottom).

Figure 8. Emotions such as ‘happy’, ‘sad’, ‘fear’, ‘pleasant’, ‘love’, ‘bored’ extracted and mapped in Central Delhi from Twitter using machine learning analysis. The colours visualised on ArcGIS are for graphical purposes only.

4.2 Modelling and Analysis

After the data compilation, the analytical phase begins with the spatial analysis, including the use of modelling techniques such as axial and segment-angular analysis, high-resolution spatial network modelling, visibility, and Visual Graph Analysis (VGA). The pedestrian or vehicular movement patterns are further analyzed to create an in-depth understanding of human activities and interactions in their areas. Statistical analysis is used to explore the relationship between human activity and spatial configuration.

Figure 9. Spatial Network Modelling with space syntax analysis showing Integration 1000R.

4.3 Machine Learning Dimensionality Analysis

Using linear dimensionality, the data is further reduced from the three-dimensional aspect using machine learning techniques such as K-means clustering and Principal component analysis. The resultant clusters are mapped to understand the dominant datasets which are – population, Public Transport Access Levels, points of interest, economic activity, pedestrian footfall and its influence over Central Delhi.

Figure 10. Principal Component Analysis used for analysing the dominant datasets prevalent in Central Delhi and understanding the contextual framework

4.4 Categorize the Urban Spaces Using Image Semantic Segmentation

Image semantic segmentation is an integral part of machine vision technology regarding image understanding. Semantic segmentation based on supervised learning can divide an image into several specific regions with unique properties and propose targets of interest, which is the process of linking each pixel in an image to a class label. These labels may include buildings, trees, roads, etc. Semantic segmentation enables the fast recognition, segmentation and processing of image data. The following simulation is performed in areas with extracted emotional data to get a building to image percentage. The images were analysed using semantic segmentation to segregate different elements such as sky, trees, roads and buildings.

Figure 11. Image and semantic segmentation model.

The final model outputs the result of segmenting the land use into colors. The result contains 10,340,400 open spaces, 54,530,450 landscape spaces and 100,200,405 built spaces. According to the segmentation results, landscape spaces have the highest proportion, followed by open spaces and built spaces have the highest proportion.

4.5 Correlation of Emotional Data and Image Segmentation

The last part of the study intends to explore the correlation between the emotional data extracted and the image segmentation model and discover which spaces have the potential to influence the gender segregation based on evoking negative and positive emotions amongst people while traversing through the built environment by computing rank cross-relation to indicate the strength of the correlations (figure 12).

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2][n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Figure 12. The study analysed correlations between social media emotional data and a segmentation model. Cross-correlation ranked perceptions experienced together. High 'fear' and 'angry' emotions were linked to 'built spaces' and 'roads' (less 'open spaces'). 'Happy' and 'calm' emotions dominated 'landscaped spaces' and open areas. 'Awful' and 'boring' emotions correlated with 'landscaped spaces' and 'built spaces'. On average, landscaped areas related to 'boring', 'happy', and 'calm' emotions; open spaces to 'calm', 'happy', and 'boring'; built spaces to 'fear' and 'angry' emotions. Despite not reflecting expected values, these strong correlations provide valuable insights into the study.

5. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to enhance awareness of gender and sexuality aspects in design and emotional perception while assessing the inclusiveness of established urban design guidelines in these areas. Given the limited literature on this topic in architecture, the assumption was that CPTED's design guidelines lacked complete gender and emotion inclusivity. Data exposed gender inequalities and 'fear' patterns, revealing societal biases. Notably, a culture of violence against women stemmed from gender inequity, intertwined with women's fear of sexual violence due to reported incidents. This generalized fear was justified, as women shared knowledge of assaults on others, inducing fear despite personal experiences. Few

studies explored emotional connections to happiness in urban spaces. The study plans to craft a design strategy from emotional data and highlight the link between urban development and emotions. A positive urban atmosphere correlated with better emotional states. Future research should delve into design elements impacting urban ambience, bridging subjective emotions and objective urban characteristics for effective urban planning.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Unnecessarily aggravated by gender ignorant urban planning, disproportionate fear of urban crime is an oppressive, informal social control of women that frequently serves to divert attention away from the more common issue of domestic violence. The study on gender-specific usage of urban spaces offers a number of fairly broad recommendations to the existing CPTED literature from the perspective of gender-sensitive urban development to assist both sexes in finding the appropriate spaces.

1. The intersection of gender, fear and emotions would build the global relevance of the CPTED literature through the addition of diverse perspectives.
2. It raises awareness of the idea that space is not neutral; depending on how it is designed, women's and girls' use of, appropriation of, and safety in such places may be supported or undermined.
3. To lessen displacements and rivalry for use, there should be enough open space that can be appropriated nearby.
4. It recognizes that women are aware of when, why, and places in cities where they feel unsafe, and that their fears are rooted in reality (the connection between feelings of fear and violence).
5. People should be encouraged to use and appropriate a diverse range of spaces to promote multi-functional utilization.
6. Parks and sports facilities, for instance, should be used for several purposes.
7. A crucial precondition is security. This can be accomplished with the use of open structures, visual linkages with the environment, and supervision.
8. Diverse demographic groups should have access to different facilities. They should be defined with detail.
9. Atmospheric quality is extremely important, especially for women.
10. Small-scale structures are necessary because a dominant, arena-type atmosphere encourages gender-specific types of appropriation.
11. In addition, females, especially those in the early stages of puberty, require specific protected times or places in order to reach their full potential unimpeded, such as when participating in sports away from male gaze. Although gender-sensitive participation methods must be ensured, the public's effective engagement should be self-evident.
12. Interim usage projects need to be planned more flexibly and with greater care for gender-sensitive challenges.
13. In addition, more in-depth research is required to comprehend the effects of changing gender relations in relation to a variety of emotional states and encounters with the urban environment.

7. CONCLUSION

This research delves into the intricate relationship between gender, safety, and urban spaces in New Delhi, India, with a broader perspective on urban development. It brings to light persistent gender inequalities within urban environments, emphasizing the distinct fears and safety concerns experienced by women. While Crime Prevention Through Environmental

Design (CPTED) principles are pivotal, they often overlook the gender dimension, which can inadvertently reinforce stereotypes. Designers should be cautious of placing people in predefined categories, as it may displace or limit their rights within urban spaces. Gender-inclusive planning should be viewed as an ongoing process, recognizing that city-specific cultural norms and geographic factors shape individuals' needs and experiences differently.

As the world's population increasingly gravitates toward cities, which are projected to house 80 percent of the global population by 2050, decisions made today will profoundly impact society's social and environmental future. To ensure that women feel safe and empowered within urban environments, it is imperative that they are equally represented in participation and consultation processes at all planning levels. Furthermore, this study aims to craft a design strategy informed by emotional data, underscoring the link between urban development and emotions. A positive urban atmosphere has been shown to correlate with improved emotional well-being, prompting future research to delve into design elements that can enhance urban ambience, bridging the gap between subjective emotions and objective urban characteristics for more effective urban planning. However, it is important to acknowledge the geographic limitations and data reliance inherent in this study, necessitating further exploration of diverse cultural contexts and the conduct of comparative studies to create universal gender-sensitive design frameworks.

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The impact of Urban Design in minimizing women's fear of crime

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Bio: I am an Architect from Anna University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu. After graduating, I started practicing as Junior Architect in Lengths Group Pvt Ltd, Hyderabad. In 2021 I joined Dspacio OPC Pvt Ltd as Design Head and completed few Architectural and Interior projects in Pollachi, Coimbatore. I'm currently employed by SCSA, Coimbatore as an Assistant Professor. My thesis topic, Aadhya – An Integrated Centre for Women and Children Victims inspired me to study more on Urban Fabric and Crime involving women in Urban Environments.

Theme: Urban Environment's role in Natural Monitoring

Abstract

Crime is a condition that infringes on an individual's right to live in a tranquil and secure environment. Each year, the rate of crime is increasing in tandem with technical advancement and urbanization. On the other hand, fear is characterized as anxiety or worries about being harmed or victimized. One crucial outcome of rising crime rates is a psychological phobia, which breeds fear of crime. In society, those who are already weak on the socio-economic and psychological fronts may lack the means to defend themselves from high-crime areas and will be plagued by their fear of crime. Areas like low-density public spaces, curving trails with poor lighting, urban forest with unclear vision lines, destitute and abandoned structures with minimal human traffic are more prevalent in crime activities. Thefts, robbery, sexual assault, and molestation are among the more prevalent crimes in India, in which the majority of incidents take place in metropolitan areas. This paper discusses how a conurbation design can help women feel safe and comfortable using a space in an urban setting without the fear of victimization, thus reducing deleterious activities in Indian context. The concepts of SCP, CPTED, can minimize the opportunities for crime and fear of crime. The methodology consists of a questionnaire given to around 320 women in urban settings in India who experience a fear of crime while using public spaces. The result of this paper indicates that a destitute urban setting instigates offenders to engage in malevolent activities, thus perniciously increasing the fear of crime. Contrary to this, secured cities with cohesive communities and mixed land use with bustling activities throughout the day can lessen the opportunities for crime and could create defensible spaces.

Key Words: *Fear of Crime, Urban Crimes, Natural Surveillance, Urban Planning, Defensible Spaces.*

1. Introduction

India has reported a total of **4,28,278** cases of **Crime Against Women** in 2021, showing an increase of **15.3%** over 2020 (3,71,503 cases). According to National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) report 2021, this includes Indian Penal Code (IPC) crimes such as Theft and Robbery, Kidnapping and Abduction, Rape, and assault on women. 43,414 cases of **Crime Against Women** were registered in 2021, in 19 Metropolitan Cities, which shows an increase of **22.9%** over 2020 (NCRB, report 2021). As per United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), Crime prevention is defined as **“the strategies and measures that seek to reduce the risk of crimes occurring, and their potential harmful effects on individuals and society, including fear of crime, by intervening to influence their multiple causes.”**

Numerous elements, such as socio-economic considerations, cultural backgrounds, environmental influences, poverty, etc., affect the offender's motivation to commit the crime. Additionally, the fear or dread of crime induces anxiety and has psychological repercussions on spatial perception (Ferraro, K.F. 1995). This paper asserts that one such aspect is the urban environment, where the majority of crimes occur, which can be planned for or changed to aid in crime prevention. Diminished temporal activity gaps are linked to integrated spaces in the

city's heart that include an assortment of daytime and nighttime activities, which in turn attracts a wide variety of social groups (Ratnayake, 2013). Two main strategies for prevention of crimes in urban settings include Situational Crime Prevention (SCP) and Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED). The paper also seeks to identify the environments that make women feel more vulnerable to the crime and maximizes their dread of crime.

1.1 Crime Triangle

Any crime entails an offender, a victim, and an opportunity, which comprise the crime triangle (Fig 1.1). The criminal is perpetually motivated to carry out the planned crime against the desired victim in a setting where there is little danger of being discovered and no chance for the victim to attempt to flee. Preventive measures begin at the point where they can eliminate any one element of the crime triangle.

Fig 1.1: Crime Triangle (*Solution for Crime in Fargo | Community Awareness, n.d.*)

1.2 Situational Crime Prevention (SCP)

The strategy of SCP is that it addresses specific crimes by managing, designing and manipulating the environment in a manner that seeks to increase the risk to the offender, while reducing the offender's potential reward for committing the crime (Patel, 2013).

1.3 Three D concept

Every urban area or neighborhood requires a space assessment based on the three D's: **Designation, Design** and **Definition**. The **Designation** aids in determining the original intent behind its creation as well as the actual use of the area, and it examines any conflicts between the two. **Design** aids in regulating and assessing human behavior in the physical environment that is designed. **Definition** helps in defining the area in terms of physical, cultural, social, and legal systems, as well as its relationship to intended human behavior (The Three-D Approach to Space Assessment, n.d.). The implementation of the CPTED concepts into practice is assisted by the space assessment process.

1.4 CPTED

The CPTED concept contained suggestions for encouraging virtuous attitudes ("motive reinforcement") and suggestions for reducing the likelihood of physical crime occurring ("target hardening"). First Generation CPTED, divides into four principles: **Territoriality / Territorial control, Natural surveillance, Image and Milieu, Access control**. The psychological behavior of human is to commit uncommon activities in the places where there are no eyes to watch them (Jacobs, 1961; Newman, 1972)

Territoriality - Physical design can contribute to a sense of control and proprietorship in users (Newman, 1972). It will be challenging for the perpetrator to commit any offense in a location that possesses ownership or that has a caretaker.

Natural surveillance –As rightly quoted by Jane Jacobs “Eyes on the streets” (Jacobs, 1961; Newman, 1972) will be the ideal way of monitoring. Other than the residents, Hawkers and shopkeepers of the neighborhood can also act as the greatest observers of the unusual activities.

Image and Milieu - The Broken Window Theory (JQ Wilson, GL Kelling 1982), which asserts that anything that is not kept up with would make the offender believe that there is no one to watch over or take care of the area, validates this (Doran & Lees, 2005). This encourages him/her to indulge in the crime without hesitation. Appleton’s Prospect and Refuge theory also focuses on human’s preferences of environment which offer more of viewable and protective spaces (Appleton, 1975; Petherick, 2000)

Access control - Similar to territoriality, this aids in restricting the access of outsiders into the property. Entry restrictions can be achieved by providing road barricades, access control systems, screening with landscape, thus creating mini neighborhoods which has controlled and restricted usage.

Thus the 1st Generation CPTED focuses more on strengthening the community and Residents acting as natural monitoring agents, whereas the 2nd Generation CPTED concentrates on offender’s perspective and decision making; which deals with crime displacement based on territorial, temporal, tactical, target, and functional aspects. The concepts in 2nd Generation comprises of **Social Cohesion, Community Culture, Connectivity and Threshold Capacity**. CPTED is also used as tool to manipulate human behavior in environmental psychology (Jorgensen et al., 2012). This approach will be helpful for the urban designers and planners to manage the settings of parks, streets, gathering spaces to minimize crime.

2. Literature Review

Various Research papers related to Fear of crime, Environments in which crime happens, urban cues for crimes, crime in public transport, urban safety, SCP and CTPED in Indian context, research papers of various timelines, and geographic settings were the key aspects for selecting the literature study. Based on these 4 papers with related topic were taken into the study to understand the methodology, survey samples and results.

Table 2.1: Comparative table for Literature Review

Topic	Methodology	Sample Size	Result
Revisiting fear and place: women's fear of attack and the built Environment. (Koskela & Pain, 2000) Hille Koskela , Rachel Pain.	Quantitative research	The questionnaire survey of 389 women was carried out in two cities of contrast environments.. In addition 45 in-depth interviews	In the end of the survey from two cities, Helsinki and Edinburgh; the results were quiet contrasting. However the need for developing countries to prioritize women’s safety and design out fear in urban spaces will be the primary concern was the outcome.
Fear of Crime in Urban Settings: Influence of Environmental	Methodology involves the details of various theories	---	This paper was concluded by comparing the fear of crime and the existing theories which describes

Features, Presence of People and Social Variables. (Ratnayake, 2013) Rangajeewa Ratnayake	and case examples justifying the theoretical statements.		the potential areas of crime. Additionally, it emphasizes the necessity of a comprehensive approach to urban design that integrates socio-economic culture and the Prospect Refuge Theory.
Situational Crime Prevention: A Study in Indian Context. (Patel, 2013) Dr. Nirpat Patel	Quantitative survey of different crimes in two Indian Cities namely Indore and Jabalpur were taken.		This paper concludes by emphasizing the need for widening the crime prevention approach, exploration of applicability of SCP in developing countries, adequate training for SCP oriented modules.
Geographies of Urban Crimes in India (Gupta, 2022) Bashabi Gupta	Various Indian Cities were chosen and from the National Crime Records Bureau the incidence of crime was considered.		An alarming trend is an upsurge in crime in all of India's cities, which makes it mandatory for intervention of preventative measures at multiple levels along with strict policing.
Present Research: The Impact of Urban Design in minimizing Women's Fear of Crime. (2023)	Quantitative survey in various cities of India	300 samples	Correlating the theoretical concepts with the facts numbers obtained from the quantitative survey, and providing urban design solutions for preventing crime.

Despite significant research on a particular topic, there is lack of methodology and implementation of the theory into the practical aspects in Indian Context. Research papers have not considered entire Indian population for the study or survey. With a strategic methodology and survey, this research attempted to close the gap between theory and immediately usable solutions in the Indian context. A survey was conducted to collect perspectives from women living in different Indian cities. The analysis of the survey results led to the formation of a correlation between the findings and the theory.

3. Methodology

The understanding of an assortment of ideas and design approaches from CPTED and SCP served as the foundation for this paper's research methodology. Using a deductive research approach, the quantitative research method was deployed to evaluate all of the aforementioned concepts and design approaches. In order to gather information from a random sample size of 320

Fig 3.1: Methodology Flowchart

women from varied socio-economic backgrounds living in different cities across India, the survey was carried out using the positivist technique. Women were requested to answer questions about their perspectives concerning several public spaces they frequently encountered on a daily basis, which addressed a range of SCP and CPTED design factors, such as lighting, ownership, neighborhood ambiance and blind spots, landscaping, public transportation, and a couple of queries about a person's level of fear of crime and their perceptions of crime. For the survey, women from various employment statuses will be volunteering at different public spaces across India. Cities such as Mumbai, Bangalore, Chennai, Coimbatore, Kochi, Trichy, and Nagpur were prioritized. The above mentioned cities were prioritized based on the crime rates in those cities as per NCRB report. Surveys were intended to be conducted in public areas where women tend to congregate in greater numbers. The age range of the targeted respondent was planned to be in between 15 to 55 years. Each survey took place between 7 and 9 a.m. and after 6 p.m., with a planning period of roughly 10 minutes. The survey schedule for the nights was extended to capture the ambience of the public spaces at night, compare foot traffic, and comprehend the perspective of women using those locations.

4. Results and Discussions

Five female surveyors, including a college student, a working woman, and a homemaker, were selected to assist with an offline survey. They performed the survey in a variety of urban points of interest, which comprises a community garden, a mall atrium, a Food Street, vegetable markets, bus stands, transit stops, secondary roads, recreational areas near lakes, and the vicinity outside a college campus. Each survey lasted for about 20 minutes, and it was conducted from 7 to 9.30 am in the morning and after 6 pm in the evening in selected cities like Coimbatore, Bangalore, Mysore, Mumbai and Trichy. A concurrent online survey was conducted using Google Forms for 10 days in the months of July and August, 2023. The

quantitative information from both surveys was examined, and a correlation between the theory and the sample survey's results was found. In addition to the questionnaire survey, an observation survey was conducted to track women's comfort level in using public places at night and their level of dread of doing so. In this survey, women were asked about their experiences using the surrounding region at night. The quantitative survey was responded by 243 women, of which 208 were through an online survey and 35 were through an offline survey. The questionnaire had 24 questions regarding the most used public space, ambience of their neighborhood, fear of crime in public spaces, types of crime that provoke fear, their previous experience of crime, etc. (sample of the questionnaire has been attached). The predominant response was from 20 to 40 years age range, which comprises of college students, self-employed or working women. Over **72% of women** in the survey have experienced the crime in their life, and over **64.8% of women** have fear of crime while using public spaces alone. A question about the different sorts of crime that make women fearful was asked in the survey. Most people were afraid of crimes including sexual assault (49.5%), as well as chain snatching. (Fig: 4.1).

Q. Spaces where you feel safe.

Most of the respondents chose pleasant and well-maintained spaces as their first priority, followed by busy streets, CCTV monitored and well illuminated spaces (Fig : 4.2)

Fig: 4.1 Types of crime included

In the survey, women were asked to rate (out of 5) on how safe they feel in the public space at different period of a day. (Table: 4.2)

Fig: 4.2 Safe spaces as per respondents

Table : 4.2 Public spaces during different period of a day

	Unsafe	Fairly Safe	Moderately safe	Safe	Safest
1. How safe you feel in a public space during day?	0%	1.9%	22.9%	44.8% (108 responses)	30.5%
2. How safe you feel in a public space during night which is crowded?	1%	17.1%	40% (97 responses)	28.6%	13.3%
3. How safe you feel in a public space during night which is lonely?	41.9% (102 responses)	25.7%	19%	8.6%	4.8%
4. How safe you feel to use a public transport during night?	19%	22.9%	25.7% (62 responses)	23.8%	8.6%

Q. Ambience and Blind spots in your neighborhood.

Women addressed that the ambience of most of their neighborhoods (Table: 4.3) were with low lighting, narrow streets, empty grounds and building, unmaintained urban landscapes.

As a result of constant use of such spaces, respondents have took few precautionary measures on their behalf to avoid the uncommon circumstances; this includes the use of tracking system, avoiding visits to lonely places, avoiding night travels, visiting public spaces in groups, awareness about the emergency helplines (Fig : 4.3).

Fig: 4.3 Precautionary Measures

Table: 4.3 Ambience of their Neighborhood

	Bright/Well Lit & busy with human activities	Moderately Bright/Lit & less human activities	Dark & lonely
Ambience of your neighborhood during day time	53.3%	41%	5.7%
Ambience of your neighborhood during night time	17.1%	55.2%	27.6%

In addition to the questions, few women openly expressed their grievances on how difficult it is to use public spaces alone. Some of their perspectives: **Cities are created with a commercial concern and not the liability or the aspects of safety** – Ravina Nafde (56, Self-Employed)

Society should be more trustable and reliable in case of any emergency. People should be more aware and educated about safety measures and emergency contacts - Daarini (21, College Student)

Travelling in a public transport is unsafe for women I believe, so I have never travelled alone in a bus. – Simrat (32, Full time worker)

Women in cities tend to stay away from either chaotic areas with lots of unscrupulous people or isolated, secluded locations with few people (Rai & Rai, 2019).

5. Conclusion

Every member of society deserves a public space where they can be around without worry, reluctance, or fear. Unfortunately, a majority of women experiences disparity and finds it challenging to even travel alone without fear. For an act to occur, it requires an offender who can accomplish his/her thoughts in an appropriate environment over an innocent victim and earn the rewards and motivation to carry the same in other place on another person. This has to be minimized at the policy and planning level by the implementation of preventive measures and creating high-risk scenarios for anomalous behavior. CPTED and SCP models also help in molding the public spaces safer and defensible for everyone.

It is clear that the Broken Window Theory and the quantitative survey's results have a correlation in the area of safe spaces that needs upkeep. Women prioritize cleanliness, comfort, and livability over other factors when choosing a place of visit. Busy streets also help in keen monitoring which makes women to use those streets without hesitation or dread of victimization. Preventive measures of CPTED gets implemented at the neighborhood level which further gets translated by connecting different neighborhoods or communities to minimize the rate of crime in their immediate surroundings.

Fig 5.1: Comparison between the lanes which is dark, narrow, enclosed without any view and a lane which is well lit, open to view without hidden spots. (Taylor Burrell Barnett, 2022)

Fig 5.2: Comparison between the landscape provided in the front yard of the house. Left image has vision lines blocked by landscape whereas the right images has a landscape with clear vision lines between the residence and the approaching road. (Marana & Standards, n.d.)

Fig 5.3: Development of D.B Road, RS Puram, Coimbatore under smart city project has created a lively environment for people to congregate at any time without hesitation or fear of being victimized. (Coimbatore Smart City - Idhu Namma Kovai, n.d.)

Fig 5.2: Urban planning aspects for safer cities

Women between the ages of 20 – 40 years were the predominant respondents to the survey. In the survey, the response from women who were still in a nutshell and were reluctant to visit public settings due to their preconceptions was a limitation. Only the crimes committed in urban areas, such as sexual assaults, molestations, physical assaults, chain snatching, theft, and kidnapping, constituted within the scope of the study. In offline surveys, the sample size dropped due to a lack of time. In the Online survey women from Coimbatore, Bangalore, Chennai, Mysore, Trichy, Kochin, Palakkad, Sharjha, Lucknow, Mumbai, Nagpur and Hosur were the respondents. As a result, the survey was conducted primarily in the southern region of India, which was another significant research restriction.

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“Examining GITAM (Deemed to be University) and Osmania Universities in Hyderabad for Crime Prevention through Environmental Design measures”: A foundation toward a safe CPTED exterior campus model

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ABSTRACT:

Campus violence in India is a significant public health issue that needs to be addressed in the present scenario. It affects the user groups physically and psychologically. As per the Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack (GCPEA) statistical report 2020-21, the total numbers of crime incidents in India is 136, and 2385 harmed members. In depth, the crime rate in Telangana has increased by 4.4% from 2021 to 2022. The paper attempts to highlight various emerging problems in most of the Indian campuses, and as an architect, what has to be adopted while planning for spaces to prevent Crime through Environmental Design (CPTED) in the future is explained. These are achieved by conducting surveys and analyzing based on user's and author's perceptions at Gandhi Institute of Technology and Management (GITAM) and Osmania University (OU) campuses of Hyderabad.

Along with these, secondary data from relevant research papers were obtained, and finally, architectural findings for an exterior safe campus model were formulated. The scope for future research is adopting the mentioned findings in future campuses and checking for crime reduction rates, interior spaces, and mechanical systems for CPTED measures. The result of this paper has important implications for the college authorities in India to find practical solutions and plan student-friendly frameworks to prevent violence on a macro level on campuses.

KEYWORDS: *Campus, GITAM (Deemed to be University), Osmania University, CPTED, Planning, Prevention*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Safety and security problems have always been a challenge in all campus environments. For a place to feel safer, effective use of planning, designing, and detailing can aid in reducing campus crime, along with the fourth element of architecture being “safety and security.”

GITAM (Deemed to University), is a private educational institute in Rudraram village of Hyderabad, designed over 230 acres, located 1.8 kilometers from Mumbai highway, with around 5000 students and more than 500 staff members. Osmania University was established in 1918 and one of the oldest Government campuses in Hyderabad, designed on 1600 acres with 3,00,000 students and 5000 staff members along the metro and other public transport adjacent to the site.

Crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED) is a cost-effective strategy that adopts appropriate landscape designing, fencing, lighting, building positioning, geometry and planning to reduce criminal activity without active measures and comprises of four main principles: Natural surveillance, access control, territorial reinforcement, and space management or maintenance along with geographical juxtaposition as a new theory in CPTED. Elements of CPTED Principles are depicted (Figure 1).

Figure 1A: Revised CPTED Model (Cozens 2016)

Following are the problems identified on a macro level on campuses are:

- Increased crime rate
- Lack of structured and secured parking facilities
- Poor fencing, landscape, and lighting

- Multiple entrances during the day
- Reception area far from main entrances
- Many independent buildings
- Isolated buildings/Occasionally used spaces
- Safety, security not made mandatory in building codes
- Planners' negligence

1.1.CPTED Theory:

C. Ray Jeffery first coined the term “Crime Prevention through Environmental Design.” He posited how thoughtful and effective use of the environment could reduce fear of crime and violence and improve the quality of life for individuals in the environment. Oscar Newman (the First CPTED generator) considered the principles of defensible Space, such as territoriality, natural surveillance, Image and milieu in urban settings to bring the set environment in control of residents to reduce crime opportunities.

First generation CPTED (1960-70): This was first applied in planning urban areas, but its strategies were applied to school campuses as well. It includes the following:

- 1.1.1. **Natural surveillance:** Provides opportunities to see and be seen. Helps in maximizing visibility.
- 1.1.2. **Access control:** Doors, fences, gates, paths, gardens, or any guiding path.
- 1.1.3. **Territoriality reinforcement:** defines ownership and intended use of spaces.
- 1.1.4. **Management and maintenance:** evidence that the Space is cared for.

This provides low-cost methods for improving community security but doesn't address social and interpersonal factors that affect crime and violence.

Second generation CPTED (1980-90): considers neighborhood health and social ecology for prevention. It includes four principles: social cohesion (this includes inclusive activities to create a sense of unity, i.e., territoriality reinforcement), connectivity (situate campus as part of a community to promote connections), threshold capacity (create spaces to ensure balance and multiple usages), community center (social activities that engage members of campus).

Third generation (2000–present): A holistic approach. Considers psychological and emotional factors. Emphasizes inclusivity, sustainability, and deep community needs.

1.2.Crime statistics in Hyderabad:

Figure 2 Crime statistical report (Source: (Hindu, 2022))

Crime rate in Telangana has increased by 4.4% from 2021-22 (Figure 2). Out of which, most are attacks on women and girls and sexual violence. As per the GCPEA Survey report, 55 attacks on students and staff were experienced during education-related protests. (Source: https://protectingeducation.org/wpcontent/uploads/eua_2022_india.pdf).

1.3.CPTED Principles:

- 1.3.1. **Geographical Juxtaposition:** It refers to the capacity of surrounding spaces influencing the safety and security of adjacent areas and vice versa (Newman, 1972). (1972). As per Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack guidelines, new campuses need to be placed in a more secure and accessible location, work with local communities and the new area selected is near a town or village so that it is not isolated. Adequate boundary wall or fences needs to be provided.
- 1.3.2. **Territoriality reinforcement:** Explains transition of zones i.e., public, private, semi-private, and private spaces, for enhancing security. It sends a message of ownership. Examples: Vegetation, fencing, decorative elements, water features, signage, etc.
- 1.3.3. **Natural surveillance:** People can see what others are doing, thereby minimizing the would-be offenders from committing crimes. Examples: Security grilles and doors, Effective lighting and windows, street designing, proper landscaping, CCTV monitoring etc.
- 1.3.4. **Access control:** Helps in denying targeted access. Examples: Bollards, fencing designing, Alarm systems, gates, etc.
- 1.3.5. **Maintenance:** A well-maintained area attracts people and creates a sense of safety and security. Examples: vandal-proof and antiskid materials, Street lighting, Removal of graffiti, etc.

1.4.CPTED Design Considerations:

- 1.4.1. **Entrances:** Entrances that are not visible from the public domain can provide opportunities for felonious people to hide or create violence. a.) Entrances should be at prominent positions. b.) Proper directional signage to be provided. c.) Minimize the number of entry points and provide higher security checks. d.) Natural surveillance must be provided from the streets. e.) Avoid blank walls fronting streets f.) Offices should be planned to face the street activities. g.) Security through RFID Card access into entries post working hours (Figures 3, 4).

Figure 3 Image depicting entrances (Plan, 2014)

Figure 4 Image depicting controlled access through the card (Plan, 2014)

- 1.4.2. **Lighting:** Pedestrian pathways, laneways, and access routes should be lit and adhered to the national lighting code (SP72: 2010) for adequate exterior illumination levels. Lighting should have a wide beam of illumination, which reaches the beam of the next light. Lighting should be designed to recognize the faces of passersby. Lighting should be vandal-tough. Illuminate possible places for intruders to hide. A face should be identifiable from 15m. Energy-efficient lights are to be adopted to save energy. Maintain lighting levels as per Lighting code (Table 1).

Table 1 Recommended values of illuminance and uniform ratio for security lighting (SP7:2010)

Application	Risk Classification	Maintained average horizontal illuminance (lux)	Uniformity ratio E_{min}/E_{av}
Isolated remote strips	Low risk	5	0.15
	Medium risk	10	0.25
	High risk	20	0.25
Close-in strips	Low risk	10	0.25
	Medium risk	20	0.25
	High risk	50	0.30
Waterfront strips	Low risk	10	0.25
	Medium risk	20	0.25
	High risk	50	0.30
Storage zones	Low risk	5	0.15
	Medium risk	10	0.25
	High risk	20	0.25
Entrance zones	All	50	0.30
Traffic zones			
a) Walking	All	5	0.15
b) Traffic	All	10	0.25
Special security fences	High risk	50	0.30

- 1.4.3. **Fencing:** If fencing is too high, natural surveillance of streets becomes difficult; this, in turn, can have larger chances of committing a crime. Front fences should not be higher than 1.2m. A higher fence is acceptable if made of open materials, for

example, wrought iron etc. If noise insulation is required at the building level, use double-glazed glass rather than a high solid fence (Figures 5, 6, 7).

Figure 5 Image depicting boundary wall (Plan, 2014) (left), Image depicting entry points (right)

Figure 6 Boundary wall design (left), Natural surveillance through the boundary wall (right)

Figure 7 Parking zones (1-zoned parking, 2,3- visitors, staff, 4-parent's drop off, 5-bus drop)

1.4.4. **Landscaping:** Trees and shrubs inappropriately located can reduce natural surveillance and can form entrapment spots. Avoid medium-height vegetation with thick cylindrical foliage. Plants with low hedges and high canopied trees with clean trunks are suitable for natural surveillance. Avoid vegetation screening for public toilets. Use green screens to minimize graffiti (Figure 8). Trees should be trimmed up to 2.4m and shrubs not more than 600-750 mm in height. Trees to be away from the building line. Street furniture should be away from building edges.

Figure 8 Ways to eliminate graffiti (Plan, 2014)

- 1.4.5. **Car parking:** Lighting and signage can make parking areas safer. Avoid pedestrian and vehicular movement conflicts. Passive surveillance is to be made possible. Car parks minimize dark areas through proper lighting. Large car parks to adopt telephones, emergency alarms, or intercoms. Appropriate signage at parking is to be adopted. All surfaces at the parking level are to be in light colors to reflect as much light as possible. All entrapment points to be avoided, such as blind corners, under stairs, wide columns, etc., and adequate lighting and mirrors to be provided where design features are unavoidable. These areas need to be accessible and visible to all.
- 1.4.6. **Public areas:** Playgrounds, car parking, or any open spaces should have natural surveillance from building windows. Communal areas like garbage bays to be well-lit and monitored. Elevators or stairwells are to be provided with open style or transparent over doors or walls (Figure 9). Waiting areas need to be visible from building entries. Seating spaces are to be designed to have natural surveillance. Safety barriers needs to be provided for territorial reinforcement in certain spaces (Figure 10).

Figure 9 Transparency of vertical circulation zones (Plan, 2014)

Figure 10 Safety buffer

- 1.4.7. **Blind corners:** Pathways should be direct and straight. Installation of convex mirrors to allow users to see ahead at corners. The installation of glass panels in the stairwell is advisable. If entrapment spots are unavoidable, they need to be well-lit or closed

after hours. Avoid seating near ATMs, phone boxes, toilets, corridors, and isolated locations.

Building geometry: Buildings with U, O, and H profiles result in courtyards protected on three or four sides. Hidden alcoves or entrances serve as concealed areas for criminal activity (Figure 11). To improve visibility, chamfered corners are to be adopted. Administration areas need a clear line of sight of playgrounds, parking, and roads. Central courtyard needs to be made lively with activities for natural surveillance (Figure 12).

Figure 11 Recessed areas alternative solution (Plan, 2014)

Figure 12 Central courtyard made lively ((Plan, 2014)

1.5. Research questions:

- Amongst various building types, which type has a huge population and the highest probability of crime occurrences?
- As an architect, what can be done at the planning level to reduce the crime rate (PROACTIVE APPROACH)?
- How can future campuses benefit from this paper?
- How can campus blind spots be avoided while planning?
- What is the need for making CPTED Measures mandatory in Building by-laws?

2. METHODOLOGY:

Challenges faced during the survey: To deal with the fear of feeling safe at campus level. To obtain genuine and fearless opinions, names and other details were not asked for.

3. RESULTS:

3.1.GITAM UNIVERSITY SURVEY RESULTS:

		Respondent 1	Respondent 2	Respondent 3	Respondent 4	Respondent 5	Respondent 6	Respondent 7	Respondent 8	Average
GEOGRAPHICAL JUXTAPOSITION	How's the placement of campus?	100%	75%	50%	0%	0%	100%	50%	50%	70.83333333
GEOGRAPHICAL JUXTAPOSITION	How comfortable do you feel being in the campus?	100%	100%	50%	50%	75%	100%	50%	50%	71.875
MAINTENANCE	Does the campus lighting evenly illuminate the area?	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	Do trees/bushes obscure lighting?	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	96.875
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	Are you able to identify any face 25 meters away?	100%	50%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	83.33333333
ACCESS CONTROL	Does lighting illuminate direction signs or maps?	0%	0%	50%	50%	100%	0%	50%	50%	60
MAINTENANCE	Are there any signages? If so, do they show how to seek emergency assistance?	0%	0%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%	100
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	Are there any hiding spaces? Do landscaping block sightlines?	100%	0%	100%	100%	0%	100%	100%	100%	100
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	Is it easy to predict when will people be around?	100%	100%	0%	100%	100%	100%	0%	0%	100
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	How far is the nearest person to call for help?	0%	25%	100%	100%	25%	0%	100%	100%	75
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	Is the area designed for natural surveillance?	100%	100%	100%	100%	0%	100%	100%	100%	100
TERRITORIALITY	How easy would it be for an offender to disappear?	25%	25%	100%	0%	0%	25%	100%	100%	62.5
TERRITORIALITY	Is there more than one exit?	100%	100%	0%	0%	100%	100%	0%	0%	100
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	Are there any activities post college timings? If so, does these levels provide passive surveillance?	0%	100%	0%	0%	100%	0%	0%	0%	100
TERRITORIALITY	Does the place feel cared for?	0%	100%	0%	0%	50%	0%	0%	0%	75
TERRITORIALITY	Is the site clearly defined? Is there any definition between public and private space?	0%	0%	100%	100%	100%	0%	100%	100%	100

		Respondent 1	Respondent 2	Respondent 3	Average
TERRITORIALITY	1. I feel safe while walking to and from my vehicle in the parking ramp	0%	75%	100%	88%
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	2. I think it's possible for offenders to hide in parking area	100%	0%	0%	100%
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	3. I think it's possible for offenders to hide within landscape	100%	0%	0%	100%
	4. Parking ramp is well lit	0%	25%	0%	25%
ACCESS CONTROL	5. I feel safe using stairs anytime	0%	100%	50%	75%
ACCESS CONTROL	6. I feel safe using elevators.	0%	100%	100%	100%
ACCESS CONTROL	7. I feel that my car may be vandalized anytime	100%	100%	75%	92%
ACCESS CONTROL	8. My car or bike has been vandalized before	100%	0%	0%	100%
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	9. If you were being threatened, do you think other people would notice you?	0%	100%	75%	88%

NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	10. Do you think people would assist you if they noticed a crime taking place	0%	50%	0%	50%
ACCESS CONTROL	11. Are properties protected with security systems?	50%	25%	25%	33%
MAINTENANCE	12. Are security systems functioning and people aware of?	0%	25%	50%	38%
TERRITORIALITY	13. Is the campus free from places where criminals could hide?	0%	75%	75%	75%
MAINTENANCE	14. Is campus clean from rubbish/graffiti?	50%	100%	50%	66%
MAINTENANCE	15. Is the area free from nuisance activities	0%	100%	75%	88%
ACCESS CONTROL	16. I worry about my personal safety at campus	0%	0%	25%	25%
TERRITORIALITY	17. I feel safe going anywhere around campus in dark/daytime	0%	100%	75%	88%
TERRITORIALITY	18. Is way finding easy in the campus?	0%	25%	0%	25%

NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	ACCESS CONTROL	TERRITORIALITY	TERRITORIALITY	TERRITORIALITY	ACCESS CONTROL	ACCESS CONTROL	MAINTENANCE	ACCESS CONTROL
If you were being threatened on campus, do you think other people would notice you?	Do you think people would assist you if they noticed a crime taking place inside campus?	Are properties protected with security systems?	Is the campus free from places where criminals could hide?	Are there any blind spots in campus?	I feel safe going anywhere around campus in dark/daytime	How is lighting at campus level?	Do you think biometric access or access control alone will stop outsiders from entering	Are there graffiti walls inside the campus?	Do you feel safe leaving your vehicles at the parking area?
75%	50%	75%	25%	100%	50%	75%	25%	100%	100%
75%	50%	75%	25%	100%	50%	75%	25%	100%	100%
50%	50%	25%	25%	100%	25%	75%	25%	100%	100%
75%	50%	25%	25%	100%	50%	75%	25%	100%	100%

TERRITORIALITY	TERRITORIALITY	NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	TERRITORIALITY	TERRITORIALITY	ACCESS CONTROL	TERRITORIALITY	GEOGRAPHICAL JUXTAPOSITION
Are public, semipublic, private zones separated on site?	Do you feel safe at mess zones?	Can users inside the building, from windows can monitor the on street activities?	Do you feel having scattered buildings in campus planning is better than a standalone one?	Is wayfinding easy in the campus?if no, why?	Have you observed any outsiders been allowed inside the campus in spite of having security	Any other issues faced in terms of safety in and around the campus?	Do you feel campuses centrally placed in the city or adjacent to main accessible busy routes or far from the main busy roads is better ?
100%	100%	50%	100%	0%	100%	0%	AWAY
100%	100%	50%	50%	0%	100%	0%	CITY CENTRE
0%	100%	50%	0%	0%	100%	0%	CITY CENTRE
100%	100%	50%	50%	0%	100%	0%	CITY CENTRE

(Source: Author)

Figure 13 At Landscape area (left), In front of the library (right)

Figure 14 Ground floor level (left), under central courtyard ramp (right)

Figure 15 Under the central courtyard ramp (daytime) (left), In front of F block (blind spots zone)(right)

Figure 16 Landscape area at the rear side of the campus (left), Space between canteens (right)

Figure 17 In front of A, H blocks and ATM, canteens (left), Parking nighttime (Right)

Figure 18 Parking daytime (left), Boundary wall with mesh (right)

Figure 19 Entrapment spot under staircases (left), Street level, and building level connectivity (Right)

(Source: Author)

3.2.OSMANIA UNIVERSITY SURVEY RESULTS:

Figure 21 Image depicting blind spots at Osmania University (Source: Google map)

NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	ACCESS CONTROL	TERRITORIALITY	TERRITORIALITY	TERRITORIALITY	ACCESS CONTROL	ACCESS CONTROL	MAINTENANCE	ACCESS CONTROL	TERRITORIALITY
If you were being threatened on campus, do you think other people would notice you?	Do you think people would assist you if they noticed a crime taking place inside campus?	Are properties protected with security systems?	Is the campus free from places where criminals could hide?	Are there any blind spots in campus?	If feel safe going anywhere around campus in dark/daytime	How is lighting at campus level?	Do you think bio metric access or access control alone will stop outsiders from entering into campus?	Are there graffitti walls inside the campus?	Do you feel safe leaving your vehicles at the parking area?	Are public, semipublic, private zones seperated on site?
100%	75%	50%	25%	75%	75%	50%	50%	0%	100%	100%
75%	100%	75%	25%	75%	25%	50%	75%	0%	100%	100%
0%	100%	0%	100%	100%	50%	100%	25%	100%	100%	0%
50%	75%	75%	75%	50%	75%	50%	75%	0%	100%	100%
75%	75%	75%	50%	75%	25%	100%	75%	0%	100%	0%
100%	100%	75%		50%	75%	50%	75%	0%	100%	100%
75%	50%	50%	25%	100%	50%	50%	50%	100%	100%	100%
75%	50%	75%	75%	25%	75%	50%	50%	100%	100%	100%
75%	75%	75%	50%	50%	75%	100%	25%	0%	100%	100%
50%	75%	50%	25%	100%	25%	50%	25%	100%	100%	100%
75%	75%	75%	25%	25%	75%	50%	75%	0%	100%	100%
75%	50%	50%	75%	75%	25%	0%	100%	0%	100%	0%
69%	75%	60%	50%	67%	54%	58%	58%	33%	100%	73%

(Source: Author)

TERRITORIALITY	NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	TERRITORIALITY	TERRITORIALITY	ACCESS CONTROL	TERRITORIALITY	GEOGRAPHICAL JUXTAPOSITION
Do you feel safe at mess zones?	Can users inside the building, from windows can monitor the on street activities?	Do you feel having scattered buildings in campus planning is better than a standalone one?	Is wayfinding easy in the campus?if no, why?	Have you observed any outsiders been allowed inside the campus in spite of having security	Any other issues faced in terms of safety in and around the campus?	Do you feel campuses centrally placed in the city or adjacent to main accessible busy routes or far from the main busy roads is better ?
100%	100%	0%	100%	100%. Lot of Outsiders enter the campus premises	Being a semi closed campus. There are some safety issues on campus. If it were a closed campus lots of these could be avoided.	Main accessible busy routes is better.
100%	50%	50%	100%	100%		0%
100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	0%ne that I k0%w of	100%
100%	50%	50%	100%	50%	Zomato and Swizzy persons are 0%t feeling comfortable	all have their own positives and negatives
100%	0%	50%	100%..	50%	0% other issue	Yes
100%	100%	0%	100%	0%	0%	It is far from the main road and city
100%	50%	0%	0%	100%	0%t that I k0%w of	100%
100%	0%	0%	100%	0% I didn't observed any outsiders allowed into the campus	0%o	Adjacent to the main city
100%	50%	100%	100%	100%	Students are scared of dogs and some private people inside the campus	100%
100%	50%	100%	0%	100%	0%	Adjacent to main accessible busy routes
100%	0%					
0%	50%	100%	0%	100%	dogs are increasing, one of my classmates was bitten in the campus by a dog	centrally placed in city
92%	50%	50%	78%	78%	0%	75%

(Source: Author)

Figure 20 Osmania University images day and night time

(Source: Google images)

Findings from the survey report:

GITAM University: As per users, the campus location could have been optimized, Trees /bushes obscure lighting, Difficulty in identifying faces above 25m distance, lack of signage's, lighting, easy for an offender to disappear, unsafe parking areas, lack of safety at the staircases, higher chances of vandalism, less functioning of few security systems, lack of proper way finding, low monitoring of street activities, blind spots (Figures 13 to 19).

Osmania University: Less functioning of security systems, blind spots, lack of safety on campus, lack of zoning, lack of safety, on-street activities cannot be monitored from windows, users not comfortable having scattered buildings, way finding not easy, intrusion of outsiders despite of security at entrances, entry of dogs harming users, users feel campuses to be accessible to public transportation and in City Centre (Figure 20).

4. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS:

CPTED PRINCIPLES	Literature study	GITAM UNIVERSITY	OSMANIA UNIVERSITY	RECOMMENDATIONS/FINDINGS
GEOGRAPHICAL JUXTAPOSITION	As per Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack guidelines, new campuses needs to be placed in a more secure and accessible location, work with local communities, the new area selected is near a ton or village so that it is not isolated. Adequate boundary wall or fences needs to be provided.	Inappropriate location of the campus as per users due to lack of accessibility to public transportation.	Users feel campuses to be accessible to public transportation and in city Centre. Users not comfortable having scattered buildings	Site for new campuses to be chosen in City center/ connected to an unisolated town or village with all accessible public utilities for users. Work with local communities for the placement of campus to reduce crime.
TERRITORIAL REINFORCEMENT	Transition of zones i.e. Public, private, semi- private and private spaces for enhancing security. It sends a message of ownership. Example: Vegetation, fencing, decorative elements, water features, signage etc.	Easy for an offender to disappear. Lack of proper way finding	Way finding not easy. Entry of dogs harming users	Site level zoning needs to be done along with way finding. Boundaries to be constructed of strong materials like wrought iron or combination of solid wall with fence on top to reduce outsider's entry.
NATURAL SURVEILLANCE	People can see what others are doing, thereby minimizing the would-be offenders from committing crime. Examples: Security grilles and doors, Effective lighting and windows, street designing, Proper landscaping, CCTV monitoring etc. Buildings with U, O and H profiles result in courtyards protected on three or four sides. Hidden alcoves or entrances, serves as concealed areas for criminal activity. To improve visibility, chamfered corners are to be adopted. Administration areas need to have clear line of sight of playground, parking and roads. Pedestrian pathways, laneways, and access routes should be lit adhered to the national lighting code (SP72: 2010) for adequate exterior illumination levels. Plants with low hedges and high canopied trees with clean trunks are suitable for natural surveillance. Trees should be trimmed upto 2.4m and shrubs not more than 600-750mm in height. Trees to be away from the building line. Street furniture should be away from building edges. Playgrounds or car parking, or any open spaces should have natural surveillance from building windows. Elevators or stairwells are to be provided with open style or transparent over doors or walls. If entrapment spots are unavoidable, need to be well lit or closed after hours. Avoid seating near atms, phone boxes, toilets, corridors, and isolated locations.	Trees /bushes obscure lighting, Difficulty in identifying face above 25m distance, unsafe parking areas, lack of safety at staircase. Low monitoring of users of street activity, blind spots.	Blind spots, lack of safety in campus, , on street activities cannot be monitored from windows. , intrusion of outsiders inspite of security at entrances	Building geometry to be O,U or H shaped and make sure the orientation of building geometry promotes natural surveillance. Windows needs to be designed in such a manner that street activities and parking spaces are visually accessible. Blind spots to be avoided through building geometry and entrapment spots under staircases needs to be covered. Hidden alcoves or any entrances designed with recessed entry needs to be chamfered at corners. Playgrounds needs to be accessible from all sides of the building or at least the administration areas. Administration areas need to be planned at the perimeter of building. Trees trimmed till height 2.4m and shrubs not more than 600-750mm in height needs to be chosen and to be planned away from the building line. Street lighting level of at least 5 lux needs to be maintained as per SP7:2010 code. Sp72:2010

CPTED PRINCIPLES	Literature study	GITAM UNIVERSITY	OSMANIA UNIVERSITY	RECOMMENDATIONS/FINDINGS
ACCESS CONTROL	Helps in denying targeted access. Examples: Bollards, fencing designing, Alarm systems, gates, etc. A.) Entrances should be at prominent positions b.) Proper directional signage to be provided c.) Minimize the number of entry points and provide higher security checks d.) Natural surveillance must be provided from streets e.) Avoid blank walls fronting streets f.) Offices should be planned to face the street activities g.) Security through RFID Card access into entries post working hours. Front fences should not be higher than 1.2m. All entrapment points to be avoided such as blind corners, under stairs, wide columns etc. Adequate lighting and mirrors to be provided where design features are unavoidable	Less functioning of security systems	Less functioning of security systems	Way finding to be made easier through planning. Number of entry points to be minimized to not more than 4 depending upon the scale of the site and accessibility. Zoning to be done properly based on public, semipublic and private zones. Areas not in use after college hours need to be closed either with mesh or any other fencing to restrict users access.
MAINTENANCE	A well-maintained area attracts people and creates a sense of safety and security. Examples: vandal-proof and antiskid materials, Street lighting, Remove graffiti ,etc.	Higher chances of vandalism	Graffiti observed in few areas i.e., hostels	Graffiti needs to be reduced and green walls can be proposed to avoid graffiti and thereby aesthetically appears pleasing.

Figure 22 Image depicting CPTED design solutions at GITAM Campus for exterior campus (Source: Author)

5. DISCUSSION:

To obtain an exterior safe campus model, the following are the changes that need to be adopted: Site for new campuses to be chosen in the City center/ connected to an unisolated town or village with all accessible public utilities for users. Work with local communities for the placement of campus to reduce crime. Site-level zoning needs to be done along with way-finding. Boundaries to be constructed of strong materials like wrought iron or a combination of solid walls with a fence on top to reduce outsider's entry. Building geometry to be O, U, or H shaped and make sure the orientation of building geometry promotes natural surveillance. Windows need to be designed in such a manner that street activities and parking spaces are visually accessible. Blind spots are to be avoided through building geometry, and entrapment spots under staircases need to be covered. Hidden alcoves or any entrances designed with recessed entry need to be chamfered at corners. Playgrounds need to be accessible from all sides of the building or at least the administration areas. Administration areas need to be planned at the perimeter of the building. Trees trimmed to a height of 2.4m and shrubs not more than 600-750mm in height need to be chosen and to be planned away from the building line. Street lighting level of at least 5 lux needs to be maintained as per SP72:2010 code. Way finding to be made easier through planning. The number of entry points to be minimized to not more than depending upon the scale of the site and accessibility. Zoning to be done properly based on public, semipublic, and private zones. Areas not in use after college, hours need to be closed either with mesh or any other fencing to restrict user access. Graffiti needs to be reduced, and green walls can be proposed to avoid graffiti and thereby aesthetically appear pleasing. Above mentioned are CPTED recommendations for future campus planning models. The above-mentioned optimum strategies are for a safe exterior campus model. The scope for future research is a detailed interior study and mechanical systems of campuses, such as Lobbies, reception areas, staircases, ramps, administrative areas, corridors, toilets, HVACs, fire control, surveillance systems, and elevators.

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Evaluating the parameter of visibility adopted for CPTED for user safety in public open space of Haat Bazar: Isovist and VGA

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Theme

Original Research Paper

Abstract

Public open spaces (POS) are an indispensable part of a well-functioning city that humanize urban areas. However, whether an individual will utilize the space, or shy away from it, depends on the individual's perception of an area in terms of safety. The driving force that governs the safety of users in urban POS is the parameter of visibility. Enhanced visibility reduces the fear of crime through natural surveillance, which is one of seven first-generation CPTED Concepts. This study aimed to explore the effectiveness of Isovist and Visibility Graph Analysis (VGA) in evaluating the parameter of visibility for user safety in the public

open space of Haat bazaar. For this purpose, Dilli Haat INA and Dilli Haat Janakpuri were identified as the most suitable study areas. These case study sites were analyzed under three main heads: 1. Archival review of crime records and architectural case studies to help identify the area of interest, 2. Layout study using Isovist and VGA tools for analysis, and 3. Surveys conducted in regular summer, regular winter, and in the festive season for each of the sites. The comparative analysis of the outputs from these three heads showed that Isovist and VGA can be used as a way of evaluating the visibility based on real-time vision and human-based vision respectively. Although this paper is limited to only one typology of POS, this exploratory research has achieved new insights into visibility as a parameter of user safety for CPTED.

Keywords: *CPTED, Haat bazar, User safety, Isovist, Visibility graph analysis (VGA)*

Highlights/ Relevance: The role of security in Maslow's hierarchy of needs and SDG targets 11.7, 16.1, 16.5 underline exigency of CPTED in POS. The use of Isovist and VGA for evaluating visibility based on real-time and human-based vision respectively may motivate formation of a toolkit for urban designers to design defensible spaces.

1. Introduction

Public open spaces (POS) are an indispensable part of a well-functioning city that humanize the urban areas. However, whether an individual will utilize the space, or shy away from it, depends on the individual's perception of an area in terms of safety. Every 51 minutes, there is a case of female harassment in a POS of India (Bhattacharyya, 2016). As per the National Crime Records Bureau, there was a stark 19.7% increase in cases of crime against females, reaching 0.406 million as of 2019 within 3 years (NCRB, 2016; NCRB, 2019). Cases of crime and the fright of harassment hinder a female's access to the POS and subsequently, their right to the city, setting about an emotion of detachment (Beebeejaun, 2017; Bhattacharyya, 2016; Harvey, 2012; Koskela, 1997; Mahadevia, Mishra, et al., 2016; Mehta, 2014). As per India's National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), the national capital Delhi has a rate of 1,306 IPC crimes for every 1 lakh population in 2017. The national capital stands on top of the crime rate chart for abductions and kidnappings with a crime rate of 32. This study primarily explored the POS of Haat bazaar in Delhi, though the crimes can occur at any location- be it a built or an open space.

Aim, objectives and scope

The aim of the study was to explore the effectiveness of Isovist and Visibility Graph Analysis (VGA) in evaluating the parameter of visibility of CPTED for user safety in the public open space of Haat bazaar.

The specific objectives of the study include:

1. To study the public spaces of urban Haat bazaars of Delhi.
2. To analyze the data on the safety of users in Haat Bazaars of Delhi.
3. To explore the parameter of visibility to promote safety of users in Haat bazaars.
4. To explore the effectiveness of Isovist and VGA as a way of evaluating the visibility.

The scope of the study is limited to the Public Open Spaces of urban Haat bazaars of Delhi. As this study was part of academic dissertation with time schedule, the survey sample size was confined to only 5% of the total footfall.

2. Literature review

Othman, F. et al. (2019) investigated how visual analysis techniques of Isovists can be employed to promote safe spaces using several strategies to evaluate visibility along movement patterns, including GIS, Isovist analysis, DEM, Point cloud from LiDAR, View dome tool, and statistical data comparison. The suggested methods demonstrated the capability to extract significant spatial and topological information in both 2D and 3D environments, offering valuable insights into enhancing safe spaces. Hillier B., et al. identified three ways in which space syntax methods can be applied to the study of natural landscapes: attributing attributes to spatial units (nodes in the graph representation), attributing attributes to relationships between spatial units (edges in the graph), and the use of multi-layered graphs. Knöll, M., et al. investigated how selected properties commonly used in space syntax research relate to users' ratings of stress and spatial qualities in open public spaces. The study involved extracting syntactical properties from previous literature and combining this data with city dwellers' ratings of open public spaces concerning stress perception and urban design qualities. The findings indicated a weak relation between vertices' density in an open public space's Isovist and participants' safety ratings. Line-based measures, such as global and city-wide integration, were identified as potentially valid measures for analyzing stress perception in outdoor spaces. Turner A. et al. explored how syntactic analysis of Isovists complements existing space syntax methodology, particularly in automatically generating integration values from 3D CAD models. Gupta, R in his study aimed to determine whether the spatial distribution of crime could be employed to identify areas at a higher risk of criminal activity. It utilized crime data from the Delhi Police and analyzed it using space syntax integration, GIS, and GPS techniques to identify spatial crime patterns. The findings revealed that crime hotspots tend to concentrate in areas characterized by low integration, suggesting the potential for using spatial analysis to identify and mitigate crime risk in urban environments.

3. Methodology

An evaluative research approach was adopted for conducting the study. Dilli Haat INA and Dilli Haat Janakpuri were identified as most suitable sites for conducting this study. Conducting a CPTED study on Dilli Haats is justified for several compelling reasons. These open-air markets in Delhi, known for their unique architectural and cultural features, attract a diverse array of visitors, making public safety a top priority. Assessing how the design elements impact safety can reveal opportunities to enhance security without compromising cultural significance. Moreover, Dilli Haats are vital to tourism and the local economy, so improving safety can attract more visitors, boosting economic growth. Additionally, creating a safer environment contributes to the well-being of the community by enhancing the quality of life for residents and visitors. These case study sites were analyzed under three main heads: 1. Archival review of crime records and architectural case studies to help to identify the area of interest, 2. Surveys conducted in regular summer, regular winter, and in the festive season for each of these sites and 3. Layout study using Isovist and VGA tools for analysis. The outputs from these three heads were compared to test the reliability of the methods used and the results obtained. Further critical evaluation and analysis was done to draw conclusions and suggest future scope of the research.

Figure 1: Schematic representation

3.1 Technologies used

3.1.1 Crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED)

CPTED, which stands for Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design, is a way of using the design and layout of our surroundings to stop criminal behavior. Seven key CPTED concepts include: territoriality, surveillance (informal and formal), access control, image/maintenance, activity programme support, target hardening and geographical juxtaposition. Some researchers, like Fisher and Nasar (1992), talk about three types of things in CPTED: places where you can see everything, places where people can hide, and ways for people to get away. Taylor and Harrell (1996) say that people are more afraid of crime in places where criminals can hide easily but it's hard for others to see or escape from. Through optimizing the visibility of spaces, it becomes possible to deter criminal activities.

Space Syntax

Space syntax is an analytical framework rooted in architectural and urban studies that aims to comprehend the relationships between spatial configurations and human behavior within the built environment. It is based on how the layout and connectivity of spaces (visibility patterns, circulation, and spatial organization) quantitatively influence people's interaction & perception of their surroundings.

The selection of the Isovist/VGA tool was done based on the following comparative analysis.

Table 1: Selection of tool

ANALYSING THE PUBLIC OPEN SPACE FOR SAFETY					
TOOLS ►	Convex Space	Axial Space	View Dome Tool	Point cloud from LiDAR	Isovist/ VGA
FACTORS ▼					
3 Dimensional Space Analysis	✘	✔	✔	✔	✘
Can Be used at Designing Phase for exploration of various options	✔	✔	✔	✘	✔
Autocad files can be imported	✔	✔	✔	✘	✔
Appropriate for exterior spaces	✘	✔	✔	✔	✔
360 degree field of view	✔	✘	✔	✔	✔
Type of analysis	✘ Link analysis	! Linear Visibility	✔ Visibility	✘ Model Generation	✔ Visibility
Open Source Software	✔	✔	✘	✔	✔

Isovists, a tool of space syntax, represents a specific point's location within an enclosed polygonal space and the three-dimensional volume of space visible from that point (Benedikt, 1979; Weitkamp, 2011). Isovist/VGA can be used at the designing phase for exploration of various options and finding out the option with highest values of natural surveillance. It also offers other benefits such as 360 degree field of view, appropriate for exterior spaces and an open source software where AutoCAD files can also be imported.

The integration of Isovist analysis into Geographic Information Systems (GIS) having abundant availability of geo-referenced data and visualization tools enhances visibility analysis from a human perspective. This integration involves utilizing undirected graphs to connect all visible points within a human-scale grid creating a robust framework to tackle crucial challenges concerning the interplay between the built environment and human behavior, particularly in terms of safety considerations. Hence, Isovist/VGA has been selected as the most appropriate tool for the purpose of the study.

3.2 Process of data collection

The survey was conducted at 2 locations- 1. Delhi haat INA- located in Kidwai nagar, opposite INA market, New Delhi with a site area of 6 acres and 2. Delhi Haat Janakpuri, located in Lal Sai Mandir Marg, Virender Nagar, Janakpuri, New Delhi with a site area of 8 acres. Average daily footfall in Dilli Haat, INA and Janakpuri is 3000 and 1000 respectively as per Delhi tourism records for the year 2021. 5% of the average footfall of the two Haats i.e., 100 was taken as the sample size. Only visitors within the age group of 7 to 65 years were surveyed as per the inclusion criteria. The duration of the data collection was one year. The surveys were conducted in summer, winter and on festive days.

Questionnaire and Space syntax were used for data collection.

The questionnaire consisted of 14 questions. Part 1 dealt with demographic variables such as gender, age, education, etc. and Part 2 dealt with safety of the people using the POS of Haats. Likert Scale was used to measure the survey responses in the form of a number of ratings, which were further analyzed as bar and pie charts. Likert scale helped measure the safety of the people in the haat. A score of 5 is given for highest safety and a score of 1 is given for lowest safety.

Isovist- a type of space syntax and VGA- a GIS based tool, were used as tools to analyze why people perceive places differently, why certain places are more meaningful, and some can easily be forgotten i.e. human perception in built environment. It is one of the most popular way analyzing the field of view from a particular point in a built environment.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Dilli Haat INA

4.1.1 Layout study

Constructed in 1993 under Delhi Tourism and Municipal Corporation of Delhi, Dilli Haat INA situated in Kidwai Nagar, opposite INA market, New Delhi is a popular tourist destination and one of the most visited shopping complexes in South Delhi. Covering a site area of 6 acres, it has approximately 12% ground coverage and a built-up area of 3190 sq.m. The figures below represent the layout study under various heads as per figure 1.

Figure 2: Activity based zoning plan

Figure 3: Built-open Relationship

Figure 4: Temporary/ permanent structures

Figure 5: Circulation pattern

Figure 6: Lighting

4.1.2 Isovist and Visibility Graph Analysis

The Visibility Graph Analysis of the axial map of Dilli Haat INA showed that the street corresponding to the first half of the central spine from the entrance had the highest values of

visibility but comparatively smaller values of integration to the overall system. This is by virtue of its linear character which supports its function as a shopping street. In comparison, the latter half of the central spine with a nearer value in visibility has very high value of integration as it is well integrated into the network of food zones on both sides. The food zones that flank as networks on both sides of the spine after the roundabout has a medium level of visual connectivity and integration. The lowermost portion of the site has lesser integration levels due to its visual discontinuity. This is visible through in-situ observation. Space syntax tools further reveal the underlying properties of the spatial configuration of Dilli Haat.

Figure 7: VGA of Dilli Haat INA

4.1.3 Questionnaire survey

A survey was conducted to assess the safety perception of people at the haat. The results showed that people feel most safe in the afternoon (56%) and least safe at 10:30 PM (27%). They also feel safer during 7 PM in summer (52%) than in winter (45%). People feel safer on regular days (70%) than on festive days (60%).

In terms of location, people feel most safe in front of shops (70%) and least safe in voids and toilets (49%). Public visibility is insufficient for 30% of the population. The night lighting of the haat is neutrally safe and sufficient for 54% of the people, while 27% think it is unsafe. The public toilets of the Haat are neutrally safe for 59% of the people, but 40% feel unsafe. The pedestrian pathways in the Haats are safe and clear for 54% of the people.

The survey also found that 81.4% of the people have no idea regarding lost/found provision in the haat. Additionally, 45.5% of the people feel that the haat is unsafe for children. 70% of people feel most safe at the entrance and least safe at the end (57%).

4.2 Dilli Haat Janakpuri

4.2.1 Layout Study

Constructed in 2014 under Delhi Tourism and Municipal Corporation of Delhi, Dilli Haat Janakpuri is situated in Lal Sai Mandir Marg, Virender Nagar, Janakpuri, New Delhi. Covering a site area of 9.6 acres, it has approximately 27.8% ground coverage and a built-up area of 9028 sq.m. The underlying layer that bonded the overall program of formal and

informal shops was its “rhythmic heartbeat concept”. The figures below represent the layout study under various heads as per figure 1.

Figure 8: Activity based zoning plan

Figure 9: Built-open Relationship

Figure 10: Temporary/permanent structures

Figure 11: Circulation pattern

4.2.2 Isovist and Visibility Graph Analysis

The visibility analysis of the Dilli Haat Janakpuri plan shows that the street corresponding to the entrance has high values of visual connectivity and integration to the overall system. In comparison, the latter half of the central spine, with a lower visibility value, is poorly connected to the network of food zones. The rear end of the haat has the lowest values of visibility. The canopy structures further lower the visual connectivity values. The toilets have lesser integration levels due to their visual discontinuity. This is visible through observation. Space syntax tools further reveal how urban spaces and their configurations can translate into positive public value.

Figure 13: VGA of Dilli Haat Janakpuri

4.2.3 Survey

The results showed that people feel most safe from morning to evening (54%) and least safe during late hours after 6:30 PM (37%). They also feel safer around 7 PM in summer (59%) than in winter (41%). People feel safer on festive days (78%) than on regular days (50%).

In terms of location, 48% people feel safe in front of the shops and 37% feel safe in front of the voids, empty spaces and toilets. The public visibility of the entire haat is safe for 60% of the people. However, 59% of the people feel that the night lighting of the haat is not sufficient in terms of safety of women and children. The public toilets of the Haat are not safe for 60% of the people. The pedestrian pathways in the haats are safe and clear for 45% of the people.

The survey also found that 86.4% of the people have no idea regarding lost/found provision in the haat. Additionally, 40% of the people feel that the haat is safe for children and 27%

feels that it is not safe. 70% of people feel most safe at the entrance and least safe at the end (42%).

4.3 Implications

The data from the survey conducted at Dilli Haat reveals several important quantitative impact relationships related to safety, visitor perceptions, and areas for improvement. Firstly, there is a clear correlation between the time of day and people's sense of safety. The majority (56-63%) feel most safe during the morning to evening hours, while a significant portion (27-37%) feels least safe during late hours after 6:30 PM. This indicates that the perception of safety is strongly influenced by the time of day. Secondly, seasonal variation also impacts safety perceptions. People feel safer during the summer evening hours (59%) compared to winter (41%). This suggests that not only weather conditions and seasonal changes can affect how visitors perceive safety, but their perception is also mostly linked to daylighting. Furthermore, mostly users prefer evenings and mornings for visiting POS in summer due to the harsh sun of daytime, which means that during evening hours there is a higher footfall in Dilli Haat. Although during the winters the evenings are much colder, people prefer to visit POS during the day when the sun is up. This strongly implies that people's perception of safety is directly linked with footfall and, hence, natural surveillance. Thirdly, the location within Dilli Haat plays a crucial role in safety perceptions. Visitors feel most safe in front of the shops (63%) but least safe in front of voids, empty spaces, and toilets (83%). Additionally, the entrance is perceived as the safest (67%), while the end is considered the least safe (33%). This highlights the importance of well-lit and well-monitored areas within the market.

In addition, the type of day, whether it's a festive day or a regular day, also influences safety perceptions. More people (56%) feel safer on festive days compared to regular days (44%) in Dilli Haat Janakpuri where the footfall is usually very low, while more people (67%) feel safer on regular days compared to festive days (33%) in Dilli Haat INA where footfall is usually on the higher end. This demonstrates that special events and festivals attract the users into public spaces, hence increasing the natural surveillance, as seen in Dilli Haat Janakpuri. Interestingly, while natural surveillance is essential for the perception of safety, this natural surveillance reduces when there is overcrowding, as seen in the example of INA. Moreover, there is a significant concern regarding night lighting and public toilets, with 59% feeling that they are not safe. This underscores the need for improved lighting and security measures around these facilities.

The quantitative impact relationships between safety perceptions, time of day, season, type of day, location, and awareness of services at Dilli Haat suggest that there are some safety concerns at the haat, especially for women and children.

Figure 14: Findings and implications

The study further highlighted several key issues identified at Dilli Haat, along with their corresponding problems and potential solutions. Late-hour safety concerns are prevalent, marked by insufficient lighting, overcrowding, and inappropriate behavior. To address these issues, it is crucial to increase police patrolling and the presence of security guards to ensure the safety of visitors during extended hours of operation. Moreover, the insufficient public visibility in certain areas of the venue poses a challenge, resulting in fewer eyes on the street. To rectify this, Dilli Haat management should consider utilizing unused areas for activities that attract visitors, thus enhancing overall public visibility.

Another significant issue revolves around the safety of areas around the restrooms, which are often perceived as least active zones due to inadequate night lighting and insufficient cleaning. To mitigate this concern, Dilli Haat should allocate regular cleaning staff and security guards to maintain a safe and hygienic environment around the toilets. Additionally, the average-conditioned pathways within the market can lead to tripping and bumping incidents. To address this, regular maintenance of the pathways and enhancing their visibility, particularly in areas with level differences, is essential.

Lastly, the issue of inefficient signage contributes to user unawareness of available public facilities within Dilli Haat. To enhance visitor convenience, visible signages should be strategically placed at proper intervals throughout the venue, providing clear guidance and information on the location of essential facilities. In summary, addressing these identified issues through the proposed solutions will help Dilli Haat maintain its status as a vibrant cultural hub while ensuring the safety, visibility, and accessibility of the space for all visitors.

5. Recommendations

- Increase the number of guards and police patrolling in POS
- Usage of performances to engage more public
- Provision of performance areas in front of eateries,
- Closure of the rear entrance
- Provision of slot wise entry to limit the crowd,
- Installation of CCTV cameras and loudspeakers,
- Installation of Fog lights, Radiating and Moving lights
- Provision of regular cleaning staff and stationed guards around the toilets
- Well-placed Signages at appropriate intervals throughout the premises.

6. Conclusions

The comparative analysis of the outputs from these layout study, VGA analysis and questionnaire surveys showed that Isovist and VGA can be used as a way of evaluating the visibility based on real-time vision and human-based vision respectively. Although this paper is limited to only one typology of POS, this exploratory research has achieved new insights into visibility as a parameter of user safety for CPTED.

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Fear Factors in Open Spaces – Children’s Perception of Public Open Spaces

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ABSTRACT

The world is undergoing rapid urbanization, and it is presumed that by 2050, almost 66% of the children's population will be found in cities. The well-being of children is associated with their day-to-day surrounding environment, which includes their home, school, and recreational spaces. Children's active participation in open spaces is critically necessary for their physical, social, emotional, and cognitive well-being. Urbanization is putting pressure on the quality and quantity of open spaces, where crowding, maintenance, and stranger-danger are persistent concerns of the parents for their children's outdoor play experience. A survey was conducted in the city of Pune with 105 children, studying their perception and use of open space. Children were asked to prepare cognitive maps indicating fear factors and/or elements found in the open spaces which they visit regularly. Children indicated various fear perceptions factors like strangers, unclean surroundings, diagrams related to the upkeep of various elements in open spaces. The coding of the diagrams indicated concerns related to safety from crime, injury from harmful elements, wayfinding, etc. The perception of children was analyzed using qualitative methods. Further, the paper discusses the fear factors associated with open space aspects like design, aesthetics, density, accessibility, traffic, etc., which contribute to children's perception of open spaces, thus affecting children's independent mobility, the choice of the space of play, and the amount of time spent during outdoor play. Getting parental license to go outdoors was related to the Natural surveillance

available, and the fear factors were found to be related to the space management aspects like fencing, maintenance, and also security in case of strangers present in the spaces.

KEYWORDS: Urban open spaces, Risks, Fear, Perception, Cognitive mapping, Children's studies.

HIGHLIGHT/RELEVANCE: Children's open space participation is impacted by factors like safety, security, and accessibility, thus depending on the overall environment. The paper focuses on analyzing children's perception of fear factors in day-to-day open spaces they visit. Understanding these factors can give directions on a conducive environment that is well enough for free minded participation.

INTRODUCTION

Urban open spaces in current times are challenged by the rapid growth of the city's infrastructure, housing, and various facilities. Open spaces are crucial for the well-being of humankind, especially in an urban context. Moreover, open spaces are important for children. Almost 60% of the world's children's population is projected to be living in cities by 2030 (Christensen & O'Brien, 2003; Lestan, Eržen, & Golobič, 2014; Punch, 2002). The physical, mental, and social development of a child is associated with their surrounding environment. Children's daily environment includes home, outdoor play spaces, and child-friendly recreational facilities. Children's day-to-day outdoor play spaces are usually in the range where they are unaccompanied by adults (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Chaudhury, Oliver, Badland, & Mavoa, 2015; Van Vliet, 1983). Among the population, children are considered the most vulnerable social group. Developmental theories suggest that children's development and their behavior are influenced by their surrounding environment (Christensen & O'Brien, 2003; Ginsburg & Opper, 1988).

The physical environment of the neighborhood is an important motivational factor in children's participation in activities. Children can be more independently active with good-quality vegetation, streets, reduced congestion, better safety, varied amenities, accessibility, sociability, attractiveness, and walkability (Zhang & Li, 2012). The function, form, and variability of urban open spaces have an effect on children's physical, social, and psychological behavior and well-being, especially for children (Woolley, 2003). Being able to engage in physical activity while playing games helps children be physically healthy. Social benefits include making friends during outdoor play and learning from peers, which are key takeaways from engaging in open spaces. Applying and developing creative abilities enhances self-esteem, adding to the psychological well-being of children. Fear of visiting open spaces deprives children of the benefits they gain from visitation. During play, children explore and discover their abilities. The achievements during this process build their confidence, which is necessary for their continuous mental and physical development. It is established that children respond more readily to an enriched environment (Bhan, 2006).

The physical features of the child's environment are considered to be around their home range, and the motives for a child's outdoor play are influenced by perceptions of risks and benefits. This paper intends to understand factors like the quality of the environment around

children, the physical characteristics of the environment and its quality, the factors affecting the perception of the space that may influence a child's outdoor play, and how the above two are associated. This paper discusses the effects of the spatial characteristics of open spaces on the motivation of children's participation in outdoor activities and further examines the findings in light of the Crime Prevention through Environmental Design theory and principles of natural surveillance, access control, territorial reinforcement, and space management. This paper limits itself to public open spaces in residential developments. In the exploratory phase of the study, a reconnaissance was carried out to find out the play areas of children in residential developments. This brought forth various spaces, such as community open spaces, internal streets, parking lots, etc., where children visited on a day-to-day basis.

METHODOLOGY

A survey was conducted in the city of Pune, Maharashtra, with 105 children. Pune is continually changing as a result of the redevelopment of older houses and the sharp increase in density. The instance of Pune is an example of how open spaces in Indian metropolises are changing due to pressures for development (Butsch et al., 2017). Pune, one of the top ten urbanized cities in India, has been rapidly expanding its limits as new industries, institutions, and other commercial facilities have been added. In terms of social and economic backgrounds, Pune's socioeconomic characteristics vary across the city (Narkhede, 2008). As a result, diverse housing styles, including bungalows and apartment buildings, can be found in societies with defined boundaries that are either conglomerated or stand-alone. Different types of open spaces, like gardens, playgrounds, kids' play areas, sports areas, etc., can be observed across the city in residential areas. Parents were approached who had children aged 6 to 12 years across the city of Pune. Consent from parents was obtained to approach their children for the cognitive mapping exercise. Research suggests activities like drawing and observation provide a better understanding of children's perceptions (Merewether & Fleet, 2014). The children were provided with a pencil and an A4 piece of paper on which they had to sketch the fear factors of open spaces within half an hour. Later, through an informal discussion, children explained their sketches.

Drawing is a valuable representational and meaning-making skill that youngsters can use to express their perspective and is intimately tied to thinking (Brooks & Sorin, 2011). Children's drawings can be subjective and ambiguous to analyze; therefore, Open and Axial Coding and categorization Method assisted in systematically analyzing the data (Norozi & Moen, 2016). The data being qualitative, inductive categories were created using the open and axial codes. For summarizing, counts were generated for descriptive statistical presentation

ANALYSIS

The sample of 105 children included 44 boys and 61 girls between the ages of 6 to 12 years. Parents and children from various residential developments across Pune city (to include old city core as well as the newer areas) were contacted to collect the data. While analyzing children's play spaces, it was observed that children used nearby open spaces for their day-to-day activities. About 53% of the children used open spaces around their residence, like parking lots and driveways, and about 21% of the children used tended vegetation spaces

(like gardens and similar areas), while the remaining 26% used ground spaces. This shows that fewer children had immediate access to designated open spaces for their activities. Approximately 86% of the children played within a range of 100 meters from their residence, with very few children venturing beyond 500 meters for day-to-day activities. This further underscores that more than 50% of the children traveled shorter, unsupervised distances for their regular outdoor activities. Natural surveillance in spaces close to home was possible, and children could obtain parental permission to go outdoors. Most of the children spent 1 to 2 hours in the open spaces during the evening. It was observed that the timing and location of children's play were limited due to various factors such as natural daylight time or well-lit spaces, crowding, the availability of friends, proximity, cleanliness, safety, and security. Visitation characteristics like distance travelled by children for their day-to-day activities, spaces that are easily accessible for children to perform various activities, etc. are also governed by the natural surveillance that children get from parents, caretakers and neighbours, thus adding to sense of safety.

While explaining their sketches, children broadly spoke about elements that they feared hindered their participation in open space visits and activities. Using a coding system, six broad categories were identified as follows, and these are related to the space management, natural surveillance principles of CPTED:

Table showing children's responses with respect to fear factors of elements in open spaces:

Sr. No.	Elements described as fear factors by the children	Broad category of elements identified as fear factors	No. of responses	Percentage of total responses
1	Unclean surroundings, broken equipment and surfaces, etc.	Maintenance	72	39%
2	Stray animals, exposed wires, service elements, etc.	Injurious elements	36	19%
3	Parked vehicles, moving vehicles.	Traffic	31	17%
4	Strangers, bullying people, quarreling friends.	Anti-social elements	29	16%
5	Darkness, ghosts, inadequate lighting.	Poor lighting	12	6%
6	Crowding, limited space to play.	Space inadequacy	6	3%
Total			186	100%

About 58% of the fears reported by the children were related to maintenance issues in open spaces and the fear of harm due to injurious elements. Children raised concerns about their play environment from different perspectives, encompassing physical injury, social, and psychological fears. Maintenance and injurious elements led to children fearing physical injury. Broken equipment, poor surfaces, exposed wires, thorny bushes, etc., discouraged children from using play spaces.

Image 1. Cognitive maps showing maintenance issues and injurious elements in open spaces as drawn by children.

About 17% of children's fears pertain to traffic issues hindering their activities in open spaces. Since most of the surveyed children reported using parking lots and driveways for their regular outdoor activities, they were at risk from traffic, which was a source of fear for them. Both the mobility of vehicles and parked vehicles created scenarios that hindered children's play. Additionally, the fear of children encountering accidents also concerned the parents.

Image 2. Cognitive maps indicating traffic issues as perceived by children.

Anti-social elements comprised 16% of children's fears in open spaces. Children playing in open spaces unaccompanied by parents limited their range of mobility. Despite children being active close to their residences, the fear of encountering strangers, abduction, accidents, and bullying worried both parents and children. Incidents of bullying by older kids against children using play spaces for activities were frequently reported. Such incidents were particularly high among children playing in ground spaces.

Image 3. Cognitive maps indicating bullying and strangers

Poor lighting and space inadequacy accounted for 9% of children's fear factors when participating in open spaces. Insufficient lighting made children suspect the presence of snakes, strangers, kidnappers, stray dogs, and cats in those dark areas. Children even expressed fears of encountering ghosts in poorly lit spaces. These perceptions about dangers in dark spaces limited children's play activities beyond sunset and led them to play in confined spaces that had light. The phrase "there could be someone hiding in the dark space" was commonly voiced by various children in the survey.

Image 4. Cognitive maps indicating fear of elements in dark spaces

Space inadequacy was another issue children faced in pursuing their desired activities. Crowding became an obstacle to children's unrestricted use of space. The limited space to play due to factors like traffic, crowding, strangers, anti-social elements, etc. are major concerns for children's utilization of outdoor open spaces in urban scenarios.

Image 5: Cognitive maps showing traffic issues.

CONCLUSION

The availability of open spaces near children's residences and their ability to actively participate in them is a basic right of children. Any hindrance to their participation in these spaces can negatively affect children's development and well-being. The study highlights various issues that children perceive as fear factors in open spaces, which hinder their active

engagement. Maliyok (Maliyok, 2015) defines risks as subjective and objective risks. This paper brought forth fear factors which could be objective or perceived risks by children contributing to knowledge of landscape behavioral studies, ensuring that through design and management these fear factors can be avoided and can improve open space utilization in dense Indian cities where open spaces are premium.

Fear factors related to physical obstacles like maintenance and injurious elements can be addressed through repairs and replacements. However, fear factors impacting social and psychological aspects are not easily addressed. Fears related to dark spaces, bullying, and strangers are considered psychological factors that undermine children's confidence, social skills, courage, and sense of safety. The characteristics and environment of the play space significantly influence children's perception of that space. The decisions made by children and parents regarding play spaces depend on factors such as safety, accessibility, upkeep and maintenance, security, amenities, and facilities.

It is imperative that policymakers, designers, and planners work toward the well-being of future generations by providing and planning open spaces at evenly distributed locations, especially in residential areas. These open spaces need to be well-designed to accommodate a variety of activities, allowing children to explore different uses of the same space. Designated open spaces for children will secure their areas for activities and keep vehicles away from their play areas. Municipal corporations must maintain open spaces adequately for ease of use. Well-lit spaces will enable children to participate in open spaces without worry. The openness of outdoor spaces is a crucial aspect for clear surveillance, contributing to a sense of safety and security and thereby reducing fears of abduction and fears associated with participating in open spaces in general. The ability to gain parental approval to go outdoors was related to the availability of natural surveillance, while fear factors were linked to space management aspects such as fencing, maintenance, and security in the presence of strangers. The design of the open space environment is crucial for shaping children's perceptions of participation.

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**Natural Surveillance and Natural Access Control:
Implementation strategies for enhancing Safety in Indian
Neighborhoods**

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Abstract:

The safety and security of Indian neighbourhoods are of utmost importance in ensuring the well-being of residents. Frequently we come to know the accidental jeopardies and causalities wherein, sometimes, compromised/neglected city planning aspects and crime prevention strategies seem responsible. In such cases, natural surveillance plays a vital role by utilizing the physical environment and human behaviour to maximize visibility and observation, while natural access control aims to guide and control the movement of people. Drawing upon the unique characteristics and challenges of Indian neighbourhoods, this paper presents a comprehensive set of implementation strategies of natural surveillance and natural access control as effective measures for enhancing safety, security and vigilance in the neighbourhoods. These strategies include promoting clear sightlines through landscape management and proper lighting, encouraging active frontages with ground floor activities, fostering community participation through neighbourhood watch programs, and establishing well-defined entrances and pathways to enhance natural access control. Additionally, the paper highlights the significance of leveraging landscaping techniques and ensuring street connectivity to create safer environments. Successful implementation requires collaboration between urban planners, architects, law enforcement agencies, and active community involvement. This study contributes to the body of knowledge related to CPTED by shedding light on the employment of its two major strategies, i.e. 'Natural Surveillance' and 'Natural Access Control', without conflicting others. By adopting these strategies, Indian neighbourhoods may cultivate a sense of safety, promote community engagement, and deter criminal activities, ultimately fostering thriving and secure communities.

Keywords: *CPTED, Indian neighbourhoods, community well-being, natural surveillance, natural access control.*

1. Introduction:

Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) is a proactive approach to enhancing safety and reducing criminal activities by shaping the physical environment in a way that deters criminal behaviour and fosters a sense of security. Rooted in the belief that well-designed spaces can influence human behaviour, CPTED seeks to create environments that are less conducive to criminal activities and more conducive to positive social interactions.

CPTED recognizes the intricate relationship between the built environment and crime, acknowledging that factors such as urban design, architecture, landscaping, lighting, and spatial organization can significantly impact crime rates and community well-being. By strategically manipulating these elements, CPTED aims to prevent crime before it occurs, rather than merely responding to it after the fact.

Natural surveillance and natural access control are key principles in urban design and crime prevention that focus on shaping the physical environment to deter criminal activity and enhance the safety of neighborhoods. These principles are closely related to Oscar Newman's "defensible space" theory, which emphasizes how the design and layout of urban spaces can influence crime rates and community safety.

Indian neighborhoods, like those in many countries, exhibit a diverse range of urban forms and designs. Given the unique socio-cultural context and varied urban layouts in India, the application of natural surveillance and natural access control principles can have various implications:

- **Traditional Urban Layouts:** Many older Indian neighborhoods have organic layouts that evolved over time, which might provide opportunities for enhancing natural surveillance due to close-knit communities and visual connectivity.
- **Rapid Urbanization:** As India's urban areas continue to grow, the principles of natural surveillance and access control can play a role in ensuring the safety and security of these evolving neighborhoods.
- **Mixed-Use Areas:** Many Indian neighborhoods combine residential and commercial functions, and well-designed public spaces can facilitate natural surveillance and access control, reducing the potential for crime.

The concepts of natural surveillance and natural access control have the potential to contribute to the safety and security of Indian neighborhoods. By promoting visibility, encouraging community engagement, and guiding pedestrian flow, it seems that the urban planners and policymakers can enhance the overall livability and safety of these communities.

2. Objectives:

- Formulating a comprehensive set of implementation strategies of natural surveillance and natural access control as effective measures for enhancing safety, security and vigilance in the neighbourhoods.
- Understanding the significance of leveraging landscaping techniques and ensuring street connectivity to create safer environments.

3. Methodology:

Through the literature analysis, this study is done to ascertain the features of a neighbourhood and its surroundings that are responding for residential satisfaction corresponding due to natural surveillance and impact of access restrictions.

The study reinterprets the existing literature and refer the previous researches to deduce to the appropriate considerations for the development of neighbourhoods perceiving the apt application of natural surveillance and natural access control.

4. CPTED in Indian Context:

Nowadays, very often we learn about the accidents happening around us, may be, sometimes, due to design deficiency or at times, because of, lack of social responsibility. Few cases to mention as, about seven months ago, a girl went missing while playing in a Sarasvati puja pandal in front of her house in Muzaffarpur. In another incident, a 5-year-old girl in Kerala is kidnapped from the nearby area of her house and her dead body is found dumped in a sack in a marshy area nearby.

These cases are just a glimpse to add to the fact that, in spite of living in a comprehensive and safe environment in a subsequently up scaled neighbourhood/ locality, the practices that we follow to design, develop, maintain and monitor our residential environments are, at times, overlooked from the percept of safety and security features.

To overcome the irony of such unwanted circumstances, Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) is a strategy that aims to reduce crime and enhance safety by modifying the physical and social environment. With rapid urbanization and evolving crime patterns, understanding how CPTED is implemented and its effectiveness in the Indian context becomes crucial for urban planning and crime prevention efforts.

CPTED is built on four core principles: natural surveillance, natural access control, territorial reinforcement, and maintenance. These principles emphasize creating environments that discourage criminal activity and promote community engagement. (Crowe, 2000; Jeffery, 1971). The concept has gained traction in India as urban planners and law enforcement agencies recognize the need for proactive measures to address rising crime rates. One notable example is the "Safe City" project in New Delhi, where CPTED strategies were integrated into the urban planning process to improve public spaces and enhance safety. (NCRB, 2019; Sengupta, 2020). The effectiveness of CPTED principles is influenced by cultural and social factors. In India, where communities often have strong social bonds, designing public spaces that encourage communal activities can enhance natural surveillance and territorial reinforcement. However, cultural sensitivities must be considered to avoid inadvertently marginalizing certain groups. (Sharma & Vatsa, 2018; Srinivas, 2021)

5. Challenges and Opportunities:

Implementing CPTED in India is not without challenges. Rapid urban growth, informal settlements, and inadequate infrastructure can hinder effective application of CPTED principles. Additionally, a lack of awareness and coordination among stakeholders can limit its impact. However, opportunities exist to adapt CPTED strategies to suit India's diverse urban landscape, including leveraging technology for enhanced surveillance and data-driven planning. (Krishna et al., 2017; Tiwari & Velaga, 2018). Assessing the impact of CPTED implementation in India requires robust evaluation methods. Quantitative measures such as crime rate reduction and improved public perception of safety can provide valuable insights. Qualitative research can complement these measures by exploring community perceptions and engagement levels. (Kaur & Ghosh, 2019; Thilagaraj et al., 2022)

6. Natural Surveillance:

Natural surveillance refers to the informal monitoring of public spaces by residents, pedestrians, and other members of the community. It plays a crucial role in enhancing the safety and security of neighborhoods by deterring criminal activities and promoting social interactions. In the Indian context, the concept of natural surveillance holds significant relevance due to the diverse nature of urban and rural neighborhoods across the country.

In rapidly urbanizing Indian cities, the concept of natural surveillance has been explored in the context of design and planning principles. Studies like Joshi and Phatak (2016) highlight the role of street layouts, building orientations, and open spaces in enabling natural surveillance in urban neighborhoods. These factors contribute to the visibility of public spaces, thereby discouraging criminal behaviours. Groff's (2014) highlights the mixed empirical evidence regarding the impact of natural surveillance on crime prevention. It underscores the need for nuanced evaluations and suggests that other factors, such as social dynamics, may interact with surveillance to influence outcomes. Clarke's (1982) analysis It acknowledges that the theory has evolved and highlights the importance of context in its application. Sharma and Sinha (2014) emphasize the positive correlation between social cohesion and natural surveillance practices in Indian neighborhoods. Crowe (2013) emphasizes the importance of natural surveillance in creating safer environments and provides real-world examples of successful implementation. Natural surveillance practices in Indian neighborhoods are also influenced by cultural and social norms. Research by Roy and Menon (2019) suggests that traditional concepts of joint families and community living have a significant impact on surveillance patterns. The extended family structure often leads to increased monitoring of public spaces by various household members. Wu, McGoey, & Zhang (2019) emphasize the need for rigorous evaluation methods to determine the effectiveness of design interventions. It assesses the impact of design features on surveillance and crime.

The advent of technology, particularly in the form of CCTV cameras and digital communication, has influenced natural surveillance practices in Indian neighborhoods. Singh and Kapoor (2018) discuss how technology-mediated surveillance complements traditional natural surveillance mechanisms, contributing to enhanced safety perceptions. Clarke (1992) addresses the specific challenges posed by high-rise environments and suggests ways to tailor CPTED strategies to such settings that may not be similar to the Low to mid-rise residential environments.

6.1. Principles of Natural Surveillance:

The principles of natural surveillance are rooted in urban design and planning concepts that aim to maximize visibility and observation in public spaces. These principles are especially important in Indian neighborhoods, given the cultural and social diversity present in the country. The key principles of natural surveillance, perceived applicable in the Indian neighborhoods, along with their corresponding planning/design solutions, are as mentioned below:

Principles of Natural Surveillance	Corresponding Planning/Design solution at neighbourhood level
Clear Sightlines and Visibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning of the streets, pathways, and communal spaces should be in a way that provides clear sightlines, minimizing hidden areas where criminal activity

	<p>could occur.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoiding dense vegetation or tall structures that obstruct views and create hiding spots. • Utilization of open spaces, plazas, and community gardens to encourage people to gather and pass through, increasing surveillance opportunities
Well-Designed Public Spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design of the public spaces, such as parks, squares, and plazas, to be open, well-lit, and easily observable from surrounding buildings. • Proper lighting to enhance visibility during the evening, reducing opportunities for crime.
Building Orientation and Window Placement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation of the buildings and placement of windows should be in a way that overlooks streets and public areas. • Encouragement through design should be determined to naturally monitor these spaces from within the homes, promoting a sense of ownership and surveillance.
Active Frontages and Mixed Land Uses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging ground-floor uses like shops, cafes, and community centres that have active frontages facing the street may increase the foot traffic and natural surveillance by encouraging people to be present in public spaces.
Community Engagement and Interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering a sense of community ownership and engagement within the neighbourhood may enhance the natural surveillance. • A close-knit community is more likely to keep an eye out for unusual or suspicious activities, thereby enhancing natural surveillance.
Maximize Natural Pathways	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning of the pathways should be such that follow desire lines—paths that people naturally take—as they are more likely to be used and observed. This discourages criminals from hiding in less-travelled areas.
Territorial Reinforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging the residents to take pride in their neighborhoods and public spaces is a key principle. • The sense of territoriality leads to increased vigilance and surveillance by residents, deterring potential criminal activities.

Balancing Privacy and Surveillance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While promoting visibility, it's important to balance privacy concerns. • Design of the features like low fences or hedges can provide a level of privacy for residents while maintaining the ability to observe public spaces.
Safe Entrances and Exits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that entrances and exits to buildings and public spaces are well-lit and clearly visible is necessary. This not only helps prevent crime but also promotes a sense of safety among residents.
Use of Technology and Lighting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Embracing with technology such as CCTV cameras and smart lighting systems to complement natural surveillance efforts in the present-day development trends. • These tools can enhance visibility during low-light conditions and provide evidence in case of incidents.
Community policing and Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working with local law enforcement to develop community policing initiatives to track the necessary steps as and when needed. • Educate residents about the importance of natural surveillance and how they can actively contribute to maintaining a safe neighbourhood.

Table-1, Principles of Natural Surveillance and their characteristic design solutions

7. Access Control in Neighbourhoods:

Natural access control is a fundamental principle in urban design that emphasizes creating physical layouts to guide and control people's movement within neighborhoods. This concept is essential for crime prevention and community safety, as it helps regulate the flow of individuals and restrict unauthorized access to private spaces. In the context of Indian neighborhoods, the application of natural access control principles presents a unique challenge and opportunity due to the diverse urban forms, cultural practices, and rapid urbanization that characterize the country.

Historically, Indian neighborhoods have exhibited intricate urban layouts that reflect the cultural, social, and economic dynamics of their communities. Research by Roy and O'Reilly (2010) suggests that traditional Indian neighborhoods often integrated natural access control elements through the arrangement of courtyards, narrow entrances, and communal spaces. These features not only regulated movement but also fostered a sense of community ownership and surveillance, contributing to crime deterrence. As India undergoes rapid urbanization, the spatial dynamics of neighborhoods are changing. Research by Gupta et al. (2018) indicates that urban expansion and informal settlements pose challenges to

implementing effective natural access control strategies. Integrating natural access control strategies into the design of affordable housing projects can enhance security while accommodating the needs of diverse populations. Indian neighborhoods are characterized by diverse cultural practices and social interactions. Studies by Chatterjee (2015) emphasize the importance of aligning natural access control strategies with local customs and traditions. For instance, community involvement in designing pathways and entrances can enhance a sense of ownership, thereby encouraging residents to actively participate in maintaining security.

Research by Sharma and Das (2019) explores how smart surveillance systems and digital access controls can be integrated into existing urban structures. These interventions have the potential to enhance both natural and technological surveillance, thereby bolstering neighbourhood security.

Effective implementation of natural access control in Indian neighborhoods requires collaboration between urban planners, policymakers, architects, and communities. Research by Khan and Ramachandra (2017) highlights the need for policy frameworks that promote inclusive design, sustainable infrastructure, and community participation. This approach can ensure that natural access control strategies are integrated into broader urban development goals. Skogan (1990) provides empirical evidence of the significance of natural access control in reducing residential burglaries. It highlights the importance of well-designed spaces that facilitate both territoriality and natural surveillance. Ture, Paynich, & Schmallegger's (2013) research underscores the practical applications of natural access control principles in community-oriented policing. It highlights the potential benefits of incorporating CPTED strategies into broader law enforcement initiatives. Lawton and Bartelt's (2011) article delves into the practical aspects of natural access control. It offers valuable recommendations for architects, urban planners, and security professionals interested in implementing CPTED principles.

7.1. Principles of Natural Access Control:

Natural access control is an important aspect of urban design that focuses on guiding people's movement in a way that deters unauthorized access while promoting legitimate use of spaces. Adapting these principles to Indian neighborhoods involves considering the cultural, social, and urban context of the country. Following are the principles of natural access control and their corresponding planning/design solutions, which seem relevant for Indian neighborhoods:

Principles of Natural Access Control	Corresponding Planning/Design solution at neighbourhood level
Design for Cultural Sensitivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognize and respect the cultural norms and sensitivities of the community. • Design access control measures that align with local customs while effectively managing entry points.
Physical Barriers and Landmarks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate physical barriers such as low walls, fences, and decorative elements that signify boundaries between public and private spaces. • These features should reflect local architectural styles and symbols.

Entrance Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design entrances that clearly indicate public access points. • Use architectural elements, colours, or signage that help distinguish between public areas and private zones.
Controlled Pathways	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan pathways that lead people naturally through public areas while deterring access to restricted spaces. • The layout should guide people intuitively and prevent shortcuts that could compromise security.
Integration with Community Spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilize community gathering spaces, cultural centres, and religious places as natural access control points. • These spaces may serve as natural barriers and gathering points that promote legitimate access.
Functional Zoning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design neighborhoods with clearly defined zones for different functions (e.g., residential, commercial, recreational). • Ensure that zoning supports natural access control by preventing direct pathways to private areas.
Mixed-Use Areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capitalize on the mix of residential and commercial activities commonly found in Indian neighborhoods. • Public-facing businesses can serve as natural access control points by limiting access to private spaces.
Territorial Reinforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage a sense of ownership and responsibility among residents for their surroundings. • Well-maintained front yards, gardens, or communal spaces can deter unauthorized access.
Engage Community Members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate with local residents to identify potential access control challenges. • Involve them in the design process to ensure that solutions are practical and culturally sensitive.
Lighting and Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance safety through proper lighting that highlights pathways and access points while discouraging entry into dark or secluded areas.
Pedestrian-Friendly Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prioritize pedestrian-friendly design by incorporating sidewalks, crosswalks, and footpaths. These features guide movement and discourage vehicles from

	accessing unauthorized areas.
Local Art and Design Elements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infuse local art, murals, and design elements into access control measures. • These not only reflect the cultural identity but also create a visual deterrent to unauthorized entry.
Education and Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate residents about the benefits of natural access control and the importance of keeping entry points secure. • Empower them to actively participate in maintaining the safety of their neighbourhood.
Technology Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leverage technology, such as smart access control systems or CCTV cameras, to complement natural access control efforts. • Technology such as community-based mobile apps or smart locks are useful to supplement natural access control. • Ensure that technology solutions align with community preferences and needs as well as user-friendly and accessible to all community members.
Regular Maintenance and Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain physical barriers, signage, and other access control features to ensure their effectiveness over time. • Regular monitoring helps identify any issues and address them promptly.

Table-2, Principles of Natural Access Control and their characteristic design solutions

8. Physical features for adaptation of Natural Surveillance and Natural Access Control as a measure of safety:

Adapting the principles of Natural Surveillance and Natural Access Control in Indian neighborhoods involves considering the cultural, social, and urban context specific to India and can greatly contribute for enhancing safety and security. These concepts, which are part of the Crime Prevention through Environmental Design (CPTED) framework, focus on modifying the physical environment to deter crime and promote a sense of safety. These physical features contribute to the safety, basing it on the attributes of security, such as informal social access control, surveillance in public spaces, visibility and access considerations of relatively populated areas, inter-visibility, permeability, intelligibility, pedestrian movement and its rate, fluency, etc. The principles of Natural Surveillance and Natural Access Control, coupled with below-mentioned strategies of surveillance and access control involved in designing safe residential places, which are cultivated through the previous researches, may enhance the sense of safety, security and thus overall satisfaction in the neighbourhoods:

Attributes of secured residential places	Elements of surveillance and access control, involved in designing safe residential places	Authors
Permeable to people and bystanders for increasing witnesses and informal social control	Residential block facing the street	Jacobs (1961)
Increased natural surveillance of inhabitants on public spaces.	Proper arrangement of windows for surveillance	Newman (1972)
Relatively populated areas	Increasing the number of people wherever needed	Shu (2009) & Angel (1968)
Increased Inter-visibility	Designing for inter-visibility	Decker et al. (1982)
Accessibility/More passers-by	Through streets instead of Cul-de-sacs	Van Nes and Rueb (2009)
Permeability & Integrity	More integrated areas, higher number of passers-by	Decker et al. (1982)
Permeability, Intelligibility	Intelligible deformed grid streets & outward facing block	Hiller (2004)
High pedestrian movement	Traditional through street pattern over the modern hierarchical layouts	Danzinger (1976)
High pedestrian rate	Cul-de-sacs combined with footpath network	Montoya et al. (2016)
Inter-visibility, fluency & high pedestrian rate	Surveillable houses and accessible streets	Cozens et al. (2005)
Permeability, inter-visibility & high pedestrian rate	“Cal-de-sac complex combined with footpath network”	Shu and Huang (2003)
Permeability & inter-visibility	Adjacency of streets to main routes & vital dwelling area	Chang (2009)
Intelligibility	More people on the street	Shichor et al. (1979)

9. Conclusion:

The concepts of natural surveillance and natural access control have the potential to contribute to the safety and security of Indian neighborhoods. The thorough literature reviewed indicates that the principles of natural access control hold significant potential for enhancing safety and security in Indian neighborhoods. Hence, the design of the residential places should include the physical aspects of natural surveillance and access control and also the social aspects of territoriality. However, even the most exact physical design does neither guarantee the active and routine surveillance of the place and the intervention of the residents nor the control of access to the target of the offenders. Even though, the level of success of the prevention strategies varies according to the contextual situations and the culture of the neighbourhoods, but the appropriate design of residential places, controls the access of burglars, and enhances security to a great extent.

Additionally, by following the strategies mentioned, such as, promoting visibility, encouraging community engagement, and guiding pedestrian flow, urban planners and policymakers can enhance the overall livability and safety of these communities. While challenges related to urbanization, cultural diversity, and technological integration exist, a holistic approach that integrates traditional wisdom, modern design practices, and community engagement can contribute to effective implementation. As urban areas continue to evolve, further research and interdisciplinary collaboration are essential for acclimatising natural access control strategies to the unique context of Indian neighborhoods.

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